

**Proceedings of Conference of Annual Conference of the North-West
Chapter of the Indian Association of Pathologists
and Microbiologists (NWIAPM-2026)**

5th APRIL 2026

**Organized by
Department of Pathology, Pt. B.D. Sharma Post Graduate
Institute of Medical Sciences, Rohtak, Haryana**

Editor-in-chief
Dr. Sunita Singh

Editor:
Dr. Sanjay Kumar

Associate Editors:
Dr. Meenu Gill
Dr. Sumiti Gupta
Dr. Monika Gupta
Dr. Promil Jain

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A Tribute to The Legend

Dr. Anita Borges

It is with profound sorrow that we, Deptt of Pathology, join the entire pathology fraternity in mourning the passing of Dr. Anita Borges, one of India's most distinguished and beloved oncopathologist. Her demise is an irreparable loss not only to the field of pathology but to the entire medical community in India and abroad.

Dr. Borges was a legend in her own right—a beacon of knowledge, precision and compassion. As the former Head of Surgical Pathology at Tata Memorial Hospital, Dean of the Indian College of Pathologists and Vice President (Asia) of the International Academy of Pathology, she exemplified excellence in leadership, mentorship and diagnostic expertise.

On behalf of organizing committee and the entire faculty at PGIMS Rohtak, who have been inspired by her life and work, we extend our heartfelt condolences to her family, friends and all members of the pathology community. Her legacy will live on through her students, her immense contributions to cancer diagnosis and research and the countless lives she improved with her wisdom and compassion.

Prof. Ashim Kumar Ghosh
Governor, Haryana

प्रो० असीम कुमार घोष
राज्यपाल, हरियाणा

HLB/PRO-MSG/2026- 23
Dated- १५.02.2026

MESSAGE

I am pleased to learn that the annual conference of the North West Chapter of the Indian Association of Pathologists and Microbiologists and Regional Society of Pathologists (NWIAPM-2026) is being organized by the Department of Pathology at Pt BD Sharma Post Graduate Institute of Medical Sciences, Rohtak, on April 5, 2026, on the theme “Current Insights of Pathology.”

Pathology forms the backbone of modern medical science, playing a vital role in accurate diagnosis, disease monitoring and guiding effective treatment. In recent years, rapid technological advancements, including molecular diagnostics, digital pathology, and artificial intelligence, have significantly enhanced the precision and scope of this discipline. Conferences such as NWIAPM-2026 provide an excellent platform for academicians, researchers and practitioners to exchange knowledge, share research findings, and deliberate on emerging trends and innovations.

I am confident that this conference will foster meaningful academic discussions and encourage young pathologists and students to pursue excellence in research and clinical practice. I extend my best wishes to the organizers, faculty members and participants for the grand success of the conference.

(Prof Ashim Kumar Ghosh)

आरती सिंह राव
Arti Singh Rao

D.O. No. HM-2026/36

स्वास्थ्य, चिकित्सा शिक्षा एवं अनुसंधान
और आयुष मंत्री, हरियाणा ।

Health, Medical Education &
Research and Ayush Minister, Haryana

Dated, Chandigarh 10-03-26

MESSAGE

It gives me immense pleasure to convey my heartfelt greetings to all the delegates, speakers and participants of NWIAPM 2026, being held at Pt. B.D. Sharma PGIMS, Rohtak on 5th April, 2026.

This Prestigious conference brings together experts in Pathology, promoting scientific dialogue and exchange of innovative ideas crucial to enhancing our healthcare system.

I congratulate the organizing team for their commitment to excellence and wish the conference every success in its mission to advance medical knowledge and public health.

(Arti Singh Rao)

Dr. Sunita Singh
Organizing Chairperson
NWIAPM-2026
Sr. Prof & Head
Deptt. Of Pathology
PGIMS, Rohtak

Dr. Sumita Misra, IAS

D. O. No. Spl. Sr. Secy./ACSH/2026/6080

**Addl. Chief Secretary to Govt. of
Haryana, Health/MER/Ayush
Departments**

Dated: 19.03.2026

MESSAGE

It is a matter of privilege that Pt. B.D. Sharma PGIMS, Rohtak is hosting the Annual Conference of North-West Chapter of IAPM and Regional Society of Pathologists – IAPM on 5th April, 2026.

Such academic gatherings are crucial for knowledge dissemination, scientific research and professional development in the field of medical sciences. This Conference highlights our collective commitment to improving health services, promoting research excellence and strengthening public health infrastructure.

I extend my best wishes to the organizers and participants for a productive and an enriching experience.

(Dr. Sumita Misra, IAS)

Dr. Sunita Singh
Organizing Chairperson
NWIAPM-2026
Sr. Professor & Head
Department of Pathology
Post Graduate Institute of Medical Sciences,
Rohtak.

**PANDIT BHAGWAT DAYAL SHARMA
UNIVERSITY OF HEALTH SCIENCES
ROHTAK-124001, HARYANA (INDIA)**

(NAAC Accredited)

(Established vide Haryana Act No.26 of 2008 and recognized u/s 12(B) & 2(F) of the UGC Act, 1956)

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MESSAGE

It is truly a moment of immense pleasure to learn that Department of Pathology, Pt. B.D. Sharma PGIMS, Rohtak, is hosting the Annual Conference of the North-West Chapter of IAPM and Regional Society of Pathologists- IAPM (NWIAPM 2026) on the theme "Current Insights in Pathology" on 5th April 2026. Hosting such a landmark event in the field of Pathology is a matter of immense honor for the University.

The NWIAPM 2026 Conference is an exemplary initiative promoting academic excellence, research collaboration and scientific advancement.

A particularly significant aspect of modern pathology is the growing role of Artificial Intelligence. AI-driven tools are transforming diagnostic workflows by enhancing accuracy, improving turnaround times, and supporting pathologists in handling increasing workloads. From digital pathology and image analysis to predictive analytics and decision support systems, AI holds immense potential to complement human expertise while maintaining high standards of quality and safety.

I am delighted to welcome all distinguished participants, speakers and delegates to Pt. B. D. Sharma PGIMS, Rohtak, with the confidence that the knowledge-sharing and academic interactions at this conference will significantly contribute to the future of medical sciences and improve public health outcomes.

I extend my warm greetings and felicitations to the participating delegates, organizers, faculty members and send my best wishes for the success of the Conference NWIAPM 2026.

Prof. (Dr.) H.K. Aggarwal
Vice-Chancellor

MESSAGE

I am pleased to learn that the Department of Pathology, Pt. B.D. Sharma PGIMS, Rohtak, is hosting the Annual Conference of the North West Chapter of IAPM & Regional Society of Pathologists – IAPM (NWIAPM 2026). The theme of the conference is “Current Insights in Pathology.” Guided by the motto “Inquisitive Minds, Nurturing Science,” is highly motivating PGIMS Rohtak is a premier tertiary care teaching institution of North India established in 1960 and renowned for its Excellence in Medical Education, Patient Care, and Research. I am indebted to the Department, especially Dr Sunita Singh, Sr. Prof. & Head, Deptt. of Pathology & Organising Chairperson. Dr Sanjay Kumar, Prof. Deptt. of Pathology, Organising Secretary and the whole Department for putting up their efforts to chalk out the beautiful academic feast as a sizzler platter to delegates & faculty coming from all over India. I extend my warm welcome from Pt. B.D. Sharma PGIMS, Rohtak, and wish you all the best for a day-long deliberation, didactic lectures, panel discussion & interactions with masters in their field. I am hopeful that it will stimulate the students and delegates to carry the knowledge into their practice.

Jai Hind Jai Bharat!

Dr Suresh Kumar Singhal
Director
Pt. B.D. Sharma UHS, Rohtak

**PANDIT BHAGWAT DAYAL SHARMA
UNIVERSITY OF HEALTH SCIENCES, ROHTAK**

ROHTAK - 124001, HARYANA, INDIA

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(Established vide Haryana Act No.26 of 2008 and recognized u/s 12(B) & 2(f) of the UGC Act, 1956)
Phone: 01262-282709, E-mail: registrar@uhsr.ac.in Web Site: www.uhsr.ac.in

MESSAGE

It is a matter of great pride and pleasure that the Department of Pathology, Pt. B.D. Sharma Post Graduate Institute of Medical Sciences, Rohtak, is hosting NWIAPM 2026 under the aegis of the North-West Chapter of the Indian Association of Pathologists and Microbiologists (IAPM) and the Regional Society of Pathologists–IAPM on 5th April 2026.

This prestigious academic event provides an excellent platform for academicians, researchers, clinicians, and experts to come together, deliberate on recent advancements, exchange ideas, and explore emerging trends in the field of Pathology. Such scientific interactions play a vital role in strengthening research, enhancing professional knowledge, and fostering meaningful collaborations.

I am confident that the conference will inspire intellectual growth and contribute significantly to the advancement of Pathology and medical science. I extend my warmest greetings to all the delegates and organizers and wish NWIAPM 2026 a grand success.

R. Sharma
05/02/26

REGISTRAR

REGISTRAR
Pandit Bhagwat Dayal Sharma
University of Health Sciences,
ROHTAK

MESSAGE

It is with great pride and joy that I extend my warm greetings to all delegates, speakers and participants of NWIAPM 2026, being organised by the Department of Pathology, Pt. B. D. Sharma PGIMS, Rohtak. Hosting this prestigious annual conference of the North West chapter Indian Association of Pathologists and Microbiologists and the Regional Society of Pathologists-IAPM is both an honour and a privilege for our institute.

I extend my best wishes for the grand success of NWIAPM 2026.

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'M.G. Vashisht', written over a light blue rectangular background.

Dr. M.G. Vashisht
Dean of Academic Affairs,
Pt. B.D. Sharma UHS, Rohtak

OFFICE OF THE DEAN, PGIMS ROHTAK
MESSAGE

Telephone No. 01262-281309
E-mail ID: dean.pgims@uhsr.ac.in
Dean.pgims@hry.nic.in

It gives me immense pleasure to know that the Department of Pathology is organising the Annual Conference of the North West Chapter of IAPM and the Regional Society of Pathologists at PGIMS Rohtak. The spectrum of Pathology is rapidly expanding, and newer technology in the field of Pathology in the detection of diseases plays a pivotal role in the management of the patient. The theme of the conference 'Current Insights in Pathology' is aptly chosen, keeping in view the advancement in technology, especially the AI and molecular applications in the field of medical education and diagnosis. The advancement and sharing of the current knowledge amongst academicians and practitioners is of paramount importance to deliver personalised and precise treatment for various ailments.

I hope the conference will be tremendously successful in achieving its theme.

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to be 'A.S.' or similar, written in a cursive style.

Dr. Ashok Chauhan
Dean
Pt. B.D. Sharma PGIMS, Rohtak

Pt. Bhagwat Dayal Sharma, PGIMS, Rohtak
Office of Medical Superintendent

Contact No:- 01262-281311

Email :-ms.pgims@uhsr.ac.in

It gives me immense pleasure to extend my warmest greetings and heartiest congratulations to the North West Chapter of the IAPM and the Regional Society of Pathologists on the occasion of **NWIAPM 2026**.

The theme of this year's conference, "**Current Insights in Pathology**," is both timely and essential. As we navigate an era of unprecedented medical advancement, the field of Pathology has transitioned from the microscope to the molecular level, bridging the gap between basic science and precision medicine. At PGIMS, Rohtak, we have always recognized that a clinician's decision is only as strong as the diagnostic foundation provided by the pathologist.

Why This Gathering Matters:

- Precision Diagnostics:** With the integration of AI and digital pathology, the "Gold Standard" is becoming more accurate and efficient than ever.
- Collaborative Learning:** This conference serves as a vital platform for seasoned experts and budding residents to exchange ideas that will eventually translate into better patient care.
- Innovation:** Exploring "Current Insights" ensures that our regional medical community remains at the forefront of global diagnostic trends.

I commend the organizing committee for their tireless efforts in bringing together distinguished faculty and delegates to our prestigious institution. I am certain that the deliberations held here will spark new perspectives and strengthen the academic rigor of our fraternity.

I wish all the participants a productive and intellectually stimulating conference. May this souvenir serve as a lasting testament to the knowledge shared and the professional bonds forged during this event.

Dr Kundan Mittal
Medical Superintendent
PGIMS, Rohtak

MESSAGE

It is with great pride and joy that I extend my warm greetings to all delegates, speakers and participants of NWIAPM 2026, being organised by the Department of Pathology, Pt. B. D. Sharma PGIMS, Rohtak. Hosting this prestigious Annual conference of the North West Chapter of the Indian Association of Pathologists and Microbiologists and the Regional Society of Pathologists-IAPM (Haryana Chapter) is both an honour and a privilege for us.

The theme of NWIAPM 2026, "Current Insights in Pathology," aptly reflects the transition of our discipline into a new era of precision diagnostics, research innovations, and patient-centred care. This conference brings together eminent experts, dedicated faculty, and enthusiastic students from across the country to share knowledge, exchange ideas, and inspire future generations in pathology.

On behalf of the Organising Committee, I express my gratitude to the leadership of IAPM, distinguished faculty and all delegates for their encouragement and participation. I am confident that NWIAPM 2026 will be a memorable academic feast, fostering learning, collaboration and camaraderie among Pathologists across the region.

I wish the conference and all its deliberations a grand success and extend a warm welcome to all to our beautiful education city, Rohtak.

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Sunita Singh', with a horizontal line underneath.

Dr. Sunita Singh
Organising Chairperson
NWIAPM 2026
PGIMS, Rohtak

MESSAGE

It is indeed a matter of immense pride and gratitude that we have been allowed to host the prestigious NWIAPM 2026, the Annual Conference of the North West Chapter of the Indian Association of Pathologists and Microbiologists, along with the Annual Conference of the Regional Society of Pathologists-IAPM (Haryana Chapter) in the Department of Pathology, Pt. B.D. Sharma PGIMS, Rohtak, on 5th April 2026. The theme for the conference is " Current Insights in Pathology". Organising this event has been both a privilege and a profound learning experience. I take this moment to express my heartfelt gratitude to the dedicated team, who have worked tirelessly, often beyond their comfort zones, to ensure that every aspect of this conference reflects excellence. The commitment, perseverance and teamwork have been the true strength behind this endeavour. This conference is not just an academic gathering but also an opportunity to curate a rich academic feast. We take pride in blending science with culture, knowledge with artistry and learning with celebration.

The journey throughout these past few months has indeed been challenging, marked by numerous hurdles and unforeseen circumstances. Yet, guided by the invaluable lessons of my mentors, to never give up, stand strong even when alone and to turn every challenge into an opportunity, we have strived forward. The blessings of my seniors, the cooperation of my colleagues and the unwavering support of the residents have made this journey not only possible but deeply fulfilling. As we come together for NWIAPM 2026, I hope that this event leaves an enduring impression academically enriching, culturally vibrant and emotionally memorable for all.

A handwritten signature in blue ink that reads "Sanjay Kumar". The signature is fluid and cursive.

Dr. Sanjay Kumar
Organising Secretary
NWIAPM 2026
PGIMS, Rohtak

Prof. Dr Asaranti Kar, MD, FICP
President, IAPM
Prof. & HOD, Pathology
SCB Medical College, Cuttack, Odisha

Dear delegates & members of IAPM,

A warm welcome to all of you on the occasion of NWIAPM-2026, the Annual conference of the North West Chapter of the Indian Association of Pathologists and Microbiologists, along with the Annual Conference of the Regional Society of Pathologists-IAPM (Haryana Chapter), being organised on 5th April 2026 by the Dept of Pathology, Pt. B. D. Sharma PGIMS, Rohtak. The North West chapter has been active and vibrant and stood out as a cornerstone for excellence in academics. The formation of the Haryana State Chapter almost 3 years ago marks an important step toward strengthening academic collaboration and professional growth within the state. The chapter will foster continuous medical education, encourage young pathologists, and contribute meaningfully to the advancement of Pathology and patient care in the region. The scientific committee has put tremendous effort into planning the program, inclusive of deliberations from eminent pathologists, plenary sessions to provide valuable insights to both experienced and young pathologists.

This conference will serve as a valuable platform for us to exchange ideas and bridge the gap between traditional practice and modern technology. I congratulate the organising team for their tireless efforts in making up for this conference and wish them all success.

Let's make it a successful and memorable one.

“Patience, persistence and perspiration make an unbeatable combination for success.”
Jai IAPM.

MESSAGE

It is both an honour and a pleasure to warmly welcome all the delegates, esteemed faculty, and postgraduate students to this annual conference of the North West Chapter of the Indian Association of Pathologists and Microbiologists, held in conjunction with the annual conference of the Regional Society of Pathologists–IAPM (Haryana Chapter).

The NW Chapter was revived three years ago after a prolonged hiatus. Since its revival, the chapter has steadily regained momentum through the dedication and enthusiasm of its members. I sincerely hope this renewed chapter continues to flourish and remain active in the years ahead, fostering regular academic and social interactions.

I extend my sincere appreciation to the organising committee and the host institution, PGIMS, Rohtak, for their dedication and hard work in organising this conference and bringing out the souvenir. I am sure that the meeting will provide an excellent forum for the dissemination of knowledge of the latest developments in Pathology and for exchanging ideas and experiences.

I wish the conference great success and hope that it continues to inspire learning, collaboration, and innovation within our professional community.

My best wishes for a fruitful and memorable conference.

A handwritten signature in blue ink that reads "Uma Handa". The signature is written in a cursive style and is underlined.

Dr. Uma Handa
President, NWIAPM
GMC, Chandigarh

MESSAGE

It gives me immense pleasure to extend my warm greetings to all delegates, faculty members, and participants of NWIAPM 2026, being organised by the Department of Pathology, Pt. B.D. Sharma PGIMS, Rohtak. This prestigious Annual Conference of the North West chapter of the Indian Association of Pathologists and Microbiologists (IAPM) provide a unique platform for sharing knowledge, discussing advances and fostering collaborations across disciplines in our ever-evolving field.

The theme, "Current Insights in Pathology," is both timely and relevant, reflecting the dynamic transformation in diagnostic approaches and the growing influence of molecular technologies in patient care. I am confident that the deliberations, scientific sessions and interactions during this conference will foster meaningful exchange of knowledge, inspire innovative ideas and strengthen our collective commitment to advancing the frontiers of Pathology and improving patient outcomes.

I congratulate the organising team for their tireless efforts in curating an excellent scientific program and for their dedication in hosting this conference in the historic and vibrant city of Rohtak.

I extend my best wishes for the grand success of NWIAPM 2026 and hope that all participants return home with enriching experiences, new collaborations and fond memories of their time in Rohtak.

With warm regards,

A handwritten signature in blue ink that reads "Nisha Marwah". The signature is written in a cursive style with a horizontal line underneath.

Dr. Nisha Marwah
President,
Regional Society of Pathology-IAPM
PGIMS, Rohtak

MESSAGE

It gives me immense pleasure that my alma mater is hosting the Annual Conference of the North-West Chapter of the Indian Association of Pathologists and Microbiologists (NWIAPM-2026) in association with the Regional Society of Pathologists (IAPM Haryana Chapter). The theme of the conference, “Current Insights in Pathology”, reflects our collective commitment to staying abreast of the rapidly evolving landscape of Pathology. It is a matter of profound honour and gratitude to acknowledge the Organising Committee of this conference, many of whom have been my revered teachers and mentors. It is inspiring to see their leadership in curating a scientific program highlighting recent advances and practical perspectives across subspecialties. I am confident that this conference will enrich knowledge and foster meaningful professional collaboration.

I sincerely appreciate the efforts of the organising committee, Office bearers of the NW Chapter of IAPM and the Regional Society of Pathologists (IAPM Haryana Chapter), faculty, contributors, and sponsors who have worked tirelessly to make this conference and the accompanying souvenir a reality.

I also extend a warm welcome to all delegates and hope this academic endeavour proves to be intellectually rewarding and professionally fulfilling.

With best wishes for the grand success of the conference.

Mukta Pujani

Dr. Mukta Pujani
Secretary
Regional Society of Pathologists (IAPM Haryana Chapter)
Professor & HOD, Department of Pathology
ESIC Medical College & Hospital, Faridabad

Haryana - The Land of Valor, Heritage and Progress

Haryana, a state rich in history, culture and resilience, takes pride in hosting this gathering of distinguished medical professionals and scholars. Situated in the heart of North India, Haryana has witnessed defining moments in Indian civilization, from the sacred land of Kurukshetra, where the timeless wisdom of the Bhagavad Gita was delivered, to the modern era where the state stands as a symbol of progress and development. Known as the “Land of the Brave,” Haryana has made remarkable contributions to the nation through its soldiers, athletes, farmers and scholars. The fertile plains of the state form the backbone of India’s agricultural strength, while its cities continue to grow as important centers of education, healthcare, industry and innovation.

The culture of Haryana reflects simplicity, warmth and strong community values. Traditional folk dances, vibrant festivals and the rustic charm of village life beautifully coexist with rapidly developing modern institutions and infrastructure. The hospitality of the people of Haryana, often expressed through simple gestures such as sharing bajra roti and fresh lassi, creates an atmosphere of warmth and belonging for every visitor.

The state has also made significant strides in the field of medical education and healthcare. Prestigious institutions such as Pt. B. D. Sharma Post Graduate Institute of Medical Sciences (PGIMS), Rohtak, continue to play a vital role in advancing medical research, training future healthcare professionals and delivering quality patient care.

Hosting this conference in Haryana represents a confluence of tradition and transformation—where ancient wisdom meets modern science and collaborative efforts pave the way for the future of healthcare.

Where Kurukshetra echoes with the Gita’s song,
Where every dusk carries story long.
Fields in bloom and ploughs that glide,
This is Haryana, with heritage as its pride.
Rhythms of folk songs and colors of Phag,
Warm hospitality in every home’s flag.
With bajra rotis and lassi sweet,
Tradition and progress beautifully meet.
Where courage, culture and care unite,
Knowledge grows and futures shine bright.
Here we gather in learning’s embrace,
In Haryana, a land of strength and grace.

Rohtak - Where Heritage Meets Progress

Rohtak, popularly known as the “Heart of Haryana,” is a historic and vibrant city located about 70 kilometers northwest of Delhi and forms an important part of the National Capital Region. As the administrative headquarters of Rohtak district, the city has grown into a prominent center for education, healthcare and culture in the state.

The origins of Rohtak trace back to ancient times when it was known as Rohitaka. Archaeological remains at the nearby Khokhrakot mound indicate that the region has been inhabited for centuries and once served as an important center of trade and culture. Due to its proximity to Delhi, the city held strategic importance during the Delhi Sultanate and Mughal periods and during British rule it developed into a significant administrative and commercial town.

Rohtak reflects the rich cultural heritage of Haryana, where traditional customs, folk music such as Ragini and vibrant festivals including Diwali, Holi and Teej are celebrated with great enthusiasm. The cuisine of the region, known for dishes like bajra roti, kadhi and churma accompanied by fresh lassi, reflects the simplicity and warmth of Haryanvi culture.

Over the years, Rohtak has also emerged as a major educational hub with prestigious institutions such as Maharshi Dayanand University, Pt. B. D. Sharma PGIMS and IIM Rohtak, contributing significantly to academic and healthcare excellence.

As the proud host city of NWIAPM 2026, Rohtak warmly welcomes all delegates to experience its academic spirit, cultural richness and traditional hospitality.

Pt. B. D. Sharma Post Graduate Institute of Medical Sciences, Rohtak

Pt Bhagwat Dayal Sharma Post Graduate Institute of Medical Sciences (PGIMS), Rohtak, is one of the leading government medical institutions in North India, dedicated to excellence in medical education, advanced research and high-quality tertiary healthcare services. Established in 1960 as Medical College, Rohtak, the institute began its academic journey with the first batch of students undergoing initial training at Government Medical College, Patiala. In 1963, academic activities were shifted to Rohtak, marking the foundation of what has since developed into a major center for medical learning and healthcare delivery.

Spread across a sprawling 350-acre campus, PGIMS Rohtak functions under the aegis of Pt. B. D. Sharma University of Health Sciences, established in 2008 to promote specialized education and research in the health sciences. The institute serves as a major referral center for the state of Haryana and provides healthcare services to patients from neighboring regions including Punjab, Rajasthan and western Uttar Pradesh. In recognition of its academic and clinical contributions, the institute secured the 50th position among medical institutions in India in the National Institutional Ranking Framework (NIRF) rankings for 2024.

PGIMS Rohtak offers a wide range of undergraduate, postgraduate, and super-specialty programs across various disciplines of medicine and surgery. The campus houses several constituent institutions, including the Postgraduate Institute of Dental Sciences, College of Nursing, College of Physiotherapy, College of Pharmacy, and the State Institute of Mental Health (SIMH).

Over the years, the institute has significantly expanded and modernized its infrastructure to enhance both academic and clinical capabilities. Notable developments include a state-of-the-art Modular Operation Theatre-cum-ICU Complex equipped with 16 modular operating theatres, a 34-bed intensive care unit, a Central Sterile Supply Department, and advanced diagnostic laboratories. Other major facilities include the Dhanwantri Apex Trauma Centre and the Mother and Child Hospital Block, a dedicated multistorey facility providing specialized maternal, neonatal and pediatric care.

The institute achieved another historic milestone on 4 February 2024 by successfully performing Haryana's first renal transplant surgery in a government medical institution. Since then, several successful transplant procedures have been conducted, marking a significant advancement in tertiary healthcare services at the institute. In addition, a number of important projects are currently underway, including the construction of a new Administrative Block, a Central Library Block and a Post-COVID Care Research Facility aimed at advancing research on long-term health outcomes.

With its strong academic environment, advanced medical facilities and dedicated faculty, PGIMS Rohtak continues to nurture skilled healthcare professionals and promote impactful medical research. The institute remains committed to providing compassionate patient care while contributing to the advancement of healthcare and medical education in India.

Department of Pathology, PGIMS, Rohtak

The Department of Pathology at Pt. B. D. Sharma Post Graduate Institute of Medical Sciences (PGIMS), Rohtak is a vital diagnostic and academic department of the institute.

Pathology department provides comprehensive laboratory services including histopathology, cytopathology, hematology, clinical pathology, immunohistochemistry and special staining techniques. These services play a crucial role in accurate disease diagnosis, prognostication and guiding appropriate clinical management. The department works in close collaboration with various clinical specialties, contributing significantly to multidisciplinary patient care.

With advancements in Diagnostic Pathology, the department has incorporated modern techniques such as molecular diagnostics, Fluorescence In Situ Hybridization (FISH), Flow Cytometry and High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC). These advanced diagnostic modalities greatly enhance the detection and characterization of hematological malignancies, genetic abnormalities, hemoglobinopathies and other complex diseases.

The department is actively engaged in undergraduate (MBBS) and postgraduate (MD Pathology) teaching and training. The academic environment encourages residents to participate in seminars, journal clubs, research projects and clinicopathological conferences (CPCs), ensuring comprehensive academic development and diagnostic expertise.

The Pathology department is currently headed by Dr. Sunita Singh, Sr Professor and Head, under whose leadership the department continues to strive for excellence in diagnostic services, academic activities and research.

Through its dedication to quality diagnostics, academic excellence and research innovation, the Department of Pathology at PGIMS Rohtak continues to contribute significantly to the advancement of medical science and improved patient care in the region.

Pathology workload at a glance

Chief Patron

Dr H K Aggarwal
Vice Chancellor,
UHS, Rohtak

Patrons

Dr Suresh Singhal
Director,
PGIMS, Rohtak

Dr Roop Singh
Registrar,
UHS, Rohtak

Dr M G Vashist
Dean academic Affairs,
UHS, Rohtak

Dr Ashok K. Chauhan
Dean,
PGIMS, Rohtak

Dr Kundan Mittal
Medical Superintendent,
PGIMS, Rohtak

Faculty

Dr. Sunita Singh,
Sr. Professor & Head,
Deptt of Pathology,
PGIMS, Rohtak

Dr. Nisha Marwah,
Sr. Professor,
Deptt of Pathology,
PGIMS, Rohtak

Dr. Rajnish Kalra,
Professor,
Deptt. of Pathology,
PGIMS, Rohtak

Dr. Sanjay Kumar,
Professor,
Deptt. of Pathology,
PGIMS, Rohtak

Dr. Veena Gupta,
Professor,
Deptt. of Pathology,
PGIMS, Rohtak

Dr. Meenu Gill,
Professor,
Deptt. of Pathology,
PGIMS, Rohtak

Dr. Sant Prakash Kataria,
Professor,
Deptt. of Pathology,
PGIMS, Rohtak

Dr. Sumiti Gupta,
Professor,
Deptt of Pathology,
PGIMS, Rohtak

Dr. Sonia Chhabra,
Professor,
Deptt. of Pathology,
PGIMS, Rohtak

Dr. Monika Gupta,
Professor,
Deptt. of Pathology,
PGIMS, Rohtak

Dr. Promil Jain,
Professor,
Deptt. of Pathology,
PGIMS, Rohtak

Dr. Renuka Verma,
Professor,
Deptt. of Pathology,
PGIMS, Rohtak

Dr. Richa Pawar,
Associate Professor,
Deptt. of Pathology,
PGIMS, Rohtak

Dr. Usha Rani,
Assistant Professor,
Deptt. of Pathology,
PGIMS, Rohtak

Dr. Rachana,
Assistant Professor,
Deptt. of Pathology,
PGIMS, Rohtak

‘OUR ALUMNI’

1979	Ram Kanwar Garg; Ramesh Juneja; K.R. Menon; Venu Gopal Mehtani
1980	Vinay Kamal
1981	Bishan Dass Radotra; Sunaina; Satish Kumar; Rita Parmar; Balbir Singh; Gulshan Paul Saliya
1982	Sunil Kumar; Varun Kumar; Piare Lal; Raj Kumar Sharma; Vasu Kumar Dogra
1983	Krishna Mehlawat; Parsid Kumar Jain; Sandeep Vasudeva
1984	Sandeep Kalra; Manyal Rai Mittal; Sudha Abrol; Satyavir Yadav; Puram Chaudhary
1985	Krishan Kr. Sharma; Vijay Malhotra; Bharti Gupta; Sarita Sondhi
1986	Jitender Mahan Khunger; Partap Singh Sawant; P.K. Sehgal; Anita Chhabra; Uma Sharma; Anu Chadha; Sushma Batra
1987	Sunita Singh; Indu Jyoti; Renu Aggarwal; Arun Kadian; Rajvir Singh
1988	Nisha Marwah; Rajnish Kalra; Priti Dhatt; Rashmi Mehta; Rajkumar Saini; Rajkumar Gupta; Kanshi Ram Bhadu
1989	Sunita Taneja; Hiralal Beniwal; A.P. Bhatia; Charanjit Chawla
1990-91	Narender Singh; Rajpal Punia
1992	Poonam; Jagdish Rai Verma; Vandana Jain; Rajan Chopra; Sangeeta Jain; Rena Kukreja; Raj Kumar; Santosh Kumari
1993	Ritu Arora; Poonam Rani; Akiko Chugh; K. Ramamurti Beena; Surinder K.R. Mahipal; Mahi Chand Verma
1994	Raman Bala Verma; Rashi Grover; Ranjana Bali; Lata Dhawan; Alka Pasrija; Liza Joshi
1995	Veena Rani; Alpana Arora; Kanwaljeet Kaur; Vandana Rana; Ashwani Kumar; Ritu Aggarwal
1996	Alka Ganda; Ajay Sharma; Anshu Gupta; B.K. Rajora; Vandana Jain
1997	V. Priya; Rima Malhotra; Richa Jindal; D. Jeewan; Aditya Swaroop Gupta; Shashi Kumar
1998	Kavita Jindal; Bharat Rekhi; Meenu Kathpalia; Ashish Narula; Bimla Rathi
1999	Sonia Chhabra; Sunita B.S.; Seema; Rahul Jain; Varinder Bharti; Pawan Singh
2000	Savita; Pooja Verma; Niharika; Bhawna Sachdeva; Gajender Singh; Sukhbir Singh
2001	Vinika Batra; Shweta Rana; Puja; Kaushal Kr. Maheshwari; Manjeet Singh; Sapna Gahlaut
2002	Chada Pradeep Kumar; Renu; Mukta Pujani; Nidhi; Cherry Bansal; Pradeep Kumar

2003	Komal Preet Dhiran; Vidhu Kaushik; Kanchan Gulati; Megha Goel; Jitender Kaur; Anju Rawal
2004	Pratibha Dhiman; Shilpi Modi; Charu Batra; Shweta; Gagandeep Kaur; Sneh Singh
2005	Natasha Garg; Surbhi Gupta; Bhawna; Priyanka Saxena; Promil Jain; Parveen Rana
2006	Nidhi Paliwal; Natasha Gulati; Shweta; Reena Aggrawal; Sachin Rastogi; Narender Dahiya
2007	Rajni Yadav; Shilpi Garg; Sheena Khetarpal; Nitin Kr Garg; Sanchita Ghosh; Sanjay Kumar
2008	Amrita Duhan; Garima Aggarwal; Ekta Rani; Divya Sethi; Shilpa Chugh; Deepti Gupta; Gulshan Chauhan
2009	Swati Sanduja; Aman Goyal; Payal Mondal; Parul Tanwar; Manish Chaudhary; Mansi Kala; Rama Goyal
2010	Sonia Hasija; Vandana Goyal; Monika; Ashima Batra; Ashok Kumar; Rinky Langan; Arsh Gupta; Shruti Kandoi; Divya Srivastava; Samta; Jyoti
2011	Nitika Chawla; Hemant Yadav; Kanika Taneja; Renuka Verma; Shruti Semwal; Padam Parmar; Richa; Sonia Singh; Jyoti Sharma; Vivek Shorain; Kuldeep Singh
2012	Aarzo Jahan; Shivani Malik; Swagatika Samal; Megha Ralli; Manoj Kumar Shankala; Deepika Jain; Pansi Gupta; Mahesh Tayal; Rajeev Panwar; Narender Singh; Shubha Lal
2013	Mansi Agarwal; Ritika; Sonu Kalyan; Sucheta; Shalini Shah; Ashish Sharma; Meenu Gilotra; Priya Jain; Mukesh Kumar; Gurpreet Singh; Vinod Kumar
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2016	Monika; Bharti Sharma; Ritesh Kumar Sheorain; Archana; Lalit Singh; Nidhi Kaushik; Himadri Hazarika; Ayushi Saxena; Raman Kapil; Sandeep Yadav; Manish Kumar; Vipul Gupta; Reeti Saini
2017	Lovekesh Monga; Richa Sharma; Shreya Sandhu; Sonu; Arushi Goel; Jashanpreet; Gourav Tehri; Pooja Pawaria; Bharti Saklani; Anubha Gupta; Vartika Goel; Rishabh Kumar
2018	Annu Phogat; Garvita Goel; Monika Dhanker; Niharika; Shivani Singhal; Pooja; Sangeeta Bamel; Ekta Lamba; Pushpa Bisht; Tripti Jain; Nikita Prasad; Ruchika Majoka; Priyanka Rawat

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2020	Aakanksha Rawat; Akhil Kumar; Anjali Ahalawat; Anku Alisha; Deepshikha; Jyoti Dahiya; Khushboo Arora; Mahak; Nidhi Yadav; Nitika Sindhu; Pooja Rathee; Priyanka Verma; Ritu; Vibhuti
2021	Akanksha; Anjali; Dishti Sharma; Harsh Kumari; Kapil Kumar Swami; Preeti Punia; Sakshi Aggarwal; Syed Ahad Choudhary; Simran Yadav; Smruti Soumya Panigrahi; Vibhav Goel; Vaishali; Sunita
2022	Ankush; Geetika; Kshitija Attry; Mehak Jindal; Navneet Kaur; Palak Bansal; Preeti Rani; Rashmi Jangra; Ritu Pachauri; Rupali; Sahil Goel; Shivani Bhargava

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SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM

Time	Session/Topic	Speaker
8:00 AM onwards	Registration & Breakfast	
8:00 – 9:30 AM / 2:00 – 3:30 PM	Oral and Poster presentations	
9:30 – 10:00 AM	Inaugural Address	President IAPM – Dr. Asaranti Kar
10:00 – 10:40 AM	Between reactivity and malignancy: Reading the lymph node story	Dr. Sumeet Gujral
10:40 – 11:20 AM	Soft tissue tumors: Challenges and Clarity	Dr. Bharat Rekhi
11:20 – 12:00 PM	Renal biopsies demystified	Dr. Col. P. Sen Gupta
12:00 – 12:40 PM	Cervical Cancer Screening: Liquid based Cervical Cytology and Molecular Markers	Dr. Nalini Gupta
12:40 – 1:10 PM	Inauguration	
1:10 – 2:00 PM	Lunch	
2:00 – 2:40 PM	Bits and Pieces: Pathology insights in decoding of duodenal biopsies	Dr. Rajni Yadav
2:40 – 3:20 PM	PG Wizard	Dr. Uma Nahar Saikia
3:20 – 5:00 PM	Slide Safari	
5:00 – 5:30 PM	Valedictory Function & Vote of Thanks	
5:30 – 6:00 PM	General Body Meeting	

Life Time Achievement Awards

Name: Dr. Uma Singh

Qualifications:

- MBBS – M.G.M. Medical College, Indore (1967)
- MD (Pathology) – AIIMS, New Delhi (1973)
- DGO – PGIMS, Rohtak (1985)
- FIAMS (Pathology) – IMA Academy of Medical Specialties (1989)

Professional Experience:

- Faculty, Department of Pathology, PGIMS Rohtak (1973–2005):
- Senior Consultant, Shri Action Balaji Hospital, New Delhi (2005–2006)
- Professor & Head, Pathology, JNCD Dental College, Sirsa (2006–2010)
- Professor & Head, Pathology, SGT Medical College, Gurugram (2010–2015)
- Senior Consultant Pathologist, Rohtak (2015– till date)
- Highly motivated Pathologist with a keen interest in surgical pathology, specializing in the diagnostic interpretation of tissues (histopathology) and cell samples (cytopathology) to guide cancer management and personalized treatment plans.

Professional Memberships:

- Indian Association of Pathologists & Microbiologists (IAPM)
- IAPM – Haryana Chapter
- Indian Society of Hematology & Blood Transfusion (ISHBT)
- Indian Academy of Cytologists (IAC)
- Federation of Obstetric & Gynaecological Societies of India (FOGSI)
- Association of Practicing Pathologists – Haryana

Current Position:

Senior Consultant Pathologist at Vidya Pathology Centre and Nirvana Diagnostics, Rohtak.

Name: Dr. Harsh Mohan

Qualification: MD, FAMS, FICPath, FUICC MNAMS, DSI (Honorary Member)

Professional Career

- Joined the Department of Pathology, PGIMS Rohtak in 1976 as Demonstrator.
- Faculty, PGIMS Rohtak (1977–1993).
- Professor & Head, Pathology, GMCH-32 Chandigarh (1994–2015).
- Senior Consultant, Histopathology & Cytology Services, Unipath Specialty Laboratory Ltd., Panchkula, Haryana.

Education

- MBBS (1977), MD Pathology (1980), PGIMS Rohtak.
- Gold Medalist – Panjab University.

Academic Contributions

- Examiner for MBBS/MD/DNB for over 20 years.
- Over 300 research papers in indexed national and international journals.
- Author of 9 textbooks in Pathology (multiple editions; translated into Spanish and Slovak).
- Delivered several conference lectures, CMEs, seminars, and webinars.

Professional Roles

- Editor-in-Chief, Indian Journal of Pathology & Microbiology (2003–2007).
- President, Indian Association of Pathologists & Microbiologists (2008).
- Reviewer for national and international journals.

Awards

Excellence in Teaching Award (2008); Haryana Vigyan Ratna (2010–11); State Honour by Chandigarh Administration (2015); Lifetime Achievement Award, NMO (2018).

Name: Dr. Satyavir Mathur

Qualification: MD (Pathology), 1979

Professional Career:

Joined the Department of Pathology, PGIMS Rohtak in 1976 as a Demonstrator. Served in various academic positions and retired as Senior Professor in 2015.

Academic Contributions:

- Dedicated Pathologist with a keen interest in surgical pathology and diagnostic histopathology, seeking to leverage expertise in tissue analysis to enhance student learning and patient diagnostics in an academic setting
- Delivered invited lectures and keynote presentations at academic conferences and scientific meetings, demonstrating subject expertise in the field of Pathology.
- Panelist / Moderator
Participated as a panelist and moderator in academic discussions and conference sessions, contributing to professional dialogue and knowledge exchange.
- Paper and Poster Presentations
Presented several scientific papers and posters at national and international conferences as part of ongoing research activities.
- Conference Attendance and Professional Development
Regularly attended national and international conferences, seminars, and continuing medical education (CME) programs to remain updated with advances in pathology and medical research.
- Published 65 research papers in national and international medical journals.

Post-Retirement Life:

Currently leading a peaceful retired life in Rohtak, Haryana.

Name: Dr. Rajeev Sen

Professor & Head, Department of Pathology
Faculty of Medical and Health Sciences, SGT University, Gurugram

Profile

Senior academic pathologist with over 38 years of experience in teaching, diagnostic pathology, and medical administration.

Education

- MBBS, SN Medical College, Agra University (1978)
- MD, Pathology, SN Medical College, Agra University (1982)
- Fellowship in Oncopathology, Tata Memorial Hospital, Mumbai (2001)
- Training in Hybridoma Technologies, National Institute of Immunology, New Delhi

Academic & Administrative Experience

- Professor & Head, SGT University, Gurugram (2021–Present)
- Sr Professor & Head, Pt. B.D.S. University of Health Sciences, Rohtak (2008–2021)
- Additional Professor, BP Koirala Institute of Health Sciences, Nepal (2004–2006)
- Served as Medical Superintendent, Acting Registrar, Dean and UG Committee Member, MCI

Academic Contributions

- 250+ research publications in national and international journals and supervised 150+ postgraduate theses.
- Examiner for MBBS, MD and DNB exams across Indian universities
- Speaker and chairperson at national and international conferences

Professional Achievements

- Established advanced diagnostics: Immunohistochemistry (250+ markers), Flow Cytometry, Immunofluorescence and Coagulation assays
- Drove automation of Hematology, Histopathology and Clinical Pathology labs
- Received research grants from ICMR and the Government of Haryana

Guest Lectures

Clear Cells: A Clue to Histomorphological Differential Diagnosis

Dr. Asaranti Kar, MD, FICP
President, IAPM
Prof. & HOD, Pathology
SCB MCH, Cuttack, Odisha

Introduction: Remarkable progress has been made in molecular medicine providing necessary information on tumor clonality, gene expression profile, prognosis, and response to targeted therapy. But till now, the microscope has remained the most important tool of the surgical pathologist in daily practice. For the selection of the relevant molecular/immunohistochemical investigations always, a precise or a presumptive histologic diagnosis is the starting point. It is surprising that the hematoxylin–eosin (H and E) stain, introduced more than a century ago, has still remained the gold standard stain for histopathological (HP) examination. Besides various clues like inclusions, granules, grooving, globules, halos observed in in HP sections, observation of clear cells serves as an important finding and clue for reporting. It can be focal or extensive and primary or rarely it may be secondary.

Clear cells and the causes of clear cytoplasm: It can be both physiological or pathological.

Physiological clear cells: Normally or physiologically, clear cells are seen in several sites of human body like remnants of dental lamina, rests of Malassez, myoepithelial cells, mucous acinar cells, secretory cells in the epithelium & eccrine sweat glands, endometrium proliferative phase & hyperplasia, Arias Stella phenomenon, endocervical cells, corpus luteum cells & degenerated cells.

Pathological clear cells: Clear cell changes may be observed in many non-neoplastic, benign, or malignant tumors of epithelial, mesenchymal, adnexal, melanocytic, or hematopoietic origin. Depending on the organ involved and histomorphologic features they carry their significance. Each entity has characteristic and distinguishing features and it is essential to give a correct diagnosis to each of these clear cell entities for better and proper management of patients. Starting from head and neck, salivary glands, CNS, FGT, urogenital tract, skin, bone and soft tissues, the list of clear-cell tumors is very vast and is covered in different chapters in text books of Pathology.

Non-neoplastic clear cell lesions can be in general cells in storage disorders, xanthomas, juvenile xanthogranuloma, viral infection cells such as koilocytes, cells in Hurler syndrome, Hand-schuller syndrome etc. In brain, the clear-cell tumors can be meningioma, oligodendroglioma, ependymoma, neurocytoma besides metastatic clear cell carcinoma (CCC). Head and neck tumors can be odontogenic tumors, salivary gland tumors, cutaneous adnexal tumors, mesenchymal tumors such as clear cell sarcomas, chondrosarcomas, alveolar soft part sarcoma, liposarcoma, paraganglioma etc. Most important clear cell lesions of urogenital tract are CC Renal Cell Carcinoma, clear cell sarcoma (CCS), mesonephric

blastoma, angiomyolipoma, clear cell adenocarcinoma of urethra and bladder, the classic type of seminoma, papillary cystadenoma of the epididymis, and well-differentiated adenocarcinoma of the prostate. CCC of endometrium, ovaries, cervix, clear cell hepatocellular carcinoma, cholangiocarcinoma, pulmonary blastoma, CCC of pancreas, gastrointestinal tract (GIT), follicular carcinoma of thyroid, clear cell carcinoid, and chordoma are some of the examples of the exhaustive list of clear cell neoplasms. CC variant of lymphoma, myeloma, melanoma, mesothelioma, thymoma, perivascular epithelioid cell neoplasms (PEComa), gastrointestinal stromal tumor (GIST), and yolk sac tumor are examples of rare clear-cell tumors.

Role of special stains and immunohistochemistry: Periodic acid–Schiff (PAS) stain is positive with glycogen, some mucins, and mucopolysaccharides, which can be diastase sensitive or resistant. Glycogen is diastase sensitive because diastase removes PAS staining. Neutral and acid-simple non-sulfated and acid-complex sulfated mucins and mucopolysaccharides are stained by PAS stain but acid-simple mesenchymal mucins and acid-complex connective tissue mucins are not stained. Alcian blue is used to demonstrate neutral and acidic mucopolysaccharides, sialomucin, and sulfomucin. Mucicarmine stains acidic mucin. Oil Red O and Sudan Black B stain neutral lipids in frozen sections and lipoproteins in paraffin sections and a combination of PAS with alcian blue is a pan-mucin marker. The commonly used immunomarkers can differentiate and distinguish most of the clear-cell tumors. Clear cell carcinoma (CCC) of female genital tract (FGT) are CD15, Napsin A, and CA125 positive and estrogen receptor (ER), Wilms tumor 1 (WT1), carcinoembryonic antigen (CEA), inhibin, and alpha-fetoprotein (AFP) negative. CCRCCs are CD10, epithelial membrane antigen (EMA), vimentin, Pax 2 +ve and CK20 negative; variable CK7 and melanomas are HMB45 and Melan A positive; skin CCCs are CK and HMWK positive; sarcomas are positive with vimentin and variably positive for desmin, smooth muscle actin, S-100, and CD68. In the central nervous system (CNS), immunomarkers such as glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP), neuron-specific-enolase (NSE), S-100, vimentin, and EMA are used for differentiation of entities. By combining morphology with immunohistochemistry (IHC), a definite diagnosis can be made in most instances.

Approach to clear cell lesions: The differential diagnosis of both benign and malignant clear-cell tumors must consider patterns of growth as well as accompanying cell populations when attempting to arrive at a definitive histological diagnosis. Because of these factors, it is necessary to systematically pursue the approach to the pathological assessment of clear-cell tumors and lesions, routinely considering not only clinical and radiologic details but also the possible application of histomorphology, special stains, immunohistology, electron microscopy, and cytogenetics.

Non-neoplastic

Artifacts, Degenerative changes, Arias-Stella phenomenon, Foamy macrophages, Xanthogranulomatous inflammation, Xanthomatous lesions

Neoplastic

Benign: Epithelial - Clear cell hydradenoma, Myoepithelioma, Papillary cystadenoma, Oncocytoma
 Mesenchymal - Leiomyoma, Fibroxanthoma, CC Dermatofibroma, Meningioma

Malignant: Epithelial- CCC of ovary, lungs, Primary CCC of other different organs, Various Cancers with CC change, Metastatic RCC, Melanoma, Mesenchymal -CCSK, CCS

Conclusion: Clear cell change can be a positive clue (associated with some malignancies) or a diagnostic pitfall. Demerits of clear cells: even though it can be a clue to histomorphologic distinction, help in diagnosis due to specific features of clear cell tumors; the presence of clear cell change can cause delay and challenge in diagnosis. Also, it may lead to problems in immunohistochemical staining. With artifactual clear cell change, there might be problems in electron microscopy procedures and may result in difficulty in correct diagnosis.

Between reactivity and malignancy: Reading the lymph node story

Dr. Sumeet Gujral
Professor & Pathologist
(Honorary Consultant)

ACTREC, TMC Mumbai & Senior Advisor, COP, Tata Trusts, Mumbai

Sensitive technologies like molecular and flow cytometry used in the symptomatic patients of hematolymphoid neoplasms (lymphadenopathy, lymphocytosis in peripheral blood) as well as in routine health checkup in healthy individuals has led to identification of small clonal populations of myeloid as well as lymphoid cell populations, seen more so in elderly.

These include MGUS (monoclonal gammopathy of undetermined significance), MBL (monoclonal B cell lymphocytosis) and CHIP (clonal hematopoiesis of indeterminate potential) to name a few. These clonal populations may be the driver mutations in so called disease defining entities like detection of t (14;18) follicular lymphoma, bcr-abl1 in CML etc. These can cause a major challenge for an oncologist to predict clinical behaviors of such lesions and dilemma of starting treatment. Best in most of such situations is to observe only.

Moreover, we presented an overview in the 5th edition of the World Health Organization Classification of Haematolymphoid Tumours focusing on lymphoid neoplasms. Myeloid and histiocytic neoplasms were presented in a separate accompanying article. Besides listing the entities of the classification, we highlighted and explained changes from the revised 4th edition. These included reorganization of entities by a hierarchical system as was adopted throughout the 5th edition of the WHO classification of tumours of all organ systems, modification of nomenclature for some entities, revision of diagnostic criteria or subtypes, deletion of certain entities, and introduction of new entities, as well as inclusion of tumour-like lesions, syndromes associated with the lymphoid neoplasms.

The 5th edition of the World Health Organization (WHO) Classification of Haematolymphoid Tumours was part of an effort to hierarchically catalogue human cancers arising in various organ systems within a single relational database. This paper summarized the new WHO classification scheme for myeloid and histiocytic/dendritic neoplasms and provided an overview of the principles and rationale underpinning changes from the prior edition. The

definition and diagnosis of disease types continued to be based on multiple clinicopathologic parameters, but with refinement of diagnostic criteria and emphasis on therapeutically and/or prognostically actionable biomarkers. While a genetic basis for defining diseases was sought wherever possible, the classification strives to keep practical worldwide applicability in perspective. The result was an enhanced, contemporary, evidence-based classification of myeloid and histiocytic/dendritic neoplasms, rooted in molecular biology and an organizational structure that permitted future scalability as new discoveries continue to inexorably inform future editions.

“Kindly go through the whole article for details”

- The 5th edition of The World Health Organization Classification of Haematolymphoid Tumours: Lymphoid Neoplasms" *Leukemia*. 2022 Jul;36(7):1720-1748. Alaggio R, et al. *Leukemia*. 2023. PMID: 37468552 Free PMC article.
- The 5th edition of the World Health Organization Classification of Haematolymphoid Tumours: Myeloid and Histiocytic/Dendritic Neoplasms. Joseph D Khoury et al. *Leukemia*. 2022 July

Soft Tissue Tumors: Diagnostic approach, challenges, and clarification, including value addition of ancillary techniques

Dr Bharat Rekhi, MD, DNB, MIAC, FICP, FRCPATH
Professor, Pathologist, Dept. of Pathology, Tata Memorial Hospital, HBNI University,
Mumbai.

Soft tissue tumors (STTs), including sarcomas are complex, heterogeneous and “intellectually” stimulating tumors, as a result of a considerable clinic-radio-pathological overlap within the various described tumor types, creating a substantial challenge for a conventional diagnosing pathologist. These are associated with significant discrepancies, especially when reported by a non-specialty pathologist. Pseudosarcomas, now recognized as neoplasms, continue to mimic certain sarcomas. Identification of more than 200 histologic subtypes of STTs; over 100 sarcomas, including one-thirds tumors with ‘genetic signatures’, all can be baffling to the treating oncosurgeon. Most of these tumor types are associated with distinct histopathological features, genetic profile and clinical behavior.

During the past two decades there have been significant updates in STT diagnosis that was initially based on the ‘time honored’ histopathological approach, including “pattern recognition” and “pattern analysis” The advent of ‘brown revolution’ of immunohistochemistry (IHC), followed by the molecular and / or genetic revolution have refined STT classification systems, finally leading to facilitate reproducible diagnosis and more sophisticated prognostication. The various discrete histomorphological patterns like “hemangiopericytomatous”, “herringbone”, along with others used in common parlance of STT diagnosis like ‘whorls’, ‘storiform’ ‘rhabdoid-like’, ‘alveolar’, to name but a few, can be objectively translated into discrete histological subtypes with application of ancillary techniques, mostly importantly IHC staining, molecular, cytogenetics and ultrastructural analysis, the latter to a limited extent. A ‘herringbone’ pattern is not restricted to a fibrosarcoma. Hemangiopericytoma has become an extremely restricted diagnosis and shares spectrum with a solitary fibrous tumor. Nonetheless, morphological patterns, including cytological subtypes guide towards ordering optimal panel of IHC markers and molecular tests, an approach that is feasible for limited resource settings like ours. Not forgetting, there

can be occasional ‘surprises’ and serendipitously identified “newer” STTs, interrelationships and “concepts”

The World Health Organization (WHO) classification of tumors has been the utilized extensively for classifying STTs. This classification was updated in the year 2013, WHO ‘blue book’ for soft tissue and bone tumors that includes newer diagnostic entities like hemosiderotic fibrolipomatous lesion/tumor, spindle cell/sclerosing rhabdomyosarcoma, phosphaturic mesenchymal tumor; additional genetic information and newly identified tumor relationships between sclerosing epithelioid fibrosarcoma and low-grade fibromyxoid sarcoma, to name but a few. This was followed by followed by 2020 (5th edition), where a new section of undifferentiated small round cell sarcoma was created between soft tissue and bone tumors, to rightfully include Ewing sarcoma and other fusion-defined entities. There were other entities featuring for the first time, such as superficial CD34- positive fibroblastic tumor, atypical spindle cell/pleomorphic lipomatous tumor, inflammatory leiomyosarcoma, *NTRK*-rearranged tumors, *EWSR1::SMAD* fibroblastic tumor, EBV-positive smooth muscle tumor.

Classification of STTs has clinical relevance. After diagnosis and the metastatic work-up, a multidisciplinary team of oncosurgeon, radiation and medical oncologist or a disease management group, as we have in our Institution, decides upon a treatment plan. Surgery forms the treatment mainstay wherein the intent is to balance tumor excision with preservation of limb functions/salvage, especially in extremity sarcomas. For larger, high-grade sarcomas, adjuvant or neoadjuvant chemotherapy (CT) is offered, based upon histological subtypes, especially pediatric soft tissue sarcomas like rhabdomyosarcoma, PNET and DSRCT that are candidates for specific CT. CT agents, such as anthracycline and ifosfamide are being offered in adult STTs like synovial sarcomas and myxoid/round cell liposarcomas. Targeted therapy for sarcomas is up on the horizon. Myxoid liposarcomas are being targeted with relatively more specific drugs like trabectedin. Besides gastrointestinal tumors (GISTs), imatinib/‘Gleevec’ is also being offered as a targeted in cases of recurrent or unresectable dermatofibrosarcoma protuberans. Synovial sarcoma is one of few adult soft tissue sarcomas, which is relatively chemosensitive, where as its closest diagnostic mimic i.e. a malignant peripheral nerve sheath tumor is chemo-refractory. While high-grade sarcomas are more commonly associated with recurrences and metastasis, low-grade sarcomas follow a protracted clinical course and are associated with delayed recurrences and or metastasis. In this way, exact diagnosis assumes importance.

For enhancing objectively, newer IHC markers have been developed, some after gene expression profiling, for example TLE1, TFE3, MUC4, SS18-SSX, INI1, to name but a few.

(i) Some Newer IHC Markers:

1. TLE 1 in cases of synovial sarcomas, with limited specificity. Presently, SS18-SSX as a surrogate for the underlying translocation is nearly a perfectly diagnostic immunomarker
2. TFE3 in alveolar soft part sarcoma with limited specificity.
3. INI1 in musculoskeletal tumors, including epithelioid sarcomas and synovial sarcomas (reduced immunoexpression).
4. Brachyury/T in chordomas and negative in parachordomas/myoepitheliomas.
5. MUC4 for low grade fibromyxoid sarcoma.

6. STAT6 for solitary fibrous tumors.

Newer markers, such as STAT6 have been helpful in better characterization of solitary fibrous tumors (SFTs), including their identification at unusual sites, such as vagina and bone.

(ii) Some inter-tumor relationships within the realm of STTs

1. Low-grade fibromyxoid sarcoma, hyalinising spindle cell tumor with giant rosettes and sclerosing epithelioid fibrosarcoma.
2. Myxoinflammatory fibroblastic sarcoma, hemosiderotic fibrolipomatous lesion/tumor (HFLL) and pleomorphic hyalinizing angiectatic tumor (PHAT)
3. Sclerosing and spindle rhabdomyosarcoma.
4. Proximal epithelioid sarcoma and extrarenal rhabdoid tumor.

(iii) Various tumors harbouring underlying *EWSR1* gene rearrangement.

Lately, certain sarcomas have been described by their gene fusions, for example *CIC-DUX4* positive and *BCOR-CCNB3*-positive sarcomas, within the group of undifferentiated round cell sarcomas, sharing some morphologic similarity, but genetic differences with Ewing sarcomas.³⁰⁻³²

This presentation will focus upon diagnostic approach, challenges, clarifications with recent developments in the diagnosis of soft tissue tumors, including relatively newly described tumor entities, newer IHC markers and concepts, including tumor relationships, especially with personal experience in the form of case examples.

Renal Biopsies Demystified

Col (Dr) P Sengupta
Professor, Dept of Pathology
Jagannath Gupta Inst of Medical Sciences & Hospital Budge, Kolkata

Introduction:

Kidney biopsy is an essential tool for diagnosis of many kidney diseases. Obtaining an adequate biopsy sample with appropriate allocation for various studies is essential. Nephrologist should understand key lesions and their interpretation because there are essential elements underlying optimal approaches for intervention.

Tissue Sampling, Allocation and Processing:

An adequate sample size must be obtained for diagnosis. Needle gauge has a dramatic impact on the sample obtained. Usually 18-19 Gauge needles are used and they give adequate samples.

For focal lesions involving small number of glomeruli, almost 25 glomeruli may be required for light microscopy examination to have a greater than 95% chance of detecting those lesions. For Segmental lesions, serial sections might help. Minimal sample size depends on the specific diagnosis. For example, to diagnose membranous nephropathy even a single glomerulus may be sufficient, however, for extent of chronicity or scarring more number of glomeruli may be required. Transplant diagnosis are most accurate when sample includes a minimum of 7 glomeruli from two separate sites of cortex. For most LM assessments to adequately assess the severity and distribution of lesions 8-10 glomeruli are needed.

Sample Location:

Subcapsular cortical samples have over representation of global Sclerosis. Juxtamedullary glomeruli are earliest to be involved in FSGS. Corticomedullary region are best suited to look for polyoma virus nephropathy.

Dividing the Tissue:

1mm cubes from each end may be removed and placed in gluteraldehyde for electron microscopy, 2/3 of the core can be placed in formaldehyde for light microscopy and remaining tissue can be used for IF. Forceps are avoided to prevent crushing artefact.

Light Microscopy:

For light microscopy formalin, paraformaldehyde, alcoholic bouin or zenker fixative may be used. Use of formalin helps in better IHC testing. If observation of urate crystals is intended then ethanol is preferred.

Immunofluorescence (IF):

For IF, tissue can be directly frozen or placed in Michel medium if it has to be transported to another laboratory.

Electron Microscopy:

For Electron microscopy 1mm cubes of cortex are placed in gluteraldehyde.

Tissue sections are usually cut at 3-4 micron thickness and stained with Hematoxylin & Eosin, Periodic acids Schiffs, Periodic acid silver methenamine and Massons Trichrome. Tissue for immunofluorescence is stained with IgG, IgA, IgM, C₃, C_{1q} or C₄, Kappa, Lamda, albumin and Fibrinogen. EM tissue is processed and embedded in a plastic hard medium and Scout sections are stained with toluidene blue to identify the specific area to be cut for thin sections to be placed on a grid for EM examination.

Salvage Technique:

Salvage light microscopy from frozen tissue: The remaining of frozen tissue may be retrieved and fixed in formalin but there can be freezing artifacts and loss of morphologic details.

Similarly EM can be processed out of paraffin blocks but outcome may be quite variable and GBM may be artefactually thinner due to formalin processing. Immunofluorescence can be done on paraffin fixed tissue after proteinase K digestion but sensitivity of deposits varies. IgA is robustly detected but anti GBM antibody may not be detected by this procedure. Crystalline light chains are better detected by this method and also are certain masked antigens and C₃.

Tissue Examination:

In a renal biopsy four compartments are assessed viz glomeruli, tubules, interstitium and blood vessels and complete report is issued out along with immunofluorescence findings.

Active vs Chronic lesions:

Active lesions include hypercellularity either mesangial or endocapillary, influx of leucocytes, fibrinoid necrosis, rupture of GBM, karyorrhexis, cellular, fibrocellular or fibrous crescents may be seen.

Tubulo interstitial active lesions are characterized by edema, inflammatory infiltrate often with tubulitis with variable lymphocytes, plasma cells and/or polymorphonuclear leucocytes. Active lesions of the vessels include intimal swelling, necrosis, thrombosis and inflammation (vasculitis). Chronic lesions of glomeruli include sclerosis, Segmental or global and fibrous crescents. Chronic tubulointerstitial lesions are interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy. Chronic lesions of vessels include medial thickening, hyalinosis and concentric intimal proliferation.

Special stains such as PAS can be useful to determine thickened Glomerular or tubular basement membrane. Deposits and cells do not stain with silver stain (PASM). PAS can also highlight deposits/immune complexes such as those seen in Lupus or Cryoglobulinemic glomerulonephritis. Massons trichrome can also stain the immune complexes.

Outline of few native Kidney Specific lesions:

1. Thickened GBM with negative IF, no double contour:
 - a) Diabetic nephropathy
 - b) Idiopathic Nodular Glomerulosclerosis
2. Double Contour by silver stain:
 - a) Chronic thrombotic microangiopathy.
 - b) MPGN
 - c) Transplant Glomerulopathy (non-native)
3. Irregular GBM by silver staining, basket weaving by EM:
Hereditary Nephritis (Alports syndrome).
4. Variable spikes or double Contour by Silver Stain may be due to masked deposits. This requires pronase digestion and IF.
5. Thick appearance of GBM with positive IF:
 - a) Membranous Nephropathy (IgG and C3)
 - b) Molded Sausage shaped Contour of deposits along capillary loop, mesangial granular deposits, GSM double contour by silver stain, subendothelial deposits by EM : MPGN due to deposits.
 - c) Polyclonal Ig with full house staining (IgG, IgA, IgM) C₃ and C1q suggests Lupus Nephritis.
 - d) Polyclonal IgG with strong IgM component after with clonal shift, with strong PAS positive deposits in lumen is suggestive of Cryoglobulins.
 - e) Polyclonal IgG with Lesser C3, GBM variable double contours by silver stain, randomly arranged fibrils by EM, negative Congo red and positive DNAJB9 staining by IHC is suggestive of fibrillary GN.
6. Thick appearance of GBM with variable IF and positive congo red is suggestive of Amyloidosis.
7. Thin Glomerular basement membrane by EM is suggestive of Alports disease or thin basement membrane disease.
8. Mesangial Hypercellularity: Variable mesangial hypercellularity with nodules may be seen in the following conditions: Diabetic Nephropathy, Monoclonal immunoglobulin deposition disease, idiopathic nodular glomerulosclerosis, amyloidosis, Nodular

MPGN. Mesangial hypercellularity with positive IF without nodules can be seen in Lupus Class II. IgA Nephropathy and chronic infection related glomerulonephritis.

Mesangial hypercellularity without immune complexes may be seen in variants of MCD, FSGS or early diabetic nephropathy.

- 9. Endocapillary Hypercellularity:** MPGN pattern is characterized by mesangial and endocapillary hypercellularity, a term denoting a combination of both endothelial cell prominence and influx of leucocytes in glomerular capillaries with double contour of GBM by light microscopy. This pattern can be caused by immune complexes and compliments.

This pattern can be seen in Lupus Nephritis, Cryoglobulinemic GN, Post infectious GN, Fibrillary GN, Immunotactoid GN, Dense deposition disease & C3 dominant GN.

- 10. Sclerosis:** Glomerulonephritis can be assessed in terms of its location within the glomerular tuft and its quality. Glomerulomegaly may be present in cases of FSGS even before sclerosis is evident. Comparisons of glomerular size must be age matched. Usual type of sclerosis can be localized anywhere within the glomerular tuft. There may be obliteration of capillary lumen by increased matrix or hyalinization, extensive foot process effacement by EM, typical of FSGS. Other patterns of sclerosis such as collapsing or tip lesion may also be seen. Secondary sclerosis can be seen in any injury or due to immune deposition.

- 11. Crescents:** Crescents are composed of proliferation of visceral epithelial cells, parietal epithelial cells and or variable inflammatory cell influx. Crescents may be seen in Anti GBM antibody disease, immune complex mediated glomerulonephritis or pauci immune small vessel vasculitis.

- 12. Intraglomerular foamy macrophages:** Can be seen in lipid storage disease (e.g. LCAT deficiency) or diabetic nephropathy with sclerosis and marked proteinuria.

- 13. Vascular lesions:** Look for sclerosis, intimal fibrosis, medial hypertrophy, thrombotic lesions, fibrinoid necrosis, embolic lesions such as cholesterol emboli. Swollen endothelial cells may be seen in eclampsia or pre-eclampsia.

- 14. Tubulo-interstitial lesions:** Acute tubular injury shows flattening, sloughing off and regeneration of tubule epithelial cells, may or may not be associated with glomerular necrosis. Interstitial inflammation may show infiltration by both lymphocytes and polymorphonuclear cells. If eosinophils are seen consider hypersensitivity reaction causing interstitial nephritis.

Granulomas may be seen in Tuberculosis, Sarcoidosis or small vessel vasculitis (Granulomatosis with Polyangitis).

- 15. Intra tubular casts:** Pigmented casts may be seen as in bilirubin casts or myoglobin casts. Tamm- Horsfall protein stains eosinophilic in H&E and on fragmentation can break the tubular basement membrane and elicit a giant cell reaction. This phenomenon is more prominently seen in light chain cast nephropathy. The casts are brittle, glassy hyaline and get easily fractured.

Crystals may be polarizable or non-polarizable. Polarizable crystals are usually calcium oxalate and 2,8 Dihydroxyadenine (DHA). Non polarizable crystals are calcium phosphate crystals, Indinavir crystals or urate crystals.

- 16. Interstitial fibrosis with tubular atrophy (IFTA):** IFTA generally correlates better with kidney functions than extent of glomerular lesions. This pattern of IFTA gives hint to aetiology.
- a - Diffuse pattern: Non specific
 - b - Striped fibrosis: Calcineurin inhibitor toxicity (CNI)
 - c - Patchy, geographic, Jigsaw puzzle pattern: Chronic pyelonephritis
 - d - Endocrine change of tubules: Prolonged Ischemia

Glossary of terms used

I Glomerular

- a - Capsular drop: Hyaline drop sitting on Bowmans capsule and protruding into Bowmans space. Characteristic of diabetic glomerulosclerosis.
- b - Collapse: Collapse of glomerular capillaries with prominent overlying podocytes. Podocytes frequently contain large protein droplets.
- c - Crescent: Two or more cell layers between the visceral podocytes and parietal epithelium of Bowman's capsule. Cellular crescents may contain inflammatory cells. Fibrous crescents have collagen with few fibroblasts. Crescent should occupy at least 10% of the glomerular circumference.
- d - Diffuse: Involves more than 50% of the glomeruli.
- e - Focal: Less than 50% of the glomeruli involved.
- f - Global: Entire glomerular tuft within a glomerulus is involved.
- g - Hyalinosis: Also called insudative or exudative lesion or in diabetes fibrin caps : Abnormal accumulation of homogenous silver negative, PAS positive proteinaceous, material from the blood into capillary wall.
- h - Intracapillary or endocapillary: Too many cells in the area bordered by GBM (glomerular capillaries and mesangium)
- i - Extracapillary: Same as crescent.
- j - Mesangial hypercellularity: More than three mesangial cells per mesangial area away from the vascular pole in a 2-3 micron section.
- k - Mesangiolytic: Necrosis of mesangium with loss of anchoring filaments of glomerular capillaries leading to glomerular microaneurysms.
- l - Nephritic Syndrome: Hematuria with RBC and granular casts, variable degree of proteinuria and frequently hypertension with periorbital edema.
- m -Nephrotic Syndrome: Severe proteinuria (> 3.5 g/24 hrs) with edema, hypoalbuminemia and often hypercholesterolemia and cholesteroluria.
- n - Nodular mesangial sclerosis: Methamine silver and PAS positive mesangial nodules with acellular centres surrounded by frequently coalescent glomerular capillaries.
- o - Obsolescence: Retracted and collapsed glomerular capillaries around the vascular pole. Bowmans space is filled with collagen. Bowmans capsule basement membrane is usually intact.
- p - Sclerosis: Abnormal accumulation of silver and PAS positive glomerular extracellular matrix resembling mesangial matrix and GBM.

- q - Segmental: “Only a segment, localized portion of glomerulus is involved. Opposite of segmental is global.
- r - Spikes: Silver positive GBM projections between subepithelial glomerular capillary deposits as seen in membranous nephropathy.
- s - Tram Tracking: Double contour of glomerular capillary loop best seen on silver methamine staining. It is caused by mesangial interposition and by deposition of any glomerular subendothelial material between which and the endothelium, a new layer of basement membrane is formed. Eg- MPGN

II TubuloInterstitium

- a - Isometric Vacuolization : Fine diffuse vacuoles approximately of the same size in the tubular epithelial cytoplasm. Can be seen in CNI toxicity.
- b - Resorption droplets : PAS positive droplets in tubular cytoplasm due to resorption of protein.
- c - Tubulitis : Infiltration of tubular epithelium by inflammatory cells.
- d - Tubular Atrophy : Classic: with thickened wrinkled basement membrane
Endocrine: clusters of atrophic tubules resembling endocrine glands
Thyroidization: Atrophic tubules with proteinaceous casts resembling thyroid follicles.

III Vasculature

- a - Fibrinoid necrosis : Deposition of proteinaceous material with the staining characteristic of fibrin in the arterial or arteriolar wall.
- b - Hyaline change : Deposition of glossy refractile homogenous eosinophilic PAS positive material in arterial walls.
- c - Intimal arteritis : Subendothelial (intimal) inflammatory cell infiltrate in transplant rejection.
- d - Intimal fibrosis : Appearance of myointimal cells with abundant deposition of extracellular matrix between the endothelium and the media. The elastic lamina is frequently disrupted and lamellated.
- e - Onion skinning : Concentric layering of elongated nuclei and cells in usually mucoid appearing intima with severely narrowed lumen. Seen in malignant hypertension, scleroderma and thrombotic microangiopathy (TMA).

Cervical Cancer Screening: Liquid-based Cervical Cytology and Molecular Markers

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Almost 80 years ago, George Papanicolaou introduced the cervical Pap smear, which could detect cervical cancer cells. The conventional method of cervical cytology has worked very efficiently for the last many decades, with up to 80% reduction in mortality from cancer of the cervix. Two technologies that have revolutionized cervical cancer screening are liquid-based cytology (LBC) and HPV (human papilloma virus) testing. Screening is also sometimes carried out by visual inspection of cervix after acetic acid application (VIA) or visual inspection after Lugol's iodine application (VILI) and self-sampling for HPV testing.

The World Health Organization (WHO) has launched a global strategy for the elimination of cervical cancer, emphasizing HPV vaccination, HPV-based screening, and effective treatment of precancerous lesions. Primary screening with high-risk HPV testing is now recommended as the preferred method by many international guidelines. HPV testing has a higher sensitivity for detecting cervical intraepithelial neoplasia grade 2 or worse (CIN2+) compared with cytology and provides a very high negative predictive value. In this evolving landscape, cervical cytology continues to play an important complementary role in screening and diagnosis.

Problems with conventional cytology smears: Inadequate rate is more; Blood, polymorphs and inflammation obscures the squamous cells, which makes interpretation difficult; cellular clumping can be more; HPV detection cannot be done from the same sample.

Liquid-based cytology (LBC) is a technique of processing the cervical samples in a liquid medium, which is intended to reduce inadequate rate of cervical samples and has been known to improve the detection of precancerous lesions of the cervix and glandular abnormalities. The obscuring factors such as inflammation, blood and polymorphs are lesser in LBC slides

as opposed to conventional smears. Fixation is uniform and the same sample can be used for preparing additional smears and cell block and also for HPV testing.

Obtaining the cervical sample

The US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approved two LBC Pap tests- ThinPrep™ in 1996 and SurePath™, formerly known as AutoCyte PREP or CytoRICH in 1999. LBC Pap test requires use of Cervex-Brush, plastic spatula and/or endocervical brush to obtain an adequate sample. The longer bristles of Cervex brush are inserted into the endocervical canal and outer shorter bristles touch the ectocervix. The brush should be **rotated five times clockwise** to obtain the sample. The head of the brush is detached into a vial containing preservative fluid in SurePath™ sample. The brush head is removed after rinsing it thoroughly in the vial for the ThinPrep™ sample.

ThinPrep® and SurePath® LBC

ThinPrep® uses filtration technology to produce a thin layer of cells on the slide.

SurePath® uses density gradient centrifugation followed by gravitational settling to create a uniform circular smear.

Both techniques produce well-preserved cellular morphology and allow residual material to be used for HPV testing and other molecular assays.

Human papillomavirus (HPV) detection and other Molecular markers

More than **90% of cervical cancers** are associated with high-risk HPV infection. Molecular techniques used for HPV detection include:

DNA-based assays

DNA-based assays detect viral DNA sequences and are widely used in clinical practice. Commonly used tests include:

- Hybrid Capture 2 (HC2)
- Roche Cobas HPV test
- Abbott RealTime HPV assay
- BD Onclarity HPV assay

These tests detect multiple high-risk HPV types and may specifically identify HPV types 16 and 18, which are associated with the highest risk of cervical cancer.

Digene Hybrid Capture™ 2 is based on the principle of hybridization with DNA/RNA hybrid formation in a solution of RNA probes complementary to the sequence of high-risk (16, 18, 31, 33, 35, 39, 45, 51, 52, 56, 58, 59, & 68) and low-risk (6, 11, 42, 43, 44) HPV types.

mRNA-based assays

mRNA assays detect expression of E6 and E7 oncogenes, which play a critical role in malignant transformation. These tests may provide improved specificity for detecting clinically significant lesions. Commonly used tests include: **Aptima HPV assay** [FDA approved in Oct 2011 for detection of 14 hrHPV types]

Role of HPV testing in cervical cancer screening

HPV testing can be used in several clinical scenarios:

- Primary screening test
- Triage of abnormal cytology results
- Co-testing with cytology
- Test of cure following treatment of cervical intraepithelial neoplasia

Table: representing various HPV assays approved in different settings

Category	Assays	Notes
Primary Screening	Roche cobas HPV, BD Onclarity HPV, Abbott Alinity m HR HPV	Only these three are currently FDA-approved for stand-alone primary HPV screening
Co-testing (HPV + Cytology)	cobas HPV, BD Onclarity, Aptima, Cervista HR	Used in women aged ≥ 30 years; recommended in transitional settings
Reflex Testing (for ASC-US or LSIL cytology)	Hybrid Capture HC2, Cervista HR, Cervista 16/18, Aptima	Used when cytology results are equivocal; guides colposcopy referral
WHO-prequalified (LMIC use)	careHPV, Abbott RealTime HR HPV, Cepheid Xpert HPV	Validated in resource-limited and self-sampling contexts; not FDA-approved

Biomarkers in Cervical Screening

In recent years, several biomarkers have been introduced to improve risk stratification of HPV-positive women.

p16INK4a: Overexpression of p16INK4a reflects disruption of cell cycle regulation caused by oncogenic HPV infection.

Ki-67: Ki-67 is a proliferation marker that indicates active cell division.

Dual staining (p16/Ki-67): Dual immunostaining for p16 and Ki-67 identifies cells with simultaneous expression of both markers, which indicates HPV-driven cell cycle deregulation. This method has demonstrated improved sensitivity and specificity for detecting CIN2+ lesions and is increasingly used for triage in HPV-positive women.

Other biomarkers: Other biomarkers that have been investigated include:

- ProEx C (MCM2 and TOP2A proteins)
- HPV E6/E7 mRNA detection
- DNA methylation markers

These markers may help identify lesions with higher risk of progression.

Take home message: Cervical cancer screening has evolved significantly with advances in molecular biology and understanding of HPV-driven carcinogenesis. Primary HPV testing has emerged as the preferred screening modality because of its high sensitivity and excellent negative predictive value. Nevertheless, cervical cytology continues to play a crucial role in

the evaluation and triage of HPV-positive women and in the diagnosis of cervical epithelial abnormalities. The incorporation of molecular biomarkers, such as p16/Ki-67 dual staining, further enhances the accuracy of screening and risk stratification. Integration of HPV vaccination, HPV-based screening, cytology, and molecular biomarkers represents the future of cervical cancer prevention and forms the cornerstone of the global strategy for cervical cancer elimination.

Bits and Pieces: Pathology Insights in Decoding of Duodenal Biopsies

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1. Introduction

Malabsorption syndrome results from defective digestion and/or absorption of nutrients from the small intestine. It may arise from luminal, mucosal, or post-mucosal abnormalities and presents with chronic diarrhea, steatorrhea, weight loss, anemia, and nutritional deficiencies. Pathology plays a central role in diagnosis, as histologic evaluation of small bowel biopsy often provides definitive clues to etiology.

2. Classification of Causes

Category	Mechanism	Representative Diseases
Intraluminal defects	Inadequate digestion	Chronic pancreatitis, cystic fibrosis, bile salt deficiency (cholestasis), Zollinger–Ellison syndrome
Mucosal (absorptive) defects	Mucosal injury or enzyme deficiency	Celiac disease, Tropical sprue, Whipple’s disease, Crohn’s disease, autoimmune enteropathy, giardiasis
Congenital / Genetic	Enzyme or epithelial transport defect	Microvillous inclusion disease, Tufting enteropathy, congenital chloride/sodium diarrhea, abetalipoproteinemia, lactase deficiency
Post-mucosal / Transport defects	Lymphatic or vascular obstruction	Intestinal lymphangiectasia, constrictive pericarditis, lymphoma
Infectious	Mucosal damage due to pathogens	Giardia, Mycobacterium avium-intracellulare, HIV enteropathy, Cryptosporidium, Cyclospora, Isospora
Drug-induced	Cytotoxic or immune-mediated	Olmesartan, mycophenolate mofetil, NSAIDs, methotrexate, colchicine

Category	Mechanism	Representative Diseases
	injury	
Neoplastic / Infiltrative	Replacement or distortion of mucosa	Intestinal lymphoma, amyloidosis, systemic mastocytosis
Miscellaneous	Metabolic or endocrine	Hypothyroidism, diabetes, carcinoid syndrome, radiation enteritis

3. Pathophysiologic Basis of Malabsorption

Stage	Site	Example
Intraluminal digestion	Defective pancreatic/bile function	Chronic pancreatitis, CF
Mucosal uptake	Damage to epithelium or enzymes	Celiac, tropical sprue, infection
Post-mucosal transport	Lymphatic obstruction	Intestinal lymphangiectasia

4. Pathologist's Stepwise Approach

Step 1: Clinical Correlation

- Age of onset, duration, systemic symptoms
 - Infancy → congenital enteropathies
 - Adult → celiac, infection, drug-induced
- Nutritional and autoimmune associations

Step 2: Adequate Biopsy Sampling

- Multiple biopsies from **duodenum (D2 ± bulb)** or **jejunum**.
- Proper **orientation** to assess villous height and crypt depth.

5. Microscopic Evaluation (Key Diagnostic Features)

Feature	Pathological Clues	Important Entities
Villous architecture	Normal / Partial / Total atrophy	Celiac, tropical sprue, autoimmune enteropathy
Crypt changes	Hyperplasia or apoptosis	Celiac, drug-induced, GVHD
Intraepithelial lymphocytes (IELs)	↑ IELs (>25/100 enterocytes)	Celiac, viral, autoimmune enteropathy
Lamina propria infiltrate	Mononuclear, eosinophilic, foamy macrophages, granulomas	Celiac, Whipple's, Crohn's, eosinophilic enteritis
Presence of organisms	Giardia trophozoites, Cryptosporidium oocysts	Infectious enteropathies
Special structural changes	Dilated lacteals, microvillous inclusions, epithelial tufts	Lymphangiectasia, congenital disorders

6. Major Entities and Their Pathological Features

A. Celiac Disease

- **Etiology:** Gluten-sensitive enteropathy; autoimmune (anti-tTG, EMA).
- **Histology (Marsh-Oberhuber):** Villous atrophy + crypt hyperplasia + ↑IELs (>30/100 cells).
- **Distribution:** Proximal small bowel.
- **Treatment:** Gluten-free diet.

B. Tropical Sprue

- **Cause:** Post-infectious enteropathy (in tropical climates).
- **Features:** Partial villous atrophy, lamina propria plasma cells, often distal > proximal.
- **Distinguishing:** History of residence in tropics, folate deficiency, antibiotic-responsive.

C. Whipple's Disease

- **Pathogen:** *Tropheryma whipplei* (Gram+, PAS+ bacilli).
- **Histology:** Expanded lamina propria with PAS-positive foamy macrophages. Dilated lacteals, blunted villi.
- **Systemic involvement:** CNS, joints, heart.

D. Crohn's Disease (Small Intestinal Involvement)

- **Features:** Patchy mucosal inflammation, granulomas, fissures, lymphoid aggregates.
- **Consequence:** Malabsorption from mucosal injury and resection.

E. Autoimmune Enteropathy

- **Mechanism:** Autoantibodies to enterocytes/goblet cells.
- **Histology:** Villous atrophy, crypt apoptosis, loss of goblet and Paneth cells.
- **Associated:** IPEX syndrome, other autoimmune diseases.

F. Common Variable Immunodeficiency (CVID) Enteropathy

- **Histology:** Villous atrophy, *reduced plasma cells*, crypt hyperplasia.
- **Serology:** Negative celiac markers.
- **Clue:** History of recurrent infections.

G. Drug-induced Enteropathies

Drug	Histopathological Pattern
Olmesartan	Villous atrophy + IELs (celiac mimic)
Mycophenolate	Crypt apoptosis and mucosal injury
NSAIDs	Focal erosions, ulcers
Methotrexate	Epithelial injury, nuclear atypia
Colchicine	Mitotic arrest in crypt epithelium

H. Infectious Enteropathies

Organism	Key Histology / Test	Comment
<i>Giardia lamblia</i>	Trophozoites on mucosal surface	No invasion
<i>Cryptosporidium</i>	Spherical organisms at apical surface	AIDS patients
<i>Cyclospora / Isospora</i>	Oocysts visible with acid-fast stain	Immunocompromised
<i>Mycobacterium avium-intracellulare</i>	Foamy macrophages, acid-fast bacilli	HIV enteropathy
<i>Strongyloides stercoralis</i>	Worms in lamina propria	Hyperinfection in immunosuppressed
<i>HIV enteropathy</i>	Villous blunting, crypt apoptosis	No specific pathogen sometimes

I. Protein-losing Enteropathies

- **Intestinal lymphangiectasia:** Dilated mucosal and submucosal lacteals; protein loss → edema, hypoalbuminemia.
- **Secondary causes:** Lymphoma, cardiac disease, constrictive pericarditis.

J. Infiltrative and Neoplastic Disorders

Entity	Pathology	Mechanism
Intestinal lymphoma (EATL, MALT)	Lymphocytic infiltration, ulceration, loss of villi	Replaces mucosa
Amyloidosis	Eosinophilic amorphous deposits (Congo red +)	Impaired absorption
Systemic mastocytosis	Infiltration by mast cells (tryptase+, CD117+)	Functional mucosal disorder

K. Congenital / Genetic Enteropathies

Disease	Mutation	Pathology	Presentation
Microvillous Inclusion Disease	MYO5B	Microvillous inclusions (EM)	Neonatal diarrhea
Tufting Enteropathy	EpCAM	Epithelial "tufts"	Infantile diarrhea
Congenital Chloride/Sodium Diarrhea	SLC26A3/SLC9A3	Normal histology, electrolyte imbalance	Watery diarrhea
Abetalipoproteinemia	MTP	Fat-laden enterocytes	Fat malabsorption, acanthocytosis
Trichohepatoenteric Syndrome	TTC37/SKIV2L	Villous atrophy + abnormal hair	Severe diarrhea
Lactase deficiency	LCT gene	Normal biopsy	Osmotic diarrhea on milk ingestion

L. Eosinophilic Gastroenteritis

- **Histology:** Marked eosinophilic infiltration of mucosa ± muscularis.
- **Causes:** Idiopathic or allergic.
- **Manifestations:** Abdominal pain, diarrhea, protein loss.

Dermatopathology -Pattern based approach

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Basics & Skin Architecture is important before interpretation of skin biopsy

- Layers of skin (epidermis, dermis, subcutis)
- Epidermal cells & appendages
- Normal histology at different sites
- Most important- Reaction patterns based approach

Site of biopsy, age, and clinical features are important for clinicopathological correlation (CPC).

Epidermal Reaction Patterns

Pattern1: Psoriasiform Dermatitis is the commonest

- Psoriasis
 - Chronic eczema
 - Lichen simplex chronicus
- Clues:** Regular acanthosis, elongated rete ridges

Pattern 2: Spongiotic Dermatitis

- Acute eczema
 - Allergic contact dermatitis
- Clues:** Intercellular edema (spongiosis), vesicles

Pattern 3: Interface Dermatitis

- Lichen planus
 - Lupus erythematosus
 - Drug reactions
- Clues:** Basal cell vacuolization, Civatte bodies

Pattern 4: Vesiculobullous Pattern

- Pemphigus
- Bullous pemphigoid
- Dermatitis herpetiformis

Level of split and type of acantholysis is important to note

-Intraepidermal vs subepidermal blister

-Acantholytic vs non-acantholytic

-Role of **DIF & salt-split skin**

Disease	Level	DIF
Pemphigus vulgaris	Suprabasal	Fish-net IgG
Bullous pemphigoid	Subepidermal	Linear IgG/C3
DH	Subepidermal	Granular IgA

Direct Immunofluorescence (DIF): biopsy prerequisites

- Perilesional skin
- Fresh lesion

Pattern 5: Granulomatous Dermatoses

- Tuberculoid leprosy
- Borderline leprosy
- Sarcoidosis
- Foreign body granuloma
- Deep cutaneous fungal infection
- Cutaneous Leishmaniasis

Always describe

-Type of granuloma

-Necrosis present or absent

-Distribution of granuloma (periadnexal, neurotropic)

Infectious Dermatoses-Special stains are mandatory

- Fungal (PAS/GMS)
- Viral (HSV, HPV, molluscum)
- Bacterial (leprosy, syphilis)
- Parasitic (scabies)

Pattern 6: Pigmentary Disorders

- Vitiligo
- Melasma
- Post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation
- Nevus vs melanoma basics

Pattern 8: Skin Tumors

Benign

- Seborrheic keratosis
- Nevi
- Dermatofibroma

Malignant

- BCC
- SCC
- Malignant Melanoma

Pattern 9: Adnexal Tumors

- Hair follicle tumors
- Sweat gland tumors
- Sebaceous tumors
- Mixed tumors

Pattern 10: Mixed pattern

- Lichenoid Interphase
- Spongiotic psoriasiform
- Periadnexal and perivascular

LIST OF ORAL PRESENTATIONS

Oral Presentation No	Registration Number	NAME	TITLE
OP 1	NWIAMP024	Dr. Chetna Dhok	Unveiling Breast FNAC Trends with the Yokohama System: A Tertiary Care Hospitals Perspective
OP 2	NWIAMP033	Dr. Unnati Bhatt	Utility of Proposed Sydney System in Reporting and Classification of Lymph Node Lesions
OP 3	NWIAMP117	Dr. Madhubala Chauhan	Diagnostic Utility of Tzanck Smear in Cutaneous Lesions
OP 4	NWIAMP016	Dr. Anjali Sharma	Immunohistochemical Expression of OCT3/4 in Breast Carcinoma
OP 5	NWIAMP018	Dr. Hemant	Analysis of IDH Expression in Glial Tumors: A one-year Institutional Study
OP 6	NWIAMP026	Dr. Shivali Soni	Immunohistochemical Expression of SOX 10 and GATA3 in Carcinoma Breast
OP 7	NWIAMP028	Dr. Biswasree Deb	Immunohistochemical Expression of PDL1 in Non Small Cell Carcinoma Lung
OP 8	NWIAMP029	Dr. Ankita Yadav	NOX 4 in Non-Small Cell Lung Carcinoma: An Emerging Diagnostic and Therapeutic Biomarker.
OP 9	NWIAMP030	Dr. Sonal Verma	Immunohistochemical Expression of PDL1 in Breast Carcinoma: A Comparative Study before and after Neoadjuvant Chemotherapy
OP 10	NWIAMP034	Dr. Ankita	Role of GATA3 Immunohistochemical Expression in Molecular Subtyping of Urothelial Carcinoma.
OP 11	NWIAMP041	Dr. Chittar Kaur	Diagnostic Utility of OCT3/4, CD117 and CD30 in identifying seminomatous differentiation in pure and mixed germ cell tumors: An Immunohistochemical Study
OP 12	NWIAMP042	Dr. Kiran Kumari	Immunohistochemical Expression of B-CATENIN in Carcinoma Cervix
OP 13	NWIAMP044	Dr. Pragya Koche	Histomorphological spectrum of breast carcinoma: A one-year Institutional Experience
OP 14	NWIAMP045	Dr. Kritika Lohumi	Immunohistochemical Expression of P53 And Ki-67 in Surface Epithelial Ovarian Tumors
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ORAL PRESENTATIONS ABRACTS

OP-1

UNVEILING BREAST FNAC TRENDS WITH THE YOKOHAMA SYSTEM: A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITALS PERSPECTIVE

Dr. Chetna Dhok, Dr. Renuka Verma, Dr. Anjali Ahlawat
PGIMS, Rohtak

Introduction

Breast lesions range from benign conditions to malignant tumors. The IAC Yokohama System for reporting breast FNAC helps to categorize cytological findings and correlates them with the risk of malignancy.

Objectives

1. To categorize breast FNAC cases according to the IAC Yokohama System.
2. To study the distribution of breast lesions in different age groups and genders.
3. To evaluate the spectrum of benign and malignant breast lesions diagnosed by FNAC.

Material and Methods

A retrospective study was conducted over a period of one year in a tertiary care hospital in 360 breast FNAC cases excluding previously treated cases or repeat FNAC samples. Cytological findings were classified according to the IAC Yokohama reporting system.

Results

The study included patients aged between 12 and 85 years, with the majority of cases occurring in the 21–30 year age group. Females constituted 93.8%, while males accounted for 6.2%. Benign lesions formed the largest category (67.8%), malignant lesions accounted for 19.5%, 9.2% cases were categorized as insufficient, 3.0% as atypical, and 0.5% as suspicious for malignancy.

Discussion

FNAC plays an important role in the initial evaluation of breast lumps as part of the triple assessment approach. The IAC Yokohama system provides a standardized framework for reporting breast cytology and helps in predicting the risk of malignancy for each category. The standardized reporting system improves diagnostic accuracy and facilitates effective communication between pathologists and clinicians.

Conclusion

The IAC Yokohama system is a reliable and user-friendly reporting system for breast FNAC.

OP-2

UTILITY OF PROPOSED SYDNEY SYSTEM IN REPORTING AND CLASSIFICATION OF LYMPH NODE LESIONS

Dr. Unnati Bhatt, Dr. Sant Prakash Kataria, Dr. Dishti Sharma, Dr. Sanjay Kumar, Dr. Rajnish Kalra,
Dr. Sunita Singh

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Introduction

Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology FNAC is a rapid, minimally invasive, and cost-effective first-line diagnostic modality for lymphadenopathy. To address variability in conventional cytology reporting which affects diagnostic clarity and clinical decision-making, the Sydney System for Reporting Lymph Node Cytology (2020) introduced a standardized five-tier diagnostic framework for uniform reporting and risk stratification.

Objective

To evaluate and categorize lymph node lesions using proposed Sydney System.

Material and Methods

This observational study included 1000 cases of enlarged lymph nodes that underwent FNAC during the year 2025. Archived cytology smears and records were reviewed and classified according to the Revised Sydney System into five diagnostic categories: L1(Inadequate/Non-diagnostic), L2(Benign), L3(Atypical cells of undetermined significance), L4(Suspicious for malignancy), and L5(Malignant). Available histopathology was correlated and diagnostic performance was analyzed.

Results

1000 cases studied with lymphadenopathy were categorized as Category I/L1- 168 cases, Category II/L2- 571 cases, Category III/L3- 18 cases, Category IV/L4 -20 case, Category V/L5- 223 cases. The L2 category predominantly comprised tubercular, reactive, granulomatous and suppurative lymphadenitis. The L5 category included metastatic carcinoma and lymphomas, with metastatic deposits being more frequent. The L5 category showed male predominance (75%), with higher incidence in elderly population (80% of total cases). Histopathological follow-up in 41 cases of L5 category showed complete concordance with malignant diagnoses, demonstrating high sensitivity and specificity supporting diagnostic reliability of the system.

Discussion and Conclusion

The Revised Sydney Classification is a practical and reliable system for lymph node FNAC reporting, providing structured diagnosis, effective risk stratification, and improved guidance for clinical management.

OP-3

Diagnostic utility of tzanck smear in cutaneous lesions

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PGIMS, ROHTAK

Introduction

Cytopathology is a valuable tool in the diagnosis of various skin lesions. Cytologic examination of skin lesions, also known as Tzanck smear, is a simple, quick, noninvasive, inexpensive procedure to perform, with little special equipment or training required.

Objective

To assess the role of Tzanck Smear in diagnosing various cutaneous lesions and their correlation with biopsy findings.

Material and methods

The study material constituted 100 cases of Tzanck smear from various skin lesions (benign and malignant). Cytological evaluation was done and results were correlated with histopathological findings. However, in case of vesiculobullous lesions, immunofluorescence findings were also correlated for further confirmation of the diagnosis.

Result

Out of 100 cases, 60 were females and 40 were males with an average age of 43.2 years. Spectrum of skin disorders diagnosed with Tzanck smear includes immunobullous diseases (42%), cutaneous infections (11), granulomatous inflammations (10), tumors (23), non-specific inflammations (7) and inflammatory dermatosis (7). Tzanck smear demonstrated high sensitivity (98.9%) and high specificity (90.9%) in diagnosing various skin lesions. These findings support the usefulness of Tzanck smear as a rapid and reliable diagnostic tool, especially in vesiculobullous disorders.

Discussion

Tzanck smear is a rapid, inexpensive and a safe tool for the early diagnosis of vesiculobullous lesions. Although, not a substitute for standard histopathology, it can serve as a useful adjunct in the diagnosis of certain vesiculobullous disorders, bacterial, viral, fungal and granulomatous inflammation.

Conclusion

Cytology has been proven as a reliable and informative tool in the diagnosis of various skin lesions. As technology continues to advance, cytology is expected to offer much more in diagnosis of various skin lesions.

OP-4

Immunohistochemical Expression of Oct3/4 in breast Carcinoma

Dr Anjali Sharma, Dr Meenu Gill, Dr Sunita Singh

PGIMS, Rohtak

Introduction

Breast cancer is the most common malignancy and a leading cause of cancer-related mortality among women worldwide. According to the IARC-WHO, India reported the highest number of female breast cancer deaths (98,337). Oct3/4 is a key regulator of pluripotency and self-renewal in embryonic stem cells. Its expression is usually low or absent in differentiated adult tissues but has been reported in various cancers, including breast cancer and testicular germ cell tumors. Increased expression of Oct3/4 has been associated with drug resistance, poor clinical outcomes, its potential role as a prognostic biomarker and therapeutic target.

Objectives

To evaluate the immunohistochemical expression of Oct3/4 in breast carcinoma and assess its correlation with histological grade. Materials and Methods: A one-year observational study was conducted at Pt. B. D. Sharma PGIMS, Rohtak, including 60 cases of breast carcinoma. Immunohistochemical staining for Oct3/4 was performed on tumor tissue sections. The expression pattern was evaluated and correlated with histological grade and other clinicopathological parameters, including the Ki-67 proliferation index.

Results

Positive Oct3/4 expression was more frequently observed in higher histological grades of breast carcinoma. Grade III tumors demonstrated significantly stronger expression compared with Grade I and Grade II tumors ($p < 0.0001$). 95% of cases showed positive Oct3/4 expression also exhibited a high Ki-67 index ($p < 0.001$).

Discussion

Higher expression of Oct3/4 in poorly differentiated tumors suggests its role in tumor progression and increased proliferative activity.

Conclusion

Oct3/4 may serve as a potential biomarker of poor prognosis in breast carcinoma, as its expression increases with higher histological grade.

OP-5

ANALYSIS OF IDH EXPRESSION IN GLIAL TUMORS: A ONE-YEAR INSTITUTIONAL STUDY

Dr Hemant, Dr Sumiti Gupta, Dr Nisha Marwah, Dr Sunita Singh

PGIMS, Rohtak

Introduction

Glial tumors are the most common primary CNS tumors and show marked histological and molecular heterogeneity. IDH expression has emerged as an important molecular marker in diffuse gliomas. Immunohistochemical detection of IDH1 expression aids in tumor classification, differentiation of glioma subtypes, and provides valuable prognostic information for predicting patient outcome.

Objectives

To evaluate the expression of IDH1 in glial tumors and correlate it with different histological types and grades of gliomas.

Methods

The study was conducted in the Department of Pathology, Pt. B. D. Sharma PGIMS, Rohtak. Histopathologically confirmed glial tumors from biopsy and surgical specimens were included. Hematoxylin and eosin staining assessed morphology, while immunohistochemistry using IDH1 (R132H) antibody detected mutations. IDH positivity was evaluated and correlated with glial tumor subtype and WHO grade.

Results

IDH1 mutation was detected in about 40–45% of diffuse gliomas. It was more common in low-grade astrocytomas and oligodendrogliomas, while most primary glioblastomas were IDH-negative. Mutation frequency was higher in grade 2 and 3 tumors than grade 4, supporting IDH as an important molecular marker with prognostic significance in gliomas.

Conclusion

Immunohistochemical detection of IDH1 expression is a reliable method for molecular characterization of glial tumors. IDH expression are commonly associated with lower-grade gliomas and secondary glioblastomas, reflecting a distinct tumor pathway. Routine IDH testing improves glioma classification accuracy and provides important prognostic information for better clinical management and patient outcome prediction.

Keywords

IDH1 mutation, Glial tumors, Glioma, Immunohistochemistry, Diffuse glioma

OP-6

IMMUNOHISTOCHEMICAL EXPRESSION OF SOX10 AND GATA3 IN CARCINOMA BREAST

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PGIMS, Rohtak

Introduction

Breast carcinoma is a heterogeneous malignancy requiring accurate classification for prognosis and therapy. Immunohistochemical markers such as ER, PR, and HER2 guide molecular subtyping. GATA3 is commonly expressed in luminal tumors, while SOX10 is associated with basal-like and triple-negative carcinomas. Combined evaluation improves diagnostic accuracy.

Objective

To study SOX10 and GATA3 expression in carcinoma breast and correlate their expression with various clinico-pathological parameters.

Material and Methods

This observational study was conducted in the Department of Pathology at Pt. B. D. Sharma PGIMS, Rohtak over a period of two years. A total of 70 histologically confirmed breast carcinoma cases were included. Tissue samples were processed using standard histopathological techniques and stained with hematoxylin and eosin. IHC staining for SOX10 and GATA3 was performed on tumor sections. Expression was assessed based on staining intensity and the percentage of positive tumor cells. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 24 and associations between IHC expression and clinicopathological parameters were analyzed using the Chi-square test.

Results

Among 70 breast carcinoma cases, most patients were in age group 41–50 years, with left-sided tumors predominating. Invasive ductal carcinoma was the most common histological type. Luminal A was the predominant molecular subtype. GATA3 showed high positivity, mainly in luminal tumors, while SOX10 expression was low and mainly associated with triple-negative breast carcinoma.

Discussion

GATA3 and SOX10 are important immunohistochemical markers in breast carcinoma. In our study, GATA3 showed high positivity (80%), in luminal tumors and ER-positive cases, while SOX10 positivity was low (7.1%) and was predominantly associated with triple-negative breast carcinoma cases which was concordant with the previous studies.

Conclusion

In this study, GATA3 showed high expression mainly in luminal tumors, while SOX10 positivity was rare but predominantly associated with triple-negative breast carcinoma, highlighting their complementary diagnostic value.

OP-7

Immunohistochemical Expression of PDL 1 in Non Small Cell Carcinoma Lung

Dr. Biswasree Deb, Dr Meenu Gill, Dr Sunita Singh

PGIMS, Rohtak

Introduction

Lung cancer is a leading cause of cancer-related deaths worldwide, with poor outcomes due to its aggressive nature and frequent metastasis. High expression of PDL-1, an immune checkpoint molecule, on cancer cells suppresses antitumor immune responses, contributing to poor prognosis and lower overall survival in lung cancer patients.

Objectives

To evaluate the immunohistochemical expression of PDL-1 in various types and stages of Non Small Cell Lung Carcinoma.

Materials and Method

A one-year observational study of 50 Non-Small Cell Lung Carcinoma cases was conducted at Pt. B D Sharma PGIMS, Rohtak, evaluating PDL-1 expression via immunohistochemistry and correlating with clinicopathological parameters.

Results

PDL-1 positivity was observed in 16/50 cases (32.0%), varying non-significantly across histologies ($p=0.6140$). A significant link was seen with differentiation ($p=0.0001$): poorly differentiated tumors showed 50.0% positivity (23.3% weak, 26.6% strong), whereas 95.0% of moderately differentiated tumors were negative.

Discussion

The convergence of findings from the present study and existing research underscores the role of PDL 1 as a biomarker of poor prognosis in cancer. Elevated PDL-1 expression is characteristically observed in tumors with aggressive phenotypes, marked by poor differentiation and higher histological grades. This association suggests that PDL-1 may serve as an indicator of tumor aggressiveness, potentially guiding clinical assessments and therapeutic strategies.

Conclusion

The study reinforces PDL-1 as a biomarker of poor prognosis in cancer, associating its elevated expression with aggressive tumor phenotypes and poor differentiation, potentially guiding clinical assessments and therapy.

OP-8

NOX4 IN NON-SMALL CELL LUNG CARCINOMA: AN EMERGING DIAGNOSTIC AND THERAPEUTIC BIOMARKER.

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PGIMS, ROHTAK

Introduction

Non-small cell lung carcinoma (NSCLC) accounts for nearly 85% of lung cancers and remains the leading cause of cancer-related mortality globally. Despite advances in molecular classification and targeted therapies, treatment resistance and disease progression continue to limit survival benefits. Increasing evidence identifies NADPH oxidase 4 (NOX4), a key regulator of intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS), as a critical mediator of tumor-associated oxidative signalling in NSCLC. Aim will be to review the current evidence regarding the role of NOX4 in the pathogenesis, progression, therapeutic and prognosis targeting of NSCLC.

Objectives

1. To review the molecular role of NOX4 in NSCLC pathogenesis.
2. To assess its potential as a therapeutic target.

Materials and Methods:

A structured review of published literature was conducted using indexed databases, including experimental, translational, and clinical studies assessing NOX4 expression and signaling pathways in NSCLC. Data regarding molecular mechanisms, correlation with tumor stage and survival, and therapeutic inhibition were analyzed.

Results

Multiple studies demonstrate significant overexpression of NOX4 in NSCLC, including lung adenocarcinoma and squamous cell carcinoma, with strong correlation to higher tumor stage, lymph node metastasis, poor differentiation, and reduced overall survival. NOX4-derived ROS activates key oncogenic cascades including PI3K/AKT, MAPK/ERK, and TGF- β pathways, promoting epithelial-mesenchymal transition, angiogenesis, metabolic reprogramming, and immune evasion. Importantly, NOX4 upregulation has been linked to chemoresistance and radioresistance, highlighting its predictive significance. Experimental inhibition of NOX4 in vitro and in vivo models demonstrates reduced proliferation, invasion, and tumor growth, underscoring its therapeutic potential.

Discussion

NOX4 acts as a central redox mediator in NSCLC progression and therapeutic resistance. Its consistent association with adverse clinicopathological parameters and demonstrated targetability highlight its promise as a diagnostic, prognostic, and therapeutic biomarker.

Conclusion

Targeted inhibition of NOX4 may represent a strategic approach in precision therapy for NSCLC.

OP-9

IMMUNOHISTOCHEMICAL EXPRESSION OF PD-L1 IN BREAST CARCINOMA: A COMPARATIVE STUDY BEFORE AND AFTER NEOADJUVANT CHEMOTHERAPY

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PGIMS, Rohtak.

Introduction

Breast carcinoma is one of the most common malignancies affecting women worldwide and shows considerable heterogeneity in biological behaviour and therapeutic response. Programmed cell death ligand-1 (PD-L1) is an immune checkpoint protein that allows tumour cells to evade immune surveillance by inhibiting T-cell mediated immune responses. PD-L1 has recently emerged as a potential biomarker for predicting response to immune checkpoint inhibitors in several malignancies, including breast cancer. Neoadjuvant chemotherapy is commonly used in locally advanced breast carcinoma to reduce tumour burden and improve surgical outcomes. However, the impact of chemotherapy on PD-L1 expression remains unclear.

Objectives

To evaluate and compare immunohistochemical expression of PD-L1 in breast carcinoma before and after neoadjuvant chemotherapy and to determine its association with clinicopathological parameters and molecular subtypes.

Materials and Methods

This observational study included 50 patients with breast carcinoma who received neoadjuvant chemotherapy. Pre-treatment trucut biopsy specimens and post-chemotherapy mastectomy specimens were examined histopathologically. Immunohistochemistry was performed for ER, PR, HER2/neu, Ki-67, and PD-L1. PD-L1 expression was assessed based on membranous staining in tumour cells and correlated with clinicopathological variables.

Results

PD-L1 positivity was observed in 16% of cases prior to chemotherapy, while the majority remained negative. Post-chemotherapy evaluation demonstrated no significant alteration in PD-L1 expression. PD-L1 positivity was more frequently observed in aggressive molecular subtypes, particularly triple-negative and HER2-enriched tumours. A significant association was also noted between PD-L1 expression and higher pre-treatment Ki-67 index.

Discussion & Conclusion

PD-L1 expression appears stable following neoadjuvant chemotherapy and shows association with aggressive tumour biology. These findings suggest its potential utility as a predictive biomarker for identifying breast cancer patients who may benefit from immune checkpoint inhibitor therapy.

OP-10

Role of GATA3 immunohistochemical expression in molecular subtyping of Urothelial carcinoma.

Dr Ankita, Dr Sunita Singh

PGIMS, Rohtak

Introduction

Urothelial carcinoma of the bladder is a common malignancy with significant biological heterogeneity and variable clinical outcomes. Recent molecular studies have identified distinct subtypes of bladder cancer that differ in prognosis and therapeutic response. Molecular profiling methods, are accurate but expensive and not routinely available. Immunohistochemistry provides a practical and cost-effective alternative for identifying tumor differentiation patterns. GATA3, has emerged as a sensitive marker for urothelial carcinoma and plays an important role in identifying tumors with luminal differentiation.

Material and Methods

This observational study was conducted in the Department of Pathology at Pt. B. D. Sharma PGIMS, Rohtak. Histopathologically confirmed cases of urothelial carcinoma were included. Representative tumor sections were subjected to immunohistochemical staining for GATA3, its expression was evaluated and correlated with tumor grade, depth of invasion, and other clinicopathological parameters. Results:

GATA3 expression was observed in a majority of urothelial carcinoma cases, demonstrating strong nuclear staining in tumor cells. Positive expression was predominantly associated with tumors showing features of urothelial differentiation.

Discussion

The findings highlight the diagnostic utility of GATA3 as a sensitive immunohistochemical marker for urothelial carcinoma. Its nuclear expression assists in confirming urothelial origin. The use of a single reliable marker such as GATA3 may facilitate molecular characterization in routine pathology practice.

Conclusion

GATA3 is a valuable immunohistochemical marker in the evaluation of urothelial carcinoma. Its expression aids in identifying urothelial differentiation and contributes to molecular characterization of tumors, thereby supporting improved diagnostic accuracy and potential prognostic assessment in bladder cancer.

OP-11

Diagnostic Utility of OCT3/4, CD117 and CD30 in Identifying Seminomatous Differentiation in Pure and Mixed Germ Cell Tumors: An Immunohistochemical Study

Dr. Chittarkaur, Dr. Nisha Marwah, Dr. Sunita Singh

PGIMS, Rohtak

Introduction

Seminoma is the most common testicular germ cell tumor affecting young adult males and may occur as a pure tumor or within mixed germ cell tumors. Although it usually shows characteristic morphology, overlapping features may cause diagnostic difficulty. Immunohistochemical markers such as OCT3/4, CD117, and CD30 help in distinguishing seminoma from non-seminomatous germ cell tumors.

Objectives

1. To study the histopathological features of seminoma.
2. To evaluate the immunohistochemical expression of OCT3/4, CD117, and CD30 in seminoma.

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted in the Department of Pathology, Pt. B.D. Sharma PGIMS, Rohtak. Eighteen Cases diagnosed as seminoma on histopathological examination were included. Hematoxylin and eosin-stained sections were reviewed for morphological features, and immunohistochemical expression of OCT3/4, CD117, and CD30 was evaluated.

Results

A total of 18 cases of seminoma/seminomatous component in mixed Germ Cell Tumors were identified. Histologically, tumors showed sheets and nests of large polygonal cells with clear cytoplasm, prominent nucleoli, and fibrous septa with lymphocytic infiltrates. OCT3/4 showed nuclear positivity in all cases (18/18; 100%), while CD117 demonstrated membranous positivity in 61.1% cases (11/18). CD30 expression was absent in all cases (0/18).

Discussion

OCT3/4, a pluripotency-associated transcription factor, showed 100% positivity, confirming its high sensitivity for seminoma. CD117 also showed significant expression, supporting its role as an adjunct marker. In contrast, CD30 negativity helps exclude embryonal carcinoma.

Conclusion

A focused panel of OCT3/4, CD117, and CD30 provides a reliable approach for confirming seminomatous differentiation and distinguishing seminoma from non-seminomatous germ cell tumors.

OP12- Immunohistochemical Expression of β -Catenin in Carcinoma Cervix

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PT.B.D. SHARMA PGIMS ROHTAK

Introduction:

Carcinoma cervix remains one of the most common malignancies among women, particularly in developing countries such as India. Tumor progression involves alterations in cell adhesion molecules and intracellular signaling pathways. Aberrant expression and altered cellular localization of β -catenin have been implicated in tumor progression and invasion in cervical carcinoma.

Objectives:

To evaluate the immunohistochemical expression of β -catenin in carcinoma cervix and to determine its correlation with various clinicopathological parameters.

Material and Methods:

This study was conducted in the Department of Pathology, Pt. B. D. Sharma PGIMS, Rohtak. A total of 110 cases of carcinoma cervix were included in the study. Hematoxylin and eosin-stained sections were reviewed for histopathological examination. Immunohistochemistry for β -catenin was performed on representative sections. Membranous alone or associated dim cytoplasmic staining were considered as normal pattern, all other patterns were considered abnormal.

Results:

Among 110 cases, Squamous cell carcinoma constituted 106 cases (96.4%) and adenocarcinoma 4 cases (3.6%). Among squamous cell carcinomas, 60 cases (54.5%) were moderately differentiated, 31 (28.2%) poorly differentiated, and 15 (13.6%) well differentiated. Many cases showed reduced membranous staining with increased cytoplasmic β -catenin expression.

Discussion:

Altered β -catenin expression indicates disruption of the cadherin–catenin complex, leading to reduced cell adhesion and increased tumor invasiveness. These findings support the role of β -catenin in the molecular pathogenesis and progression of cervical carcinoma.

Conclusion:

Aberrant β -catenin expression is frequently observed in carcinoma cervix and may serve as a useful adjunct marker for understanding tumor behavior and predicting prognosis.

**HISTOMORPHOLOGICAL SPECTRUM OF BREAST CARCINOMA: A ONE-YEAR
INSTITUTIONAL EXPERIENCE**

Dr Pragya Koche, name: Dr Sumiti Gupta, Dr Nisha Marwah, Dr. Veena Gupta, Dr Meenu Gill, Dr
Sunita Singh

PGIMS, Rohtak

Introduction

Breast carcinoma represents the most common malignancy among women and contributes significantly to surgical pathology workload. Core needle biopsy (CNB) enables early diagnosis and treatment planning, while modified radical mastectomy (MRM) specimens provide definitive histopathological evaluation.

Objective

To determine frequency distribution of breast tumour subtypes.

Material and Methods

A retrospective descriptive study was conducted in the Department of Pathology, PGIMS Rohtak from February 2025 to February 2026. A total of 410 breast specimens, including core needle biopsies and MRM specimens, were evaluated. Haematoxylin and eosin–stained sections were reviewed and tumours classified using standard histomorphological criteria.

Results

Invasive ductal carcinoma accounted for 381 cases (92.9%). Other lesions included ductal carcinoma (3.4%), phyllodes tumour (1.2%), lobular carcinoma (0.5%), metaplastic carcinoma (0.5%), and rare variants such as mucinous, tubular, secretory carcinoma, adenocarcinoma (NOS), mucinous adenocarcinoma, and mesenchymal tumors (each 0.24%).

Discussion

The predominance of invasive ductal carcinoma correlates with global epidemiological data. CNB proved reliable for early diagnosis, whereas MRM specimens enabled confirmation and comprehensive tumor assessment.

Conclusion

Combined evaluation of CNB and MRM specimens provides accurate histopathological characterization and supports optimal therapeutic decision-making.

Keywords

Breast carcinoma, Core needle biopsy, Modified radical mastectomy, Histomorphology

**IMMUNOHISTOCHEMICAL EXPRESSION OF P53 AND KI-67 IN SURFACE
EPITHELIAL OVARIAN TUMORS**

Dr. Kritika Lohumi, Dr. Veena Gupta, Dr. Sunita Singh

PGIMS, Rohtak

Introduction

Surface epithelial ovarian tumors (SEOTs) constitute majority of ovarian neoplasms. Immunohistochemical markers such as p53 and Ki-67 help in assessing tumor aggressiveness and biological behaviour.

Objectives

To evaluate the immunohistochemical expression of p53 and Ki-67 in SEOTs and correlate their expression with histopathological subtype and tumor grade.

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted in the Department of Pathology, PGIMS, Rohtak. Fifty histopathologically confirmed cases of SEOTs were included. p53 staining patterns and Ki-67 labelling index were assessed and correlated with tumor type and grade. Statistical analysis was performed using Fisher's exact test ($p < 0.05$ considered significant).

Results

Among these cases, 34 were malignant, 12 benign, and 4 borderline tumors. Serous tumors constituted the majority (76%), followed by mucinous tumors (18%). Among malignant tumors, 26 cases were high-grade and 8 cases were low-grade.

Benign tumors demonstrated wild-type p53 expression, while mutant p53 expression with predominance of diffuse overexpression was seen. High Ki-67 labeling index was predominant in malignant tumors, whereas none of the benign or borderline tumors showed high Ki-67 expression. High Ki-67 expression also showed significant association with high tumor grade and with mutant p53 expression ($p = 0.0028$).

Discussion

The observed predominance of mutant p53 expression and higher Ki-67 labelling index in malignant and high-grade tumors reflects increased genetic instability and proliferative activity in aggressive SEOTs.

Conclusion

The significant association of mutant p53 expression and high Ki-67 index with malignant and high-grade tumors underscores their role as indicators of tumor progression and proliferative potential in SEOTs.

HISTOPATHOLOGICAL SPECTRUM OF URINARY BLADDER LESIONS WITH EMPHASIS ON TUMOR GRADING, DEPTH OF INVASION AND UNCOMMON ENTITIES: AN INSTITUTIONAL STUDY

Dr. Kovarthanan A, Dr. Sunita Singh, Dr Veena Gupta, Dr Simran
PGIMS, Rohtak

Introduction

Urinary bladder cancer is the 10th most common malignancy worldwide. Urothelial carcinoma constitutes nearly 90–95% of primary bladder tumors. Tumor grade and depth of invasion are important prognostic indicators. Histopathological examination therefore remains essential for accurate diagnosis and staging.

Objectives

The study aimed to evaluate the histopathological spectrum of urinary bladder lesions, with emphasis on tumor grading, depth of invasion and identification of uncommon entities.

Material and methods

A retrospective descriptive study was conducted in the Pathology Department at PGIMS, Rohtak over a one-year period from January to December 2025. A total of 153 urinary bladder specimens including TURBT chips, bladder biopsies and excised bladder masses were analyzed. Specimens were fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin, stained with H&E and IHC applied.

Results

The majority of patients belonged to the 6th and 7th decades, with a marked male predominance. Urothelial carcinoma was the predominant diagnosis. High-grade tumors (94 cases; 61.4%) were more frequent than low-grade tumors (59 cases; 38.6%). Tumor invasion involved lamina propria (42.5%) and muscularis propria (34.6%). Rare tumors included small cell neuroendocrine carcinoma, non-Hodgkin lymphoma and prostatic adenocarcinoma infiltration.

Discussion

The findings highlight that urothelial carcinoma remains the dominant bladder malignancy, predominantly affecting elderly males. Assessment of tumor grade and depth of invasion is essential for staging and therapeutic planning. Recognition of rare tumors is important because their clinical management differs.

Conclusion

Urinary bladder lesions demonstrate a broad histopathological spectrum. Accurate evaluation of tumor grade and invasion depth remains crucial for prognosis and clinical management.

OP-16

Mismatch repair protein MLH1 and MSH2 in colorectal carcinoma

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PGIMS, Rohtak

Introduction

Colorectal carcinoma (CRC) is one of the most common malignancies of the gastrointestinal tract and a major cause of cancer-related morbidity and mortality worldwide. Defects in the DNA mismatch repair (MMR) system lead to microsatellite instability and play an important role in colorectal carcinogenesis. MLH1 and MSH2 are key proteins involved in maintaining genomic stability. Loss of their expression indicates mismatch repair deficiency and may be associated with hereditary conditions such as Lynch syndrome. IHC is a reliable method for detecting these proteins in tumor tissues.

Objectives

To evaluate the immunohistochemical expression of MLH1 and MSH2 in colorectal carcinoma and correlate their expression with clinicopathological parameters.

Materials and Methods

This observational study was conducted in the Department of Pathology, Pt. B. D. Sharma PGIMS, Rohtak, over 2 years. Fifty histologically confirmed cases of colorectal carcinoma from colectomy specimens were included. Routine histopathological examination was performed using hematoxylin and eosin staining. IHC staining for MLH1 and MSH2 was carried out on tumor sections. Statistical analysis was done using SPSS version 24 with the Chi-square test.

Results

The mean age was 54.7 ± 16.6 years with male predominance (58%). Adenocarcinoma was the most common subtype (80%), and most tumors were moderately differentiated (68%). Loss of MLH1 expression was observed in 22% and MSH2 in 16% of cases, with concurrent loss in 16%. A significant association was seen with younger age groups.

Conclusion

IHC evaluation of MLH1 and MSH2 is useful for detecting mismatch repair deficiency in colorectal carcinoma and may help identify patients requiring further genetic evaluation.

OP-17-Skin adnexal tumors unveiled: A tertiary care perspective from North India

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PGIMS, ROHTAK

Background

Skin adnexal tumors (SATs) encompass wide spectrum of benign and malignant tumors that differentiate toward one or more adnexal structures found in normal skin. Overall incidence of SATs is low, yet they can be challenging to diagnose.

Objectives

The aim of this study was to evaluate the morphological, clinical, and histological features of SATs and categorize them according to their line of differentiation.

Materials and Methods

The present study was a retrospective study conducted over a period of 3 years from January 2021 to December 2024 including a total of 75 cases diagnosed as SATs in the department of Pathology at Pt. B.D. Sharma Institute of Medical Sciences, Rohtak. Formalin fixed, paraffin-embedded sections were stained with hematoxylin and eosin for histopathological analysis.

Results

Most of the ATs were benign (74/75) with head and neck being the most common location (52%). The hair follicle tumors accounted for the largest number of cases 50.67% (38/75), followed by eccrine tumors 38.67% (29/75), apocrine tumors 6.67% (5/75), and sebaceous gland tumors 2.67% (2/75).

Discussion

Overall incidence of SATs is low, yet they can be challenging to diagnose.

Conclusion

Histopathological examination is gold standard for establishing diagnosis of SATs due to its indistinctive clinical presentation.

OP-18

Evaluation of Salivary miR-125b and Immunohistochemical Expression of Bcl-2 and p53 in Oral Lichen Planus

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Post Graduate Institute Of Dental Sciences, Rohtak

Introduction

Oral lichen planus (OLP) is a chronic immune-mediated disease classified as a potentially malignant disorder with an uncertain molecular pathogenesis. Dysregulation of apoptosis-related pathways involving microRNA-125b, p53, and Bcl-2 may contribute to disease persistence and its progression towards oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC).

Objectives

This study aimed to quantify salivary miR-125b expression in normal individuals, OLP, and OSCC, evaluate the immunohistochemical expression of Bcl-2 and p53, and correlate salivary miR-125b levels with tissue expression of these markers.

Methods

A prospective cross-sectional study was conducted on 42 participants, 14 each of healthy individuals, OLP and OSCC. Salivary microRNA -125b expression was quantified using RT-qPCR. Expression of p53 and Bcl-2 was evaluated in corresponding biopsy specimens using immunohistochemistry. Data were analysed using non-parametric statistical tests, with $p < 0.05$ considered significant.

Results

Median (IQR) salivary microRNA-125b expression demonstrated a significant decline across normal mucosa, OLP, and OSCC groups ($p = 0.010$). p53 expression showed a significant stepwise increase ($p < 0.001$), while Bcl-2 expression also increased significantly ($p = 0.026$). A moderate positive correlation was observed between Bcl-2 and p53 ($\rho = 0.320$, $p = 0.039$). Correlations between microRNA-125b and both markers were negative but not statistically significant.

Conclusion

Reduced salivary microRNA-125b expression accompanied by increased p53 and Bcl-2 expression suggests alterations in apoptosis-related molecular pathways in OLP and OSCC. The combined evaluation of these biomarkers may provide insight into molecular changes associated with disease progression. Salivary miR-125b may represent a potential non-invasive biomarker for monitoring molecular alterations in OLP.

EXPRESSION OF PROGRAMMED DEATH 1/PROGRAMMED DEATH LIGAND 1 AND CD4+ T CELLS IN PERIAPICAL GRANULOMA AND RADICULAR CYST- AN IMMUNOHISTOCHEMICAL STUDY

Dr. Astha Upadhyay, Dr. Mala Kamboj, Dr. Shweta Mittal, Dr. Anjali Narwal, Dr. Anju Devi, Dr. Adarsh Kumar

PGIDS, Rohtak

Introduction

The progression of periapical lesions is governed by a complex interplay between microbial factors and host immune responses. Immune checkpoint molecules such as programmed death-1 (PD-1) and programmed death ligand-1 (PD-L1) regulate T-cell activation and immune tolerance, potentially contributing to the persistence and chronicity of periapical pathoses. This pilot study aimed to evaluate and compare the immunoexpression of CD4, PD-1, and PD-L1 in periapical granuloma and radicular cyst and to correlate their expression with the intensity of inflammatory infiltrate and the thickness of cystic epithelial lining.

Objectives

To evaluate PD-1 and PD-L1 expression and CD4⁺ T-cell infiltration in periapical granuloma and radicular cyst, and to assess their correlation with inflammatory score and epithelial lining thickness in radicular cyst.

Material and Methods

An observational cross-sectional study was conducted on 81 formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded tissue sections, including 27 cases each of periapical granuloma and radicular cyst, 14 healthy pulp samples, and 13 normal oral mucosa samples. Morphological and immunohistochemical analyses were performed using anti-CD4, PD-1, and PD-L1 antibodies. The mean number of CD4⁺ T cells, mean PD-1 and PD-L1 expression, and inflammatory score were calculated. Statistical analysis was performed using the Kruskal–Wallis H test, Mann–Whitney U test, Chi-square test, and Spearman correlation test ($p < .05$).

Results

CD4 expression was significantly higher in radicular cyst than in periapical granuloma ($p = .010$). PD-L1 expression was significantly higher in periapical granuloma ($p = .003$), while PD-1 expression was observed only in periapical granuloma ($p < .001$). The inflammatory score was similar in both groups with predominance of severe inflammation ($p = .82$). A non-significant correlation was found between CD4, PD-1, and PD-L1 in both lesions; however, CD4⁺ T cells showed a significant correlation with inflammatory score in periapical granuloma ($p = .006$).

Discussion and Conclusion

The significant expression of PD-1, PD-L1, and CD4⁺ T cells in periapical granuloma suggests an exhausted or dysfunctional immune response in long-standing lesions, possibly acting as an intrinsic mechanism to regulate persistent inflammation and limit excessive periapical bone destruction. In contrast, the absence of PD-1 expression in radicular cyst indicates the involvement of alternative immune regulatory pathways in its pathogenesis and progression. Further studies with a broader panel of immune cell markers are required to better elucidate the immune regulatory mechanisms underlying these lesions.

**EVALUATION OF HISTOLOGICAL PROGNOSTICATORS IN INCISIONAL BIOPSY
VERSUS CORRESPONDING RESECTIONS OF ORAL SQUAMOUS CELL CARCINOMA –
AN IMMUNOHISTOCHEMICAL STUDY**

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Virendra Singh

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Introduction

Accurate preoperative prognostic assessment in oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC) is important for treatment planning and risk stratification. Incisional biopsy is routinely used for diagnosis, but its ability to represent definitive histopathological prognostic parameters, particularly those related to the invasive tumor front, remains uncertain.

Objectives

To evaluate the concordance of Ki 67 labelling index, tumor budding score, CD57 positive tumor infiltrating lymphocytes (TILs), and Bryne's invasive front grading between incisional biopsy and corresponding resection specimens in OSCC.

Material and Methods

A cross sectional observational study was conducted on 30 cases of OSCC with available incisional biopsy and corresponding resection specimens. Ki 67 labelling index, tumor budding score, CD57 positive TILs, and Bryne's invasive front grading were assessed in both specimen types. Statistical analysis was performed to determine agreement and correlation ($p < 0.05$).

Results

Bryne's grading showed good agreement between biopsy and resection specimens ($p = 0.227$). Ki 67 labelling index showed excellent concordance ($\rho = 0.945$, $p < 0.001$). TIL counts showed significant correlation ($\rho = 0.687$, $p < 0.001$). Tumor budding scores were lower in biopsy specimens than resection specimens ($p < 0.001$) but showed moderate correlation ($\rho = 0.613$, $p < 0.001$). No significant correlation was observed among Ki 67, tumor budding, and TILs.

Discussion and Conclusion

Incisional biopsy reliably reflects Ki 67 expression, TIL density, and Bryne's grading in OSCC. Tumor budding is underestimated but reflects relative severity. Biopsy assessment can aid preoperative risk stratification, while resection specimens remain the gold standard.

OP-21

Detection of MLL/KMT2A Gene Rearrangements by Fluorescence In Situ Hybridization in Pediatric Acute Leukemias and their Clinicopathological Correlation

Dr Suman Sharma, Dr. Monika Gupta, Dr. Divya Dhull, Dr. Sunita Singh

PGIMS Rohtak

Introduction

Acute leukemias are clonal hematopoietic malignancies characterized by genetic and molecular alterations that influence prognosis and therapeutic strategies. Cytogenetic abnormalities, particularly MLL/KMT2A gene rearrangements, are associated with aggressive disease biology in pediatric acute leukemias. Fluorescence in situ hybridization (FISH) offers a rapid and sensitive method for detecting such abnormalities.

Objectives

To detect MLL/KMT2A gene rearrangements using FISH and correlate these abnormalities with clinical and laboratory parameters in pediatric acute leukemia patients.

Methods

This prospective observational study was conducted over a two-year period. Newly diagnosed pediatric acute leukemia cases confirmed by morphology and immunophenotyping were subjected to FISH analysis for MLL/KMT2A gene rearrangement using peripheral blood or bone marrow samples. Standard laboratory protocols were followed.

Results

A total of 32 pediatric acute leukemia cases were analyzed. Acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) constituted 84.3% of cases, while acute myeloid leukemia (AML) accounted for 15.6%. MLL/KMT2A gene rearrangement was detected in 4 cases (12.5%), all of which were ALL. Among infants (<1 year), 50% were positive compared to 8.6% positivity in children above one year.

Discussion and Conclusion

MLL/KMT2A gene rearrangements were predominantly observed in infantile ALL and were associated with adverse biological behavior. FISH is a valuable diagnostic tool for early detection of clinically significant genetic abnormalities, supporting its routine use in pediatric acute leukemia diagnostics.

Keywords

Acute leukemia, Pediatric leukemia, MLL/KMT2A, FISH, Cytogenetics

OP-22 A MULTI-EPI TOPE PEPTIDE VACCINATION AGAINST TRIPLE-NEGATIVE BREAST CANCER: IN SILICO DESIGN AND IN VITRO VALIDATION

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PGIMS ROHTAK

One of the most prevalent malignancies in women is breast cancer (BC), whose incidence is alarmingly rising. Given the high prevalence and rising incidence of breast cancer, more focus needs to be placed on creating effective treatments. There are currently a number of unresolved limitations with standard passive therapy. On the other hand, new immunotherapy approaches, such as cancer vaccines, have demonstrated promising results in treating advanced breast cancer. The main goal was to develop a multi-epitope vaccination against breast cancer using the five most antigenic proteins. We first identified antigenic protein epitopes and assessed their immunogenicity in order to stimulate robust immune responses. Promiscuous epitopes were conjugated with the proper adjuvant (50S ribosomal L7/IL-12 protein) and included the proper linkers (GPGPG, AAY, and EAAAK) to reduce junctional immunogenicity. To obtain a better 3D model, the best estimated 3D model was improved and confirmed. The structural integrity and stability of the vaccine/mouse TLR-2, 4, 7, and 9 complexes were determined using molecular modeling and molecular docking investigations. After optimization, the vaccine was cloned into the pcDNA3.1(+) vector pET28 (+). Additionally, the vaccine's ability to trigger immune responses (B cells, T cells, antibodies, and cytokines) against breast cancer was shown by immunological simulation. As a result, immunoinformatic analysis of the created vaccine shows that it has the capacity to elicit robust humoral and cellular immune responses in the target organism. As a result, it may encourage further research in the field and have potential as a therapeutic agent against breast cancer. These findings provide a foundation for developing effective peptide vaccines against TNBC.

OP-23

Application Of International Academy of Cytologists Yokohama System for Reporting Breast Fine Needle Aspirates and Their Histopathological Correlation.

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Saraswathi Institute Of Medical Sciences

Introduction

Palpable breast lumps are the most common presentation in surgical and pathological practice. FNAC is the initial diagnostic modality in the management of the breast lumps and to prevent unnecessary intervention in benign breast disease.

Objective

To study the correlation between categorizing the fine needle aspirates according to the IAC Yokohama system and their correlation with histopathology.

Material and Methods

This research is a hospital-based observational study of one year beginning in October 2023 and ending in September 2024. A total of 100 cases were studied in the Central Laboratory and Histopathology Lab, SIMS, Hapur

Results

There were a total of 100 cases; divided into category C1, C2, C3, C4 and C5 according to the IAC Yokohama System and subsequent histopathological examination was done.

Discussion

Breast cytology is reported using the IAC Yokohama System (C1–C5). In this study, most cases were benign (C2), with fibroadenoma being the most common lesion. C3 and C4 categories represented gray-zone and suspicious lesions, while C5 cases showed malignant features and were confirmed as carcinoma on histopathology. Overall, FNAC showed good correlation with histopathology, though inadequate sampling or poor cellularity can occasionally lead to false-negative results.

Conclusion

The study revealed that although FNAC is a useful preoperative tool for diagnosis, histopathology still remains the gold standard.

A 5 year Institutional Experience with Application of the Papanicolaou Society of Cytopathology (PSC), Japan Lung Cancer Society (JLCS) and WHO Reporting Systems for Respiratory Cytopathology with Risk of Malignancy (ROM) assessment

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Introduction:

Respiratory cytology is a minimally invasive diagnostic modality for evaluating lung lesions. Standardized reporting systems improve diagnostic reproducibility and communication between cytopathologists and clinicians. The Japan Lung Cancer Society–Japanese Society of Clinical Cytology (JLCS–JSCC) system, the Papanicolaou Society of Cytopathology (PSC) system, and the WHO–IAC reporting system have been proposed. However, comparative evaluation of these systems in the same cohort remains limited.

Objectives

To apply and compare the JLCS–JSCC, PSC, and WHO–IAC reporting systems for respiratory cytology and assess their Risk of Malignancy (ROM) and diagnostic performance.

Materials and Methods

This retrospective study included 468 respiratory cytology specimens received over five years. All cases were categorized using the three reporting systems. Histopathological correlation was available in 257 cases. ROM, sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, and negative predictive value were calculated. Subgroup analysis was performed for bronchoalveolar lavage and CT-guided FNAC.

Results

Categorization was feasible across all systems. ROM was highest in malignant categories (>90%). Higher ROM in inadequate and benign/negative categories likely reflected sampling limitations. PSC and WHO–IAC demonstrated comparable diagnostic performance, while JLCS–JSCC showed variation due to exclusion of the inadequate category. CT-guided FNAC showed higher sensitivity and specificity than BAL across all systems.

Discussion and Conclusion

Despite structural differences, all three systems showed comparable diagnostic utility. Variations in ROM and diagnostic parameters highlight the impact of system design. CT-guided FNAC emerged as the most reliable modality. These findings support the need for harmonized reporting with context-specific interpretation.

Seminal Calprotectin as a Biomarker in Male Infertility: Association with Semen Parameters

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Title

Seminal Calprotectin as a Biomarker in Male Infertility: Association with Semen Parameters

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Introduction

Seminal plasma akin to serum contains various biochemical components and proteins that may serve as potential biomarkers in the evaluation of male infertility which are cost-effective, and non-invasive.

Aim/Objective

To evaluate the biochemical marker Calprotectin in seminal plasma and its correlation with the quality of semen (sperm count, motility, vitality and morphology of spermatozoa).

Material and Method

A prospective cross-sectional study was conducted on 200 males of infertile couples. Semen analysis was performed according to WHO laboratory manual for the examination and processing of human semen, 6th edition by both manual and automated techniques. Calprotectin levels were measured using ELISA.

Results

The correlation between semen calprotectin levels and semen parameters revealed very weak negative correlations for total sperm count, concentration, motility and normal sperm morphology, indicating increased calprotectin levels slightly reduce these parameters. However, vitality showed a weak positive correlation with calprotectin levels, suggesting a slight increase in sperm vitality with higher calprotectin levels.

Discussion & Conclusion

Calprotectin, an inflammatory protein composed of S100A8 and S100A9 subunits, is a well established marker in IBD, but its role in male infertility remains largely unexplored. Limited evidence suggests that the S100A9 subunit may induce inflammatory processes that negatively affect sperm function, including motility, viability and embryonic development. Calprotectin showed weak negative correlations with most semen parameters suggesting a slight reduction in semen quality with higher levels. Larger scale multi-centric studies are essential to conclusively establish the role of calprotectin in male infertility and its potential implications for clinical practice.

Diagnostic Utility of The International System for Reporting Serous Fluid Cytopathology in Serous Effusions: A Cross-Sectional Analytical Study with Conventional Cytology and Cell Block Correlation

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SGRD

Introduction

Serous effusions are common clinical specimens, and cytological evaluation is important for detecting malignancy. Conventional cytology smears are rapid and cost-effective but may be limited by low cellularity and poor architectural preservation. The International System for Reporting Serous Fluid Cytopathology (TIS) provides standardized reporting categories, while the cell block technique improves cellular yield and preserves tissue architecture, thereby enhancing diagnostic accuracy.

Objectives

To compare conventional cytology with The International System for Reporting Serous Fluid Cytopathology (TIS) and to determine the sensitivity, specificity, diagnostic accuracy, positive predictive value, and negative predictive value of TIS using the cell block technique as the gold standard.

Materials and method

This cross-sectional analytical study was conducted on serous effusion samples received in the Department of Pathology over a defined study period. Conventional cytology smears were prepared and evaluated, and cases were categorized according to TIS. Cell block preparation was performed wherever feasible and served as the gold standard for comparison.

Results

Application of TIS improved diagnostic categorization of serous effusions. Compared with cell block findings, TIS showed high sensitivity, specificity, and diagnostic accuracy. The combined use of conventional cytology, TIS, and cell block increased the detection of malignant effusions.

Discussion

Standardized reporting through TIS improves diagnostic consistency and communication with clinicians. The cell block technique enhances diagnostic yield by preserving cellular architecture and enabling additional ancillary studies when required.

Conclusion

TIS is a reliable reporting system for serous effusion cytology. Its use alongside conventional cytology and the cell block technique improves diagnostic accuracy, standardization, and clinical decision-making.

OP-27

Prevalence of Beta thalassemia minor in pregnant women & its correlation with degree of anemia in a tertiary care centre

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Introduction

Beta thalassemia minor is a common genetic hemoglobinopathy that often remains undiagnosed in pregnant women with anemia. Differentiating it from iron deficiency anemia is essential to avoid inappropriate therapy and ensure optimal maternal and fetal outcomes.

Objectives

It is a hospital based cross sectional study to assess the prevalence of Beta thalassemia minor among pregnant women in a tertiary care hospital over a period of 1 year.

Methods

634 antenatal cases screened by CBC & RBC indices underwent HPLC testing for haemoglobin fraction analysis.

Results

Out of 634 antenatal cases, anemia was observed in 282 (44.4%) with a mean Hb of 10.2 ± 1.2 g/dl. Mild, moderate, and severe anemia were seen in 126 (19.8%), 139 (21.9%), and 17 (2.68%) cases respectively. Beta thalassemia trait was detected in 12 cases (prevalence 1.89%). Among these, 41.66% had mild, 50% moderate, and 8.33% severe anemia, with a mean Hb of 9.6 ± 1.1 g/dl, lower than non-thalassemic women (10.2 ± 1.4 g/dl). Beta thalassemia minor cases also showed reduced red cell indices (mean MCV 66.6 ± 5.6 fL; MCH 25.4 ± 2.3 pg). Coexistent iron deficiency anemia was present in 5 cases (41.66%). A significant association was noted between Beta thalassemia minor and increasing anemia severity. Other hemoglobinopathies included 3 cases of HbD Punjab trait, 1 HbE, and 1 HbE trait.

Conclusion

Beta thalassemia minor is an important cause of anemia in pregnancy. Early detection and genetic counselling are essential to prevent transmission to future generations.

COMPARISON OF IMMUNOFLUORESCENCE IN FORMALIN FIXED PARAFFIN EMBEDDED AND FRESH-FROZEN SECTIONS OF LUPUS NEPHRITIS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO REVISED ISN/RPS CLASSIFICATION

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Introduction

Renal biopsy is considered as an invaluable method in the evaluation of the patient with renal disease. Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) is a chronic inflammatory disease with variable clinical manifestations. One of the most prevalent and dangerous forms of SLE is lupus nephritis (LN) which affects 40–75% of patients. Clarity in the definitions and classification of glomerular lesions in lupus nephritis was advocated by revised ISN/RPS classification (2018).

Objectives

1. To study histomorphological patterns of renal biopsy in clinically diagnosed cases of SLE with reference to revised ISN/RPS classification
2. To compare the efficacy of IF-F and IF-P in LN.

Methodology

Present study was carried out in department of pathology PGIMS, Rohtak over a period of one year which included 30 cases of LN diagnosed on renal biopsies. The renal biopsies were subjected to routine light microscopic and conventional fluorescence microscopy (IF-F) and immunofluorescence microscopy on formalin fixed paraffin embedded sections after proteinase-K- digestion. Histopathological lesions were be classified according to Modified ISN/RPS Classification (2018).

Results

It was observed from our study that the intensity on FFPE was one score less than that seen on frozen tissue. Endocapillary hypercellularity was the most common active lesion and tubular atrophy was the most common chronic lesion identified in LN .

Discussion

Clarity in the definitions and classification of glomerular lesions in LN was advocated by the 2018 revision of the ISN/RPS classification. Mesangial hypercellularity, cellular, fibrocellular and fibrous crescents are defined in new ways. The term "endocapillary proliferation" is dropped.

Conclusion

Proteinase-K enzyme treatment can be used to show Ig and complement deposits in tissue that has been paraffin-embedded and fixed in formalin. It is quite helpful when there is insufficient tissue or no new tissue available for IF.

Correlation of Programmed Death Ligand 1 (PD-L1) and CD8+ Tumor Infiltrating Lymphocytes in Molecular Subtypes of Urothelial Carcinoma

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ESIC, FARIDABAD

Introduction

Urothelial carcinoma is the most aggressive bladder malignancy following histological and molecular heterogeneity. Molecular subtyping and evaluation of immune markers such as PD-L1 and CD8+ TILs have emerged as important tools for predicting prognosis and immunotherapy.

Aim

To assess PD-L1 expression, CD8+ TILs, and molecular subtypes in urothelial carcinoma and to determine their association with clinicopathological parameters.

Materials and Method

A 5 years ambispective study was conducted on 51 cases. Immunohistochemistry for GATA3, CK5/6, CD8, and PD-L1 was performed. PD-L1 positivity graded as >5% tumor cells showing membranous staining. CD8+ TILs as low (<25 cells) or high (>25 cells). Cases were subtyped based on GATA3 and CK5/6 expression.

Results

The mean age was 60.2 years, with a male predominance. Hematuria was found in 86% cases and smoking history in 60% cases. Muscle-invasive tumor was observed in 54.9%. High TILs were found in 66.6% cases and is associated with strong PD-L1 expression ($p = 0.04$). Molecular classification revealed luminal (47.1%) and basal (35.3%) as the predominant subtypes. PD-L1 positivity was noted in 51% of cases and showed a strong association with basal subtype ($p < 0.01$) and double-positive subtype ($p = 0.02$). A significant correlation was also seen between tumor stage and molecular subtype ($p < 0.01$).

DISCUSSION

Recent advances in cancer treatment have focused on targeted therapies with PD-L1 emerging as an important therapeutic target. The present study evaluated majority of muscle-invasive papillary urothelial carcinoma cases showed a higher percentage of PD-L1 positivity with a male predominance. Furthermore, our results demonstrated stronger PD-L1 expression in the basal subtype.

Conclusion

PD-L1 expression and CD8+ TIL infiltration vary significantly across molecular subtypes of urothelial carcinoma highlights the importance of integrating molecular subtyping and immune profiling. There are a lot of ongoing studies exploring the utility of neoadjuvant anti-PD-1/PD-L1 agents.

EVALUATING ENDOMETRIAL BIOMARKERS: PAX2 OUTPERFORMS B-CATENIN AND PTEN IN PREDICTING DEVELOPMENT OF HISTOLOGIC ABNORMALITIES

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Introduction

Endometrial carcinoma is one of most common gynecological malignancies worldwide, with rising incidence in both developed and developing countries. Abnormal endometrial histology includes disordered proliferative endometrium, endometrial hyperplasia, and carcinoma. Histomorphological overlap between these entities often makes diagnosis challenging. Therefore, reliable immunohistochemical biomarkers are essential to improve diagnostic accuracy and risk stratification. β -Catenin, PAX2, and PTEN emerged as promising molecular markers in evaluating abnormal endometrial lesions.

Objectives

To evaluate the role of β -Catenin, PAX2, and PTEN immunohistochemical expression in distinguishing normal from abnormal endometrial histology and to assess their diagnostic utility individually and in combination.

Material And Method

This study included all endometrial biopsies and hysterectomy specimens from women aged 15–49 years (WHO reproductive age group) received between April 2024 and July 2025. Immunohistochemistry for β -Catenin, PAX2, and PTEN was performed using a fully automated Ventana Benchmark GX IHC stainer.

Results

All three markers showed statistically significant differences between cases and controls. Among individual biomarkers, abnormal PAX2 expression emerged as the only statistically significant independent predictor (coefficient 3.35, standard error 1.07, $p = 0.002$). The combined use of PAX2 and PTEN demonstrated the highest sensitivity among dual-marker combinations, while the addition of β -Catenin did not significantly enhance diagnostic discrimination.

Discussion

The findings support the diagnostic value of these markers in identifying abnormal endometrial lesions. PAX2 loss appears to be the most sensitive indicator of abnormal endometrial histology.

Conclusion

PAX2, PTEN, and β -Catenin are useful adjuncts in differentiating normal from abnormal endometrium, with PAX2 loss emerging as most sensitive biomarker.

CLINICOPATHOLOGICAL SPECTRUM OF GRANULOMATOUS MASTITIS: A 3-YEAR RETROSPECTIVE STUDY FROM A TERTIARY CARE CENTRE

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Introduction

Granulomatous mastitis is an uncommon benign chronic inflammatory disease of the breast with varied clinical presentations. It typically affects young to middle-aged women and often mimics breast abscess or carcinoma clinically and radiologically, posing significant diagnostic challenges.

Objective

To evaluate the clinicoradiological and histopathological spectrum of granulomatous mastitis over a three-year period and assess the role of histopathology and Ziehl–Neelsen (ZN) staining in identifying infectious etiology.

Material and Methods

This retrospective observational study included 17 histopathologically diagnosed cases of granulomatous mastitis at a tertiary care centre over three years. Clinical presentation, laterality and radiological findings were retrieved from records. Fine-needle aspiration cytology findings were reviewed where available. Hematoxylin and eosin-stained sections from core/tru-cut biopsies and excision specimens were examined. Ziehl–Neelsen staining was performed in all cases to detect acid-fast bacilli and clinicopathological correlation was undertaken.

Results

The mean age was 35.8 years. Most patients presented with a painful unilateral breast lump with swelling or abscess formation. Right-sided involvement predominated (64.7%). Imaging commonly showed hypoechoic lesions with abscess-like collections. Cytology revealed granulomatous inflammation with epithelioid cells and multinucleated giant cells. Histology demonstrated lobulocentric epithelioid granulomas with lymphoplasmacytic infiltrate and neutrophilic microabscesses. Caseous necrosis was seen in one case. Two cases were AFB positive on ZN staining, consistent with tuberculous mastitis, while the remaining 15 were diagnosed as idiopathic granulomatous mastitis.

Discussion

Granulomatous mastitis overlaps clinically and radiologically with suppurative mastitis and inflammatory carcinoma. Histopathology is essential for diagnosis. In this study, two cases showed ZN positivity confirming tuberculous mastitis, although caseous necrosis was present in only one case, highlighting that necrosis may not always be evident.

Conclusion

Histomorphology with routine ZN staining is crucial for differentiating idiopathic granulomatous mastitis from tuberculous mastitis and guiding management.

BEYOND FIXED RATIOS: ROLLING ASCUS : SIL ANALYSIS FOR IMPROVED CYTOLOGY QUALITY CONTROL

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Background

The atypical squamous cells of undetermined significance to squamous intraepithelial lesion (ASCUS:SIL) ratio is an established quality assurance indicator in cervical cytology. Rolling (dynamic) ratio analysis may provide a more sensitive tool for ongoing laboratory quality monitoring.

Objectives

To evaluate long-term trends in ASCUS:SIL ratio using both fixed six-month and six-month rolling (dynamic) methods, and to assess the utility of rolling ratios as a quality assurance tool in cervical cytology reporting.

Materials and Methods

A retrospective analysis of 401 Pap smear reports over a 10-year period (December 2015–January 2026) was conducted. Cases were categorized as ASCUS, low-grade SIL (LSIL), or high-grade SIL (HSIL) according to the Bethesda System. Dynamic ASCUS:SIL ratios were computed using a six-month rolling window. Trend analysis was performed, and a Shewhart-type control chart was applied using a threshold ratio of 2.0 to identify potential outliers and periods of concern.

Results

Fixed ASCUS:SIL ratios demonstrated marked temporal fluctuations, ranging from 0.21 to 3.5. Six-month rolling ASCUS:SIL ratios showed smoother trends and highlighted sustained elevations more effectively. Periods exceeding the quality assurance threshold (ratio >2.0) were identified predominantly during the COVID-19 and immediate post-COVID phases, with the highest rolling ratio observed during February–July 2024 (2.55). Subsequent periods showed normalization of ratios, suggesting corrective stabilization in reporting practices.

Conclusion

Six-month rolling ASCUS:SIL ratio analysis provides a more stable and sensitive measure of cytology reporting trends compared to fixed-period ratios. Incorporation of rolling ratio monitoring and control chart analysis can enhance laboratory quality assurance by enabling early detection of sustained deviations and facilitating timely corrective interventions.

EVALUATION OF FROZEN SECTION DIAGNOSIS IN FEMALE GENITAL TRACT LESIONS WITH HISTOPATHOLOGICAL CORRELATION

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Introduction

Intraoperative frozen section (IFS) plays a crucial role in guiding surgical management of female genital tract lesions by providing rapid histopathological diagnosis during surgery.

Objective

To evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of IFS in female genital tract lesions and correlate the findings with final histopathology.

Methods

This retrospective study included 83 female genital tract specimens evaluated by IFS over a three-year period. Diagnostic accuracy and concordance were analysed for ovarian lesions (benign, borderline and malignant categories) and in uterine lesions.

Results

Out of total 83 cases, 73 (88%) were ovarian lesions and 10 (12%) were uterine lesions. Ovarian lesions included 44 benign, 5 borderline, and 24 malignant cases with concordance rate of 98.6%. Only a single case of malignant ovarian tumour was discordant. Among uterine lesions, all 4 (40%) benign and 6 (60%) malignant cases were correctly identified, showing 100% concordance. Overall diagnostic accuracy for FGT lesions was 98.8% (82/83), with sensitivity of 100% and specificity of 98.2%. The positive predictive value was 96.4% and the negative predictive value was 100%, indicating a very high reliability of frozen section.

Discussion

The high concordance in this study confirms the reliability of intraoperative frozen section (IFS) in evaluating female genital tract lesions. There was one discordant case of thecoma which was misinterpreted as granulosa cell tumour on frozen section, likely due to morphological overlap as both belong to sex cord–stromal tumours.

Conclusion

IFS is a highly reliable intraoperative diagnostic tool for female genital tract lesions, especially ovarian tumours, and significantly aids appropriate surgical decision-making.

HISTOCHEMICAL PROFILING OF MUCIN EXPRESSION DISTINGUISHES INFLAMMATORY, BENIGN AND MALIGNANT SALIVARY GLAND LESIONS

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Title : HISTOCHEMICAL PROFILING OF MUCIN EXPRESSION DISTINGUISHES INFLAMMATORY, BENIGN AND MALIGNANT SALIVARY GLAND LESIONS

Introduction

Salivary gland lesions, ranging from inflammatory to malignant, require precise histological differentiation for accurate diagnosis and treatment. Since mucin makes up the majority of saliva produced by salivary glands, it is essential to understand the type, pattern, and distribution of mucin in different salivary gland lesions. Mucin stains, like Mucicarmine, Alcian Blue, and, Periodic Acid Schiff (PAS) are hence essential to the procedure.

Objective

To ascertain the diagnostic value of mucin stains by analyzing their distribution, pattern, and intensity in salivary gland lesions.

Materials and Methods

This cross-sectional study evaluated 58 salivary gland lesion biopsies collected from September 2022 to August 2024 at BLDE (Deemed To Be University) Shri B. M. Patil Medical College Hospital & Research Centre, Vijayapura. The lesions included 15 inflammatory, 35 benign, and 8 malignant cases. Histochemical staining with PAS, Alcian Blue, and Mucicarmine was performed, and the results were statistically analysed using Chi-square tests.

Results

The predominant age group was 30-39 years (28%), with having a 1.07:1 male to female ratio. In most cases, the diagnosis was Pleomorphic Adenoma (57%), followed by Chronic Non-specific Inflammation (26%). When PAS stain was used, there were notable variations in the stromal and intracellular expressions among lesion types (Chi-square values were 19.054 and 16.539 and p-values were 0.001 and 0.002, respectively). Notable differences in alcian blue staining of the intracellular and stromal expressions (p-value for both was 0.001, Chi-square values were 36.163 and 27.085 respectively). Substantial variations in stromal and intracellular expressions with mucicarmine staining (p-value for both was 0.000 and Chi-square values = 38.74 and 26.670 respectively).

Conclusion

The distinction between inflammatory, benign, and malignant salivary gland lesions can be made with ease using the PAS, Alcian Blue, and Mucicarmine stains. Notably, staining patterns across lesion types varied significantly, indicating the importance of these histochemical approaches for precise diagnosis and therapy planning.

KEYWORDS

Salivary glands, Histochemical Stains, Periodic Acid Schiff, Alcian Blue, Mucicarmine.

EXPLORING THE IMMUNE LANDSCAPE OF COLORECTAL CARCINOMA: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF PD-L1 AND ITS CORRELATION WITH MICRO SATELLITE INSTABILITY, TUMOR INFILTRATING LYMPHOCYTES, BRAF MUTATION AND CLINICOPATHOLOGICAL DATA

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Introduction

Colorectal carcinoma is a biologically complex disease with multifactorial etiology, arising through diverse molecular pathways.

Objectives

This study sought to evaluate PD-L1 expression in colorectal carcinoma and to determine its correlation with clinicopathological parameters, TILs, MSI and BRAF mutation.

Materials and Methods

50 patients of CRC were evaluated for PD-L1, MSI and BRAF mutation by IHC, while TILs were examined on H&E sections. Evaluation of PD-L1 was done by using three parameters- TPS, IPS and CPS. PD-L1, MSI, BRAF and TILs were correlated with clinicopathological data as well as with one another.

Results

PD-L1 expression on tumor cells (TPS) was 40%, 62% in immune cells (IPS), while the combined positive score (CPS) was 74%. Significant association of TPS with TILs and MSI was noted. IPS showed a positive correlation with PNI. Correlation of CPS with PNI was also seen. MSI was seen in 24% cases and was associated with a higher tumor grade and N stage.

Discussion

These findings underscore the dynamic interaction between tumor genetics and immune modulation in colorectal carcinoma with possible therapeutic implications. Integrating PD-L1 evaluation into routine diagnostic algorithms may enhance patient selection for targeted immunotherapy. This study showed concurrent findings as studies done by Shrivastava et al, Lang- Schwarz et al and Rosenbaum et al.

Conclusion

With the increased availability of anti-PDL1 agents, it is the need of the hour to evaluate PD-L1 expression in CRC to identify patient groups that will benefit from immune checkpoint inhibitors instead of conventional chemotherapy.

**IMMUNOHISTOCHEMICAL EXPRESSION OF MISMATCH REPAIR PROTEINS IN
ENDOMETRIAL CARCINOMA: BRIDGING MORPHOLOGY AND MOLECULAR PATHOLOGY**

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Conference Registration Number: NWIAMP315

Introduction

Mismatch repair (MMR) is a critical step in repairing errors during DNA replication in the cell cycle. Failure of MMR results in microsatellite instability and can contribute to carcinoma development. The altered expression of MMR proteins plays a pivotal role in the tumorigenesis of various cancers; however, their significance in gynecological neoplasms, particularly in endometrial carcinogenesis, remains controversial.

Objectives

To determine the immunohistochemical expression of MMR proteins (MLH1, MSH2, MSH6, and PMS2) in endometrial carcinoma and to correlate these expressions with other clinicopathological parameters.

Material and Methods

Immunohistochemistry (IHC) was performed for MMR proteins (MLH1, MSH2, MSH6, and PMS2) expression on formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded tissue from 30 histologically proven endometrial carcinoma cases. Positivity of all four proteins indicated MMR proficiency (MMRp), whereas loss of any one protein indicated MMR deficiency (MMRd).

Results

Of 30 cases, 57% were MMRp and 43% were MMRd. Among MMRd cases, 14% showed loss of one protein, 20% loss of two proteins, and 9% loss of three proteins. PMS2 was the most frequently lost protein. Endometrioid adenocarcinoma was the predominant histotype in MMRd cases.

Discussion

MMRd was identified in 43% of cases, with PMS2 being the most frequently lost protein. Endometrioid adenocarcinoma predominated among MMRd cases, underscoring the value of routine IHC-based MMR testing for Lynch syndrome screening and immunotherapy guidance.

Conclusion

Aberrations involving MMR genes can provide early insights into the molecular imprint of endometrial carcinoma and may improve diagnostic accuracy, therapeutic stratification, and prognostication in such patients in the near future.

“FROM PROTECTORS TO PROMOTERS: THE SIGNIFICANCE OF CD68 AND CD163 EXPRESSION OF TUMOR-ASSOCIATED MACROPHAGES IN ORAL SQUAMOUS CELL CARCINOMA.”

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VMMC and SJH

Introduction

Oral Squamous Cell Carcinoma (OSCC) remains one of the major oral malignancies with frequent late-stage diagnosis, particularly in India. Tumor-Associated Macrophages (TAMs), especially the immunosuppressive M2 subtype, drive angiogenesis, immune evasion, and tumour progression. Assessing CD68 (pan-macrophage) and CD163 (M2-specific) expression in TAMs present across different histological grades of OSCC may provide critical prognostic insights.

Objectives

To evaluate CD68 and CD163 expression in TAMs and correlate their density with histological grading in OSCC.

Materials and Methods

This cross-sectional study included 30 histopathologically confirmed OSCC cases. Immunohistochemical staining for CD68 and CD163 was performed on formalin-fixed, paraffin-embedded sections. TAM density was quantified as mean count per 10 HPF and statistically correlated with histological grade and clinicopathological parameters ($p < 0.05$, considered significant).

Results

The cohort was predominantly male with a mean age of 47.57 years. CD68⁺ and CD163⁺ TAMs were identified across all cases and grades. Both markers correlated significantly with higher histological grade, larger tumor size, and lymph node metastasis ($p < 0.001$). CD163⁺ TAM density showed a progressive increase from well-differentiated to poorly differentiated OSCC, demonstrating stronger grade-specific correlation than CD68⁺.

Discussion

TAMs predominantly adopt the M2 phenotype in OSCC. CD163⁺ M2 macrophage dominance in higher-grade tumours reflects a pro-tumorigenic immune shift. CD68, marking both M1 and M2 populations, lacks polarization specificity, limiting its independent prognostic value.

Conclusion

CD163 outperforms CD68 as a prognostic marker in OSCC, correlating significantly with histological grade and tumour aggressiveness. Further large-scale studies are warranted to validate its clinical utility and explore macrophage-targeted therapies.

SOX10 AND GATA3: NAVIGATING TRIPLE NEGATIVE BREAST CANCER COMPLEXITY.

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VMMC AND SAFDARJUNG HOSPITAL, NEW DELHI

Introduction: Breast cancer is the most common malignancy among women worldwide. Triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC), lacking estrogen receptor (ER), progesterone receptor (PR), and HER-2/neu expression, is an aggressive subtype associated with higher histological grade and poor prognosis, with limited treatment options. SOX10, a basal differentiation marker, and GATA3, a luminal differentiation marker, are emerging biomarkers and have shown variable expression in TNBC. Therefore, determining their combined role in TNBC might help improve understanding of tumor biology and prognostic assessment of such patients.

Objectives

To evaluate the immunohistochemical expression and association of SOX 10 and GATA3 in TNBC.

Material and Methods

Immunohistochemistry (IHC) was performed for SOX10 and GATA3 expression on formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded tissue from 30 histologically proven TNBC cases.

Results

Out of 30 cases, 50% were SOX10 positive, 40% were GATA3 positive, and 10% shows both negative.

Discussion

SOX10 was strongly associated with TNBC and correlated with large tumor size, higher grade, and basal-like features, whereas GATA3 was highly expressed in luminal A, luminal B, and HER-2/neu overexpressed breast cancers. The expression of SOX10 and GATA3 was negatively correlated in TNBC.

Conclusion

The combined use of SOX10 and GATA3 may serve as valuable diagnostic markers by indicating more aggressive tumor behaviour in breast carcinoma cases lacking ER, PR, and HER-2/neu expression. However, further studies are needed to explore the diagnostic significance of these markers and their potential role in guiding targeted therapeutic strategies.

OP-39

TO STUDY CYCLIN D1 IN ENDOMETRIAL LESIONS

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KDMCHRC

Introduction

Endometrial lesions range from benign proliferative changes to premalignant and malignant conditions. Endometrial hyperplasia is considered an important precursor to carcinoma, and histomorphological overlap between these lesions often causes diagnostic difficulty. Cyclin D1, a key regulator of the cell cycle, has been implicated in endometrial carcinogenesis and may help in distinguishing premalignant and malignant lesions.

Materials and methods

A cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of Pathology at K.D. Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Mathura, over 18 months. Sixty-four endometrial biopsy and hysterectomy specimens were included. Lesions were classified into hyperplasia without atypia, atypical hyperplasia, and endometrial carcinoma. Immunohistochemistry for Cyclin D1 was performed and expression was evaluated using staining intensity, extent, and H-score.

Results

The mean patient age was 52.1 ± 9.8 years, with most cases occurring in peri- and postmenopausal women presenting with vaginal bleeding. Cyclin D1 positivity was observed in 50% of cases, with expression increasing from hyperplasia without atypia to atypical hyperplasia and carcinoma. Sensitivity, specificity, and diagnostic accuracy were 63.6%, 66.7%, and 65.6%, respectively.

Discussion

The findings indicate increasing Cyclin D1 expression with disease progression. Similar observations were reported by Laisom et al. (2021), supporting its role in endometrial carcinogenesis.

Conclusion

Cyclin D1 expression correlates with the severity of endometrial lesions and may serve as a useful adjunct to routine histopathology for identifying high-risk lesions.

Immune Microenvironment Remodelling After Denosumab Therapy In Giant Cell Tumor of Bone: A Comparative Immunohistochemical Analysis.

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VMMC AND SAFDARJUNG HOSPITAL, NEW DELHI

Introduction

Giant Cell Tumor of Bone (GCTB) is a locally aggressive neoplasm composed of osteoclast-like giant cells and neoplastic stromal cells. Denosumab, a monoclonal antibody targeting RANKL, is widely used in the management of unresectable or advanced GCTB. However, its effect on immune checkpoint pathways, particularly programmed death-ligand 1 (PD-L1) expression, remains unclear.

Objectives

To compare PD-L1 expression in paired pre- and post-denosumab biopsy specimens from the same patients and evaluate potential treatment-related changes in the tumor immune microenvironment.

Material and methods

Thirty patients with histologically confirmed GCTB who underwent core biopsy prior to denosumab therapy and repeat biopsy at interval assessment were included. PD-L1 immunohistochemistry was performed. Membranous staining in mononuclear stromal tumor cells and immune cells was assessed, and a combined tumor proportion score >1% was considered positive.

Results

PD-L1 expression was absent in all pre-treatment samples. Following denosumab therapy, PD-L1 positivity was identified in two cases that were initially negative, demonstrating newly acquired membranous expression in post-treatment biopsies. Overall, PD-L1 positivity was observed in 6.7% of post-denosumab samples.

Discussion

The emergence of PD-L1 expression in a subset of post-denosumab biopsies suggests possible therapy-related modulation of the tumor immune microenvironment. Limitations include use of a different PD-L1 antibody clone compared with reference studies, lack of comparable Indian data, and limited sample size.

Conclusion

A small proportion of GCTB cases demonstrated newly acquired PD-L1 expression following denosumab therapy, indicating potential immune microenvironment remodeling. These findings may have implications for exploring combination strategies with immune checkpoint inhibitors in selected patients.

POSTER PRESENTATIONS ABSTRACTS

PP-1

Orbital Chordoma Presenting as Unilateral Proptosis – A Rare Extraskkeletal Presentation

Dr. Ankita Garg, Dr. Veena Gupta, Dr. Sunita Singh
PGIMS, ROHTAK

Introduction

- Chordoma is a rare malignant tumor arising from embryonic notochordal remnants, typically involving the axial skeleton.
- Primary extraskkeletal orbital chordoma is exceptionally rare and may clinically mimic other orbital neoplasms.

Objectives

- To report a rare case of primary orbital chordoma.
- To highlight the role of histopathology and immunohistochemistry in diagnosis.

Case report

A 59-year-old male presented with progressive right-sided proptosis and visual impairment for six months.

- Examination revealed marked non-pulsatile proptosis with restricted ocular movements and reduced vision (perception of light).
- CECT orbit showed a well-defined heterogeneously enhancing superomedial orbital mass (4.4 × 2.4 cm) without bony destruction or intracranial extension.
- The patient underwent right orbital exenteration due to extensive involvement.
- Microscopy demonstrated lobules and cords of large polygonal cells with abundant vacuolated (physaliphorous) cytoplasm in a myxoid stroma.
- Immunohistochemistry showed tumor cell positivity for S-100, epithelial membrane antigen (EMA), and cytokeratin (CK), confirming orbital chordoma.

Discussion

- Orbital chordoma is extremely rare and radiologically indistinguishable from other orbital tumors such as meningioma or lymphoma.
- Definitive diagnosis depends on identifying physaliphorous cells and characteristic immunoprofile.

Conclusion

- Chordoma should be considered in the differential diagnosis of unilateral proptosis.
- Early histopathological evaluation is crucial for accurate diagnosis and appropriate management.

PP-2

Intrathyroid Parathyroid Carcinoma: A Diagnostic Challenge

Dr.Anjali Ahalawat, Dr.Veena Gupta, Dr.Sunita Singh
PGIMS ROHTAK

Introduction

Parathyroid carcinoma is a rare endocrine malignancy, accounting for <1% of cases of primary hyperparathyroidism. Ectopic localization of parathyroid tissue may occur due to aberrant embryological migration, and intrathyroidal parathyroid carcinoma represents an extremely uncommon presentation. Because of its location within the thyroid gland and overlapping cytological features, it can mimic thyroid neoplasms, leading to diagnostic difficulty both clinically and cytologically.

Objective

To highlight the diagnostic challenges associated with intrathyroid parathyroid carcinoma and emphasize the role of histopathology and immunohistochemistry in establishing the correct diagnosis.

Case Report

A middle-aged patient presented with clinical and biochemical features suggestive of primary hyperparathyroidism, including markedly elevated serum calcium and parathyroid hormone levels. Radiological evaluation revealed a thyroid nodule suspicious for a thyroid neoplasm. Fine needle aspiration cytology suggested a follicular-patterned lesion and was inconclusive for definitive diagnosis. The patient subsequently underwent surgical excision. Histopathological examination revealed a tumor composed of polygonal cells arranged in trabecular and nested patterns separated by dense fibrous bands, with evidence of capsular invasion. Immunohistochemical analysis demonstrated positivity for parathyroid hormone (PTH) and GATA3, while thyroid markers such as TTF-1 and thyroglobulin were negative, confirming the diagnosis of intrathyroid parathyroid carcinoma.

Discussion

Intrathyroid parathyroid carcinoma is a rare diagnostic pitfall that may closely resemble thyroid follicular neoplasms on imaging and cytology. Definitive diagnosis relies on careful histomorphological evaluation supported by immunohistochemistry.

Conclusion

Awareness of this rare entity and clinicopathological correlation are essential for accurate diagnosis and appropriate surgical management of patients presenting with thyroid nodules associated with hyperparathyroidism.

PP-3

Lung carcinoid tumour: A case report

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PGIMS, ROHTAK

Introduction

Pulmonary carcinoid tumours are rare neuroendocrine neoplasms accounting for approximately 1–2% of all lung malignancies. They are typically slow-growing and may present with non-specific respiratory symptoms, often leading to delayed diagnosis.

Objectives

To report a rare case of pulmonary carcinoid tumour and highlight the role of histopathology and immunohistochemistry in establishing the diagnosis.

Case Report

A 28-year-old non-smoker male presented with cough, chest pain, back pain and haemoptysis. Radiological imaging revealed a heterogeneous mass in the left infra-hilar region involving the lower lobe bronchus. Bronchoscopy showed complete occlusion of the left lower lobe bronchus. The patient underwent left lower lobectomy. Gross examination revealed a grey-white firm mass measuring $3.5 \times 3 \times 2.3$ cm. Microscopy showed tumour cells arranged in nests and trabeculae composed of uniform cells with round nuclei, salt-and-pepper chromatin and moderate eosinophilic cytoplasm. Immunohistochemistry demonstrated positivity for CK, CD56, chromogranin and synaptophysin, while TTF-1, napsin A and CDX2 were negative.

Discussion and Conclusion

Pulmonary carcinoid tumours are uncommon and may clinically mimic other pulmonary conditions. Histopathological examination along with immunohistochemistry is essential for accurate diagnosis. Surgical resection remains the treatment of choice and offers favourable prognosis in typical carcinoid tumours.

PP-4

Collision Tumor of Ovary: Benign Cystic Teratoma and Mucinous Cystadenoma in the Same Ovary – A Case Report

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PGIMS, ROHTAK

Introduction:

Collision tumors are rare lesions in which two histologically distinct neoplasms coexist within the same organ without intermixing. Ovarian collision tumors are uncommon, accounting for less than 1% of cases. The most frequent combination reported is a benign cystic teratoma with mucinous cystadenoma.

Objectives:

To report a rare case of an ovarian collision tumor and highlight the importance of clinicopathological correlation and meticulous histopathological evaluation.

Case Report:

A 22-year-old female presented with abdominal pain for one year and urinary retention for 1.5 years. Radiological imaging revealed a large cystic mass in the right ovary. Tumor markers were within normal limits. The patient underwent exploratory laparotomy with right ovarian cystectomy. Gross examination showed a multiloculated cyst containing straw-colored fluid along with focal areas of hair and pultaceous material.

Discussion:

Microscopic examination revealed two distinct components: mucinous cystadenoma lined by tall columnar epithelium and benign cystic teratoma composed of skin appendages, hair follicles, and sebaceous glands. The components were sharply demarcated without histological intermixing, confirming a collision tumor. Proposed mechanisms include coincidental occurrence, altered microenvironment, and differentiation from a common progenitor cell.

Conclusion:

Ovarian collision tumors are rare entities requiring thorough grossing and extensive sampling. Accurate diagnosis is essential to avoid misinterpretation and ensure appropriate management.

PP-5

Papillary thyroid carcinoma presenting as widespread lytic bone metastasis: A diagnostic challenge

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PGIMS, ROHTAK

Papillary thyroid carcinoma (PTC) is the most common differentiated thyroid malignancy and is generally associated with an excellent prognosis and frequent regional lymph node involvement. Distant metastasis, particularly to bone, is uncommon and rarely represents the initial clinical manifestation.

Objective

To describe the clinicopathological, and immunohistochemical features of a case of Papillary thyroid carcinoma presenting primarily with extensive lytic bone metastasis.

Case Report

A 56-year-old woman presented with pain and swelling over the left shoulder. X-ray revealed destructive lytic lesions involving the acromion process of the left scapula. PET-CT demonstrated additional metastatic deposits in the lungs, mediastinal, and supraclavicular lymph nodes. Biopsy from the scapular lesion showed complex arborizing papillae with fibrovascular cores revealing overlapping of nuclei, nuclear grooving and nuclear chromatin clearing suggestive of malignant papillary neoplasm. Immunohistochemistry demonstrated strong nuclear positivity for TTF-1 and cytoplasmic positivity for CK7, while CD10 and CD20 were negative, supporting metastatic papillary thyroid carcinoma and excluding primary bone and lymphoid malignancies.

Discussion and Conclusion

Although PTC commonly spreads to lymph nodes, hematogenous dissemination to bone may occur rarely and can mimic primary skeletal tumors. Histopathological evaluation supplemented by immunohistochemistry is essential for accurate identification of the primary site. Early recognition of metastatic PTC ensures appropriate therapeutic management and prognostic assessment.

PP-6

Cervical Endometriosis Masquerading as a Cervical Lesion: An unusual cause of postcoital bleeding.

Dr. Yachna, Dr. Sonia Chhabra, Dr. Sunita Singh
PGIMS, ROHTAK

Introduction

Endometriosis is characterized by presence of functional endometrial glands and stroma outside uterine cavity. While pelvic sites such as ovaries are commonly involved, cervical localization is extremely rare. Cervical endometriosis may clinically mimic benign or malignant cervical lesions, posing a diagnostic challenge.

Objective

1. To highlight a rare case of cervical endometriosis
2. To emphasize the importance of histopathological examination of cervical biopsy in establishing the diagnosis and differentiating it from other cervical lesions, including malignancy.

Case Report

Reproductive aged women presented with chief complaint of postcoital bleeding. Per speculum examination revealed small erythematous lesion on cervix, clinically suspected to be cervical polyp or neoplastic lesion. Cervical biopsy was performed and submitted for histopathological evaluation.

Histopathological findings revealed ectocervical squamous epithelium with underlying endometrial type glands and stroma. No evidence of epithelial dysplasia or malignancy was identified, confirming the diagnosis of cervical endometriosis. On immunohistochemistry:

Glands : ER positive

Stroma: CD 10 positive

Discussion

Cervical endometriosis is an uncommon entity and may present with abnormal vaginal bleeding, particularly postcoital bleeding. Clinically it may simulate cervical neoplasia, making histopathological examination crucial for accurate diagnosis.

Conclusion

This case highlights the importance of considering cervical endometriosis in the differential diagnosis of cervical lesions presenting with postcoital bleeding. Awareness of this rare entity helps prevent misdiagnosis and unnecessary aggressive management.

PP-7

Extramedullary Plasmacytoma of Forehead: A Case Report

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Introduction

Extramedullary plasmacytoma (EMP) is a localized monoclonal plasma cell neoplasm occurring outside the bone marrow and represents <5% of plasma cell dyscrasias. Cranial involvement, particularly of the frontal bone, is extremely rare and poses a diagnostic challenge on cytology due to overlap with other plasma cell-rich and small round cell lesions.

Objective

To highlight the cytomorphological features, utility of cell block and immunohistochemistry in establishing monoclonality, and the role of FNAC in diagnosing EMP at an uncommon cranial site.

Case Details

A 65-year-old female presented with a forehead swelling. Imaging revealed a destructive mass arising from the frontal sinus. FNAC showed highly cellular smears composed of mature and immature plasma cells with eccentric nuclei, coarse chromatin, abundant basophilic cytoplasm, binucleation, and occasional plasmablasts in a hemorrhagic background. Cell block demonstrated sheets of plasma cells. Immunohistochemistry showed strong CD138 positivity with kappa light chain restriction and lambda negativity, confirming a monoclonal plasma cell proliferation. Bone marrow examination, skeletal survey, serum protein electrophoresis, and urine for Bence Jones protein were normal, excluding multiple myeloma.

Discussion

Cytological differentials include plasma cell granuloma, lymphoma with plasmacytic differentiation, and metastatic tumors. Demonstration of light chain restriction is essential to distinguish monoclonal lesion from reactive plasma cell proliferations. FNAC with cell block provides adequate material for immunophenotyping and is particularly valuable in anatomically sensitive cranial lesions.

Conclusion

FNAC combined with cell block and immunohistochemistry is a reliable, minimally invasive approach for diagnosing EMP at rare sites. Demonstration of monoclonality and exclusion of systemic disease are critical for accurate diagnosis and management.

PP-8

Intracranial solitary fibrous tumour / hemangiopericytoma: A rare meningeal neoplasm

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PGIMS, ROHTAK

Introduction

Solitary fibrous tumour/hemangiopericytoma (SFT/HPC) is a rare mesenchymal tumor of the meninges, accounting for less than 1% of intracranial neoplasms. Although it resembles meningioma radiologically, it demonstrates more aggressive behavior with higher recurrence and metastasis rates.

Objective

To report a rare case of intracranial SFT/HPC highlighting its histopathological and immunohistochemical features for accurate diagnosis.

Case Report

A 65-year-old female presented with left-sided weakness for one year and confusion for one month. Non-contrast CT scan showed an extra-axial lesion in the right frontal region abutting the falx, suggestive of meningioma. The patient underwent right frontoparietal craniotomy with gross total tumor excision. Histopathology revealed a spindle-cell neoplasm composed of oval to spindle-shaped cells with mild to moderate pleomorphism and characteristic branching “staghorn” vessels. Immunohistochemistry showed positivity for vimentin, CD34, BCL-2, and CD99 with focal EMA positivity, while Cd56, SMA and S100 were negative. Ki-67 proliferation index was approximately 5–10%. These findings were consistent with hemangiopericytoma (WHO Grade II).

Discussion and Conclusion

Intracranial SFT/HPC can mimic meningioma clinically and radiologically. Histopathological features and supportive immunohistochemistry are essential for accurate diagnosis. Long-term follow-up is important due to the risk of recurrence and metastasis.

PP-9

Submucosal lipomatosis with coexisting xanthogranulomatous appendicitis

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Introduction

Submucosal lipomatosis of appendix is an extremely rare condition characterised by an encapsulated infiltration of mature adipose tissue within the wall of appendix. It may be isolated or associated with lipomatosis of ileocaecal region. Clinically it may be asymptomatic or represent as acute appendicitis. Rare cases may be associated with chronic inflammation, fibrosis or hypertrophy of muscular layer.

Objectives

To report a rare case of appendiceal submucosal lipomatosis and to highlight its clinicopathological significance.

Case Report

A 33-year-old female presented with intermittent dull aching pain in the right iliac fossa for one month. Clinical examination revealed localized tenderness without guarding or rigidity.. Ultrasonography revealed a mildly thickened appendix. A clinical diagnosis of appendicitis was made, and the patient underwent elective appendicectomy. Microscopically submucosa was expanded revealing infiltration by mature adipocytes with foci of mononuclear infiltration, foamy macrophages and giant cells in periappendiceal tissue.

Discussion

The coexistence of submucosal lipomatosis and XGA is extremely rare and may reflect a pathogenic interaction rather than a coincidental finding. Diffuse adipose proliferation within the submucosa can narrow the appendiceal lumen and impair drainage, creating conditions that favor persistent inflammation and xanthogranulomatous change. Importantly, the associated wall thickening and yellow discoloration may simulate appendiceal neoplasms or granulomatous disease, posing a potential diagnostic challenge.

Conclusion

This case expands the spectrum of chronic appendiceal pathology and highlights a rare clinicopathological association that may mimic malignancy. Awareness of this entity is essential to establish the correct diagnosis, avoid overinterpretation, and guide appropriate clinical management.

PP-10

Case report: A Rare location of Aneurysmal bone cyst, proximal phalanx of great toe.

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Aneurysmal bone cyst (ABC) is an uncommon benign but locally aggressive bone lesion characterized by expansile osteolytic cavities filled with blood. It most frequently affects the metaphysis of long bones and the vertebral column, while involvement of the bones of the foot is rare.

Objectives

To report a rare presentation of aneurysmal bone cyst involving the proximal phalanx of the great toe and highlight its clinical features, diagnostic approach, and management.

Material and Methods

This study describes a case of a 20-year-old male who presented with pain and swelling of the great toe. Clinical examination was followed by radiological investigations to assess the lesion. Surgical intervention was performed, and the excised tissue was subjected to histopathological examination to confirm the diagnosis.

Results

Radiographic findings revealed an expansile osteolytic lesion involving the proximal phalanx of the great toe. Surgical curettage and appropriate management were carried out. Histopathological evaluation confirmed the diagnosis of aneurysmal bone cyst. Post-treatment follow-up showed satisfactory recovery without immediate complications.

Discussion

Although ABC is considered a benign lesion, it can demonstrate aggressive local behavior and may lead to bone destruction if not diagnosed early. Occurrence in the phalanges of the foot is uncommon, which may delay recognition. Imaging studies combined with histopathological analysis play a crucial role in establishing the diagnosis and guiding treatment.

Conclusion

Aneurysmal bone cyst involving the proximal phalanx of the great toe is rare. Early diagnosis and appropriate surgical management are essential to prevent complications and ensure favourable outcomes.

PP-11

Chorangioma of placenta : A rare placental cause for adverse fetal outcome

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Introduction

Chorangioma is a benign angioma of placenta arising from chorionic tissue. Most Chorangiomas have no clinical relevance but Large chorangiomas (>4cm) may be associated with perinatal morbidity and even mortality due to hemodynamic stresses on the fetus.

Objectives

To report a rare case of Placental Chorangioma associated with adverse fetal outcome.

Case report

A 31 year old primigravida presented at 36 weeks of gestation with decreased fetal movements. Ultrasonography revealed a well circumscribed hypoechoic mass arising from the fetal surface of the placenta. The fetus showed features of intrauterine growth restriction. No maternal complications were noted. Following delivery, the placenta showed a nodular, reddish brown mass measuring 8x7x3 cm near the umbilical cord insertion. Histopathological examination revealed mass comprising of numerous proliferating capillary sized vascular channels with area of fibrosis, hyalinization and calcification confirming the diagnosis of chorangioma.

Discussion

Chorangiomas are usually asymptomatic. Incidental findings of large grossly visible masses can be seen and diagnosis can be made antenatally by imaging. Large tumour maybe associated with perinatal morbidity and even mortality due to hemodynamic stress and need to be monitored carefully with symptomatic interventions.

Conclusion

Although rare, Placental chorangioma should be considered in cases with placental mass on antenatal imaging. Large lesions can lead to adverse fetal outcomes, emphasizing the importance of antenatal surveillance.

PP-12

CD19-Negative Precursor B-Lineage Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia in a Three-Year-Old Child: A Rare Diagnostic Challenge

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Introduction

B-lineage acute lymphoblastic leukemia (B-ALL) is the most common hematological malignancy in children and is characterized by uncontrolled proliferation of precursor B-lymphocytes in the bone marrow and peripheral blood. Flow cytometric immunophenotyping is essential for determining leukemic lineage, with CD19 serving as a key pan B-cell marker for B-lineage assignment. However, rare cases lacking CD19 expression have been reported and may create diagnostic uncertainty when limited immunophenotypic panels are used.

Objectives

To report a rare case of CD19-negative precursor B-ALL in a pediatric patient and emphasize the importance of comprehensive immunophenotypic evaluation for accurate diagnosis.

Case Report

A 3-year-old female presented with generalized weakness, intermittent fever, joint pain, and hepatosplenomegaly for four months. Laboratory investigations revealed severe anemia (hemoglobin 6.4 g/dL), leukocytosis ($62.3 \times 10^9/L$), thrombocytopenia ($30 \times 10^9/L$), and 90% circulating blasts. Bone marrow aspiration showed near-total replacement by blast cells. Flow cytometric immunophenotyping demonstrated blasts positive for CD10, HLA-DR, TdT, CD34, dim CD45, dim CD22, and CD79a, while negative for CD19, cytoplasmic CD3, cytoplasmic myeloperoxidase, CD5, CD7, CD13, and CD33.

Discussion and Conclusion

Despite absence of CD19, expression of other B-lineage markers confirmed precursor B-ALL. This rare immunophenotypic variant highlights the importance of extended multiparametric immunophenotyping to avoid diagnostic pitfalls and ensure accurate classification and appropriate management of pediatric acute leukemias.

PP-13

Beyond the M spike: Understanding non-secretory multiple myeloma

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Introduction

Non-secretory multiple myeloma (NSMM) is a rare subtype of multiple myeloma, accounting for 2-4% of cases. It involves clonal plasma cell proliferation in bone marrow without detectable monoclonal protein, making diagnosis challenging.

Objectives

To highlight the clinical presentation and diagnostic approach of NSMM

Case report

A 62 years old female presented with persistent bone pain for two months and femur fracture.

- Examination: revealed pallor and bony tenderness.
- Laboratory investigations: showed Hb:10g/dl, TLC:4000cells/cumm, platelets:1.5 lacs/cumm, elevated urea(59.00mg/dl), uric Acid(9mg/dl) and calcium(10.7mg/dl).
- X-Ray: revealed humeral fracture.
- PET-Scan: revealed multiple osteolytic lesions.
- Serum protein electrophoresis: negative for M Spike.
- Bone marrow aspiration: showed 50% plasma cells.
- Bone marrow biopsy: confirmed 45-50% infiltration.
- Immunohistochemistry: was positive for CD38(50%) and CD 138(45-50%).

Discussion

NSMM often presents with bone pain, osteolytic lesions, anemia and hypercalcemia. Absence of detectable monoclonal protein requires reliance on imaging and bone marrow evaluation for diagnosis.

Conclusion

Diagnosis of NSMM requires high clinical suspicion. Integration of clinical features, imaging and bone marrow studies is essential for accurate diagnosis and timely management.

PP-14

Interphase fluorescence in situ hybridization (FISH) for BCR::ABL1: the molecular wizard determining chronic myeloid leukemia: a pilot study

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Introduction

The BCR::ABL1 fusion gene is a hallmark genetic abnormality in Chronic Myeloid Leukemia (CML) and is also detected in a subset of Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia (ALL). It arises due to a reciprocal translocation t(9;22)(q34;q11), resulting in the formation of the Philadelphia chromosome. Detection of the BCR::ABL1 fusion gene is essential for diagnosis, prognostication, and monitoring of response to targeted therapy with tyrosine kinase inhibitors. Fluorescence In Situ Hybridization (FISH) is a sensitive molecular cytogenetic technique widely used to detect gene rearrangements. In certain cases, a double BCR::ABL1 fusion signal pattern may be observed, which can indicate classical or variant chromosomal rearrangements.

Aim

To describe the FISH methodology for detecting dual BCR::ABL1 fusion signals and to highlight its diagnostic significance in CML.

Materials and Methods

Peripheral blood or bone marrow samples from patients suspected of leukemia were processed for interphase FISH analysis. Dual-color dual-fusion probes targeting the BCR gene on chromosome 22 and the ABL1 gene on chromosome 9 were used. Slides were prepared using standard cytogenetic protocols, including fixation, denaturation, hybridization with labeled probes, and post-hybridization washing. Hybridization signals were visualized using a fluorescence microscope equipped with appropriate filter sets. Signal patterns were analyzed in at least 200 interphase nuclei per sample. The presence of dual fusion signal patterns (typically 2F1R1G or variant patterns) was interpreted according to established FISH scoring criteria.

Results

In this preliminary study, seven samples were analysed using fluorescent DNA probes targeting BCR::ABL1. A double BCR::ABL1 fusion signal pattern was identified in four cases, indicating the presence of the classical Philadelphia chromosome involving chromosomes 9 and 22. Two samples were negative, while one sample was inconclusive due to inadequate signal quality.

Conclusion

FISH is a reliable and sensitive technique for detecting BCR::ABL1 gene rearrangements. Identification of dual fusion signals provides important cytogenetic information and confirms the presence of the Philadelphia chromosome in leukemias. FISH remains an important adjunct to conventional cytogenetics and molecular techniques for the accurate diagnosis and management of leukemia patients.

PP-15

Disarming Bacterial Defenses: Novel Protein Targets and Hijacking Strategies for Next-Generation Anti-Resistance Bactericides

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Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) poses a global health emergency, necessitating innovative bactericides beyond the classes that inhibit either the cell-wall or ribosome. This review highlights new protein targets and mechanistic strategies that disable bacterial survival systems, re-sensitize microbes to antibiotics of choice, and slow resistance evolution. Key targets include the Rtc RNA repair system, which drives heteroresistance to ribosome-targeting antibiotics by preserving translation under stress; its inhibition sensitizes populations to macrolides and aminoglycosides. In Gram-negatives like *Acinetobacter baumannii*, lipid A-modifying enzyme PmrC enables colistin resistance via membrane charge alteration—targeted inhibitors restore polymyxin activity. Ribosomal protection proteins (ARE-ABCFs, e.g., CplR) actively eject antibiotics from the ribosome; blocking them revives macrolides and lincosamides. Toxin-antitoxin (TA) systems control persister dormancy—disrupting toxin-antitoxin PPIs triggers intracellular suicide. Autolysin regulators are exploited by glycopeptides such as corbomycin, which block cell-wall remodeling without direct enzyme inhibition, yielding near-zero resistance. Innovative strategies amplify impact: bacterial targeted protein degradation (BacPROTACs) hijacks the Clp protease to catalytically destroy resistance enzymes and efflux pumps. Encrypted antimicrobial peptides from human proteins deliver membrane disruption and immunomodulation with minimal resistance risk. Antibiotic potentiators (efflux-pump inhibitors, outer-membrane permeabilizers) revive legacy drugs, while pathogen-specific PPI modulators target mutation-resistant interfaces in membrane regulation and replication complexes. This multi-pronged framework may prevent resistance emergence and accelerate clinical translation.

PP-16

Ghost cell lesions of the jaw: an institutional experience

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Introduction

Ghost cell lesions of the jaws represent a heterogeneous group of odontogenic lesions characterized histopathologically by eosinophilic epithelial cells that have lost their nuclei but retain their cellular outlines, known as ghost cells. These cells are considered a hallmark feature in certain odontogenic lesions and may undergo calcification. Lesions reported to exhibit ghost cells include Calcifying Odontogenic Cyst, Dentinogenic Ghost Cell Tumor, Ghost Cell Odontogenic Carcinoma and odontomas. Although relatively uncommon, these lesions are diagnostically significant because of their varied clinical presentation and biological behavior.

Objective

To present a series of jaw lesions demonstrating ghost cells and compare their histopathological features, with emphasis on the morphological variations of ghost cells in different lesions.

Case report

This case series includes jaw lesions showing ghost cells on histopathological examination retrieved from previously diagnosed cases in the Department of Oral Pathology at PGIDS. Archived histological slides were reviewed to evaluate the distribution and morphological characteristics of ghost cells. The slides were assessed for appearance, structural features and patterns of ghost cell formation, and the variations observed among the lesions were compared.

Discussion

Ghost cells are believed to arise from aberrant keratinization or degenerative changes within odontogenic epithelium. Their morphology and extent vary among lesions and may assist in differential diagnosis.

Conclusion

Ghost cell lesions of the jaws show variable histopathological features. Detailed evaluation of ghost cell morphology may aid in accurate diagnosis and better understanding of these lesions.

Histopathological spectrum of skin lesions at a tertiary care hospital

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Introduction

Skin diseases are highly prevalent worldwide, and many dermatoses show overlapping clinical features; hence histopathological examination is essential for accurate diagnosis and classification.

Aim and Objectives

To analyse the histopathological spectrum of skin lesions, correlate findings with age, sex, anatomical site and categorize lesions into non-neoplastic and neoplastic groups including benign, premalignant, intermediate, and malignant tumors.

Materials and Methods

A cross-sectional observational retrospective study of skin biopsies was conducted over a period of years with a sample size of 260 patients in the Department of Pathology, GCSMCH & RC. Chi-square test and Fisher's Exact Test were applied where appropriate, with $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

Results

Skin lesions were most common in adults aged 21–50 years with nearly equal gender distribution. Non-neoplastic lesions constituted the majority, mainly infections and inflammatory dermatoses and predominantly involved the lower limbs and torso, while tumors were more frequent in sun-exposed head and neck regions. Neoplastic lesions were fewer and mostly benign, whereas premalignant and malignant tumors were more common after 60 years. Keratinocytic tumors predominated, with seborrheic keratosis as the commonest benign lesion and squamous and basal cell carcinomas showing similar frequency.

Discussion

The predominance of infectious and inflammatory dermatoses reflects regional epidemiological patterns. Benign tumors were common, while malignancies increased with advancing age, likely due to cumulative ultraviolet exposure. A lower melanoma incidence compared with Western populations was observed.

Conclusion

Histopathology is indispensable for definitive diagnosis, early detection of malignancy, accurate classification, and guiding appropriate clinical management of skin lesions.

PP-18

A prospective study to determine the prevalence of abnormal cervical smears in reproductive age group on liquid based cytology (lbc)

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Introduction

Cervical cancer is the 2nd most common cancer in females in India. Progression from precancerous lesions to cancer takes years, allowing scope for early detection by screening.

Objectives

To find the prevalence of various abnormal cervical smears, study the cytomorphological features on LBC as well as conventional PAP smear and to compare these two methods. To correlate the findings with histopathology and HPV status wherever possible.

Material and methods

Cervical samples were taken by LBC cytobrush making a conventional slide first and then transferring the material to LBC vial.

Results

Statistically significant association was observed between LBC and conventional PAP with higher-grade lesions showing similar agreement. However, LBC had higher detection of LSIL, ASC-H & ASC-US. Although higher-grade lesions were more frequent among HPV-positive women, the association did not reach statistical significance.

Discussion

Higher age shows association with abnormal lesions. LBC shows higher sensitivity (80.8% vs. 61.5% of conventional pap) but similar specificity of 90%. Many studies also show LBC to be more sensitive with other advantages such as decreased unsatisfactory rates, HPV DNA testing from same sample and better quality smears.

Conclusion

LBC is found to be better than conventional PAP mainly with respect to higher sensitivity. It does provide advantages and is gaining popularity, however conventional method continues to be a valuable method and practical choice in resource-limited settings. Irrespective of method used - periodic follow up is advised. HPV DNA and vaccination status can help in predicting disease progression.

PP-19

Giant placental chorangioma- a case series of two cases

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Introduction

Chorioangioma is a benign, non-trophoblastic vascular tumor of the placenta, with an estimated incidence of approximately 1%. Giant chorioangiomas, defined as lesions exceeding 4 cm in diameter, are uncommon and occur in about 1 in 3,500 to 1 in 9,000 pregnancies. These large tumors are readily identifiable on prenatal ultrasonography and are often linked with twin gestation, gestational diabetes mellitus, maternal hypertension, and female fetuses.

Objective

We report two cases of placental chorangioma.

Case reports

The first case involved a 24-year-old primigravida at 39 weeks of gestation with history of hyperthyroidism admitted for vaginal delivery, while the second case was a 34-year-old multigravida G3P2L2 with uneventful antenatal history and suspicion of chorangioma or succenturiate lobe was admitted for caesarean section. Gross examination revealed a raised nodular area measuring 8x7.5 cm and 6x5cm respectively. Histopathology from the both the lesions were consistent with chorangioma.

Discussion

Giant chorangiomas, > 5 cm in diameter, are rare tumours, with prevalence ranging from 1:9,000 to 1:50,000, and often associated with a variety of pregnancy complications and a poor perinatal outcome. Kataria et al in 2020 reported a frequency of about 1% chorangiomas in their study. Buca et al in 2019 reported, perinatal mortality occurred in 31.2% of fetuses suggesting that chorangiomas are associated with adverse perinatal outcome.

Conclusion

Careful surveillance and serial ultrasound assessments are essential in pregnancies complicated by chorioangioma for a better outcome.

PP-20

Histopathological spectrum of non-neoplastic and neoplastic dermatological lesions

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Introduction

The skin is the largest organ of the body and frequently affected by a wide range of disorders. Despite variable histological presentations, many skin conditions share overlapping clinical features. Histopathological analysis through skin biopsies, especially punch biopsy is crucial for definitive diagnosis and effective treatment planning.

Objective

To study the histopathological patterns of neoplastic and non-neoplastic dermatological lesions in skin biopsy specimens received under over a one-year period.

Materials and method

A retrospective review was conducted on 45 punch biopsy cases received in the department of pathology. Patient details including age and gender were retrieved. All biopsies were evaluated histologically to classify lesions into neoplastic and non-neoplastic categories.

Result

Out of 45 cases, 68 were non-neoplastic and 32 were neoplastic. Cystic lesions and Hansens disease were the most common non-neoplastic findings. Rare non-neoplastic conditions such as Acropigmentation of Kitamura and elephantiasis Nostras Verrucosa were observed. Two rare neoplastic cases of dermatofibrosarcoma protuberans were also reported. The 21-30 year age group was most affected, with male predominance.

Discussion and conclusion

Punch biopsy proves to be a vital diagnostic tool for dermatological conditions, particularly when clinical features are ambiguous. The study provides valuable insight into the specimen of histopathological diagnoses and emphasize the importance of biopsy in identifying both common and rare skin disorders, thereby enhancing clinical outcomes.

PP-21

Paraurethral leiomyoma presenting as a bladder mass: a rare case report

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Introduction

Leiomyomas are benign tumors originating from smooth muscle cells. However, paraurethral leiomyomas are extremely rare, with only a few cases reported in the literature to date. Due to their rarity and overlapping clinical features with other urogenital and gynecological conditions, their diagnosis and management often pose a diagnostic challenge.

Objective

To highlight paraurethral leiomyoma as an important differential diagnosis of a paraurethral mass and to emphasize its clinical presentation, diagnostic approach, and management.

Case report

We report a case of paraurethral leiomyoma in a 27-year-old female presenting with a bladder mass. Contrast-enhanced MRI revealed a well-defined, solid, ovoid lesion with altered signal intensity measuring approximately 26×39×38 mm, located along the vaginal wall, lateral to the urethra. The patient underwent surgical excision of the mass. Histopathological examination confirmed the diagnosis of leiomyoma, supported by immunohistochemical positivity for smooth muscle antigen (SMA).

Discussion

Paraurethral leiomyoma is a rare benign, hormone-dependent mesenchymal tumor, predominantly affecting women of reproductive age, typically in the fourth or fifth decade of life. Clinically, it presents as a paraurethral mass, often associated with urinary symptoms such as dysuria, urinary retention or obstructive symptoms. Imaging modalities such as ultrasonography and MRI aid in preoperative evaluation, while histopathology with immunohistochemistry confirms the diagnosis. Complete surgical excision remains the treatment of choice with excellent prognosis.

Conclusion

Paraurethral leiomyoma is a rare benign tumor of periurethral smooth muscle and an important differential diagnosis for paraurethral masses in reproductive-age women; early imaging and multidisciplinary evaluation aid accurate diagnosis and management.

PP-22

Histopathological spectrum of female genital tract tuberculosis: A retrospective study of three years

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Bps Gmc W Khanpur kalan

Introduction

Female genital tract tuberculosis is frequently encountered disease in developing countries and a global health problem. It accounts 10-20% of extrapulmonary tuberculosis cases, out of which 9% cases are of genital tuberculosis.

Objectives

To study the histopathological spectrum of female genital tract tuberculosis.

Material and Methods

This study was conducted in the Department of Pathology, BPS GMC (W) Khanpur Kalan. Patients data was collected retrospectively from January 2023 to December 2025 in one year duration.

Histopathological requisition forms and slides were retrieved and were evaluated.

Results

A total of 17 cases were taken in this study, out of which 52.9% cases were in second decade. Maximum patients presented with infertility (41.1%) and Bleeding per vaginum (41.1%) respectively. On histopathological examination, 64.7% cases had granuloma and 35.2% cases showed caseation with granuloma. Out of 17 cases only 1 case was positive for Acid Fast Bacilli stain.

Discussion

In this study, mean age was 30.1 years. In the present study, endometrial tuberculosis (58.8%) is the most frequently involved similar to the study done by Raja M et al with 45.46% cases of endometrial tuberculosis. Similarly, study done by Mondal SK et al showed 12.7% cases of caseation with granuloma which is in concordance with 35.2% cases of present study.

Conclusion

Genital tuberculosis is a huge burden specially in reproductive females as it presents with vast variety of clinical features. Tuberculosis as the primary possibility in endemic countries like India should be kept in mind as the disease has good prognosis with proper treatment.

References

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PP-23

Unexpected after the knife- pseudolymphoma masquerading as gastrointestinal malignancy

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Introduction

Pseudolymphoma, or reactive lymphoid hyperplasia, is a rare benign proliferation of lymphoid tissue that can closely mimic malignancy on clinical, radiological, and endoscopic evaluation. RLH commonly occurs in the skin and mucosal surfaces of various organs, but gastric and biliary involvement is uncommon, making preoperative diagnosis particularly challenging.

Objectives

To present two rare cases of pseudolymphoma involving the stomach and common bile duct that clinically mimicked malignancy and resulted in radical surgical treatment.

Case Reports

Case 1: A 47-year-old female presented with frequent bloating, acidity issues and loss of appetite.

Case 2: A 56-year-old male presented with intermittent abdominal pain and was admitted for further evaluation. Physical examination was unremarkable, and his vital signs were stable with mildly elevated ALT, ASP and ALP.

Both patients showed imaging and clinical findings highly suggestive of malignancy. One patient underwent gastrectomy for suspected gastric carcinoma, while the other underwent pancreaticoduodenectomy for presumed cholangiocarcinoma. However, histopathological examination revealed reactive lymphoid hyperplasia with no evidence of malignancy.

Discussion

Pseudolymphoma is a polyclonal lymphoid proliferation forming germinal centers and follicles in response to chronic antigenic stimulation. It is commonly seen in middle-aged individuals with a female predominance. Preoperative diagnosis is difficult because imaging resembles malignancy. Definitive diagnosis requires histopathological evaluation, highlighting the importance of considering pseudolymphoma in the differential diagnosis of suspicious gastrointestinal masses.

Conclusion

Pseudolymphoma can closely resemble malignant tumors and may lead to extensive surgery. Awareness of this rare entity is essential to guide appropriate clinical management.

PP-24

Hypereosinophilic syndrome

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Introduction

Hypereosinophilia is defined as persistent elevation of absolute eosinophil count above $1.5 \times 10^9/L$ in peripheral blood. It may arise due to reactive conditions such as parasitic infections, allergy, drug reactions, autoimmune diseases, or clonal hematologic malignancies. Persistent eosinophilia requires thorough evaluation because prolonged eosinophilic proliferation can lead to tissue infiltration and organ damage. Bone marrow examination plays an important role in differentiating reactive hypereosinophilia from neoplastic conditions such as chronic eosinophilic leukemia.

Case Report

A 32-year-old male presented with complaints of generalized weakness, intermittent fever for one year, and joint pains. Hematological investigations showed hemoglobin of 13.5 g/dL, TLC of $27,230/mm^3$, and platelet count of $3.39 \times 10^5/mm^3$. Differential count revealed marked eosinophilia (70%) with an absolute eosinophil count of $19,061/mm^3$. Peripheral smear showed normocytic normochromic red cells with marked eosinophilic leukocytosis and adequate platelets.

Bone marrow aspiration revealed normocellular marrow with a myeloid-to-erythroid ratio of 2.8:1. Erythropoiesis showed normoblastic maturation, while myelopoiesis demonstrated orderly maturation with increased eosinophils and their precursors. Blast count was 2% and megakaryocytes were adequate. Trepine biopsy confirmed normocellular marrow with eosinophilic predominance without dysplasia.

Discussion

Hypereosinophilia may be reactive or clonal. The absence of dysmyelopoiesis, increased blasts, or molecular evidence of clonal proliferation helps exclude neoplastic causes. In presented case, bone marrow findings showed increased eosinophils with normal maturation, suggesting nonneoplastic hypereosinophilia.

Conclusion

This case highlights the importance of bone marrow examination in evaluating persistent eosinophilia. Identifying reactive causes and assessing for possible organ involvement are essential for appropriate management and followup.

PP-25

Return of dark fungus: a recurrent case of subcutaneous phaeohyphomycosis

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Introduction

Phaeohyphomycosis is a rare fungal infection caused by dematiaceous fungi commonly affecting immunocompromised individuals but may occasionally occur in immunocompetent patients. The disease can involve skin, subcutaneous tissue, paranasal sinuses, or systemic organs and often poses a diagnostic challenge due to its varied clinical presentation.

Case report

A 53-year-old immunocompetent male presented with complaints of nodular swellings at different locations over the left upper limb for one year. FNA was performed from a lesion over thumb which revealed dense neutrophilic infiltrate along with macrophages, lymphocytes and multinucleated giant cells. Numerous pigmented septate fungal hyphae with globose swellings were also seen which were highlighted on PAS and Masson Fontana stains. After 5 months, he developed a similar nodular swelling over the left elbow, raising suspicion of a recurrence. FNA was repeated and cytological smears showed similar morphology. Further, the patient underwent excisional biopsy of the same. Histopathological examination showed a cystic tissue fragment with a wall composed of palisaded histiocytes and foreign body type giant cells with intracytoplasmic pigmented septate fungal hyphae, confirming the diagnosis of phaeohyphomycosis.

Discussion and Conclusion

Subcutaneous phaeohyphomycosis may present as recurrent lesions, often posing a diagnostic challenge as phaeoid fungi are rarely seen in routine cytologic practice. This case highlights the value of careful evaluation of cytologic smears and an awareness of the characteristic morphologic features of phaeohyphomycosis is helpful in diagnosis fungal infection, as its recognition is important to ensure timely management to prevent dissemination.

PP-26

Assessment of chatgpt as a potential tool in scenarios and knowledge based questions in pathology solving case

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Introduction

ChatGPT (Chat Generative Pre-Trained Transformer) is an advanced conversational Artificial Intelligence tool that can support educational initiatives. The aim of this study is to provide a comprehensive and practical assessment of ChatGPT for the application of AI in medical education.

Material and Methods

A total of 100 questions from 36 topics of Pathology according to CBME (Competency based medical education) curriculum were selected by three faculty members. These 100 questions comprised 50 open-ended questions which included problem-based questions and long answer questions and 50 multiple choice questions (MCQs) with single answer. The response generated by ChatGPT were evaluated. Using a score of 0 and 5, all 100 questions were evaluated.

Result

Out of 50 MCQs, answers of 39 (78%) were found correct along with appropriate explanations. The mean score was 3.9 with standard deviation of 2.09. The result was statistically significant with a mean hypothetical value of 2.5 but was insignificant with mean hypothetical value of 4.0. In the case of 50 long answer questions, the overall mean score was 4.36 with standard deviation of 0.62, which was found to be statistically significant.

Conclusion

ChatGPT can serve as virtual tutor, mentor and guide offering explanations of complex medical concepts requiring higher order reasoning. However, ChatGPT seems partially effective in providing relevant details specific for pathology in terms of laboratory diagnosis. Further improvement, review and validation is required for its potential usage.

PP-27

Mucormycosis, Left Kidney, Presenting as infected kidney in a 70-year-old male.

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Introduction

Mucormycosis is a rapidly progressive, angioinvasive fungal infection caused by fungi of the order Mucorales. It primarily affects immunocompromised individuals and commonly involves rhino-orbital and pulmonary sites. Isolated renal mucormycosis is rare and often presents as a diagnostic challenge due to nonspecific clinical and radiological features.

Objectives

To report a rare case of renal mucormycosis presenting as an infected kidney and to highlight its characteristic histopathological features.

Case report

A 70-year-old male underwent nephrectomy for a clinically suspected left infected kidney. Grossly, the kidney measured $11.5 \times 8.5 \times 6.5$ cm with attached ureter. The outer surface showed grey-brown discoloration with purulent material. Cut section revealed necrotic cortex and a grey-white cheesy nodule in perinephric fat. Microscopy showed extensive ischemic necrosis involving glomeruli, vessels, tubulointerstitium, and perirenal fat. Poorly formed epithelioid granulomas with dense inflammatory infiltrate were noted. Numerous broad aseptate fungal hyphae with irregular right-angle branching infiltrating renal tissue and vessels were identified. Angioinvasion with thrombosis was evident. PAS stain was positive, confirming fungal elements.

Discussion

Renal mucormycosis occurs due to hematogenous spread or ascending infection and is characterized by angioinvasion leading to thrombosis and infarction. Histopathology remains the gold standard for diagnosis.

Conclusion

Renal mucormycosis is a rare, life-threatening infection requiring high clinical suspicion. Early histopathological diagnosis is essential for timely management and improved survival.

PP-28

Neuroendocrine tumor of larynx : A rare entity

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Introduction

Neuroendocrine tumor of the larynx exhibit a wide spectrum of morphological features and biological behavior, making accurate histopathological diagnosis and grading crucial for appropriate management and prognosis.

Objectives

To highlight the histomorphological and immunohistochemical features of well-differentiated neuroendocrine tumor of the larynx to emphasize the importance of ancillary studies in diagnosis and grading.

Case Report

A biopsy specimen was received from an ulceroproliferative growth involving the arytenoid region of the larynx.

microscopy revealed a tumor composed of sheets, nests, trabeculae, and cords of tumor cells separated by hyalinized stroma. The tumor cells showed mild to moderate pleomorphism with round to ovoid, centrally to eccentrically placed nuclei, granular chromatin, variably prominent nucleoli, and scant to moderate eosinophilic cytoplasm were noted. Focal nuclear palisading and rosette formation were present. Few mitotic figures, including atypical ones seen (<20/10HPF). Immunohistochemical showed Pan-cytokeratin, CK7, CEA, synaptophysin, chromogranin, and INSM1 positive confirming epithelial and neuroendocrine differentiation. Based on the morphological features and IHC a diagnosis of well-differentiated neuroendocrine tumor, WHO Grade 3, was rendered.

Discussion

Laryngeal NETs comprise less than 1% of all laryngeal neoplasms with strong male predominance. Differential diagnosis includes poorly differentiated SCC, Basaloid SCC, Paraganglioma of larynx and Malignant lymphoma. Classic morphology with IHC marker of Neuroendocrine differentiation (Synaptophysin, Chromogranin, INSMI) helps in distinction from these entities.

Conclusion

Given the rarity of laryngeal NETs and their aggressive behaviour, a combined approach using histomorphology and a comprehensive immunohistochemical panel is vital for accurate diagnosis and grading, which directly impacts patient management and prognosis.

PP-29

Pure squamous cell carcinoma of gall bladder-case report of a rare lesion

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Introduction

Pure squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) of the gallbladder is an exceptionally rare malignancy, accounting for only 1% of all gallbladder cancers. It is associated with aggressive local invasion and poor prognosis, often presenting with nonspecific symptoms that delay diagnosis.

Objective

To report a rare case of pure SCC of gallbladder and highlight its histopathological features and clinical significance.

Case Report

A 45-year-old female presented with epigastric pain for 9 months. Ultrasonography revealed a distended gallbladder with multiple calculi and an echogenic mass (55×53.2 mm) arising from the fundus. The patient underwent extended cholecystectomy.

Gross examination showed a distended gall bladder measuring 10.5×7.5×1.5cm. Cut surface of the gall bladder showed lumen filled with pultaceous material and multiple stones. Wall thickness varied from 0.3 to 0.5cm. Microscopy revealed a well differentiated SCC with vascular invasion and tumour infiltration into liver and hilar tissue - pT3N0 (AJCC 8th edition).

Discussion

Pure SCC predominantly affects females in the fourth to sixth decades and is often associated with long-standing cholelithiasis and chronic inflammation induced squamous metaplasia and malignant transformation. SCC demonstrates aggressive local growth into adjacent organs, particularly the liver with relatively lower lymph node metastasis. Prognosis largely depends on the stage at diagnosis, and surgical resection remains the primary treatment for localized disease.

Conclusion

Pure SCC of the gallbladder is a rare and aggressive malignancy characterized by marked local invasion. This case highlights its association with chronic cholelithiasis and underscores the role of meticulous histopathological evaluation of cholecystectomy specimens for early detection of this uncommon tumour.

PP-30

Micropapillary Urothelial Carcinoma of the Bladder: A Rare but Aggressive Variant

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Introduction

Micropapillary urothelial carcinoma (MPUC) is a rare and aggressive histological variant of urothelial carcinoma of the urinary bladder. It is associated with a high rate of lymphovascular invasion, early muscle invasion, and poor clinical outcomes. Early identification of this variant is essential because it often requires more aggressive therapeutic management compared to conventional urothelial carcinoma.

Objectives

To present a case of invasive micropapillary urothelial carcinoma of the urinary bladder and highlight its characteristic histopathological features and aggressive nature.

Case Report

A 66-year-old male presented with urinary symptoms and hematuria. Radiological evaluation with CT urography revealed a heterogeneously enhancing lesion along the right posterolateral wall of the urinary bladder. Transurethral resection of bladder tumor (TURBT) was performed. Histopathological examination showed high-grade high-grade urothelial carcinoma, micropapillary subtype. The overlying urothelium demonstrated carcinoma in situ, and tumor infiltration into the deep muscle was identified.

Discussion

Micropapillary urothelial carcinoma (MPUC) is an uncommon but clinically significant variant characterized by aggressive biological behavior and a high propensity for early muscle invasion and metastasis, accounting for 0.6-2.2% of bladder cancers. Prior to establishing the diagnosis, it is essential to rule out secondary involvement from other primary tumors exhibiting micropapillary morphology. Common primary sites include the urinary bladder and lung in males, and the breast and ovary in females, which should be considered during clinicopathological correlation.

Conclusion

Micropapillary urothelial carcinoma is an aggressive variant of bladder cancer. Early diagnosis and timely management are crucial to improve patient outcomes.

PP-31

A fatty surprise: incidental lipoleiomyoma in hysterectomy specimens

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Introduction

Lipoleiomyoma is a rare benign mesenchymal tumor of uterus and considered a variant of leiomyoma, characterized by presence of mature adipose tissue admixed with smooth muscle cells. Most common in peri-menopausal and post-menopausal women and associated with metabolic conditions.

Objective

We report two incidental cases of uterine Lipoleiomyoma.

Case Reports

A 49 year female P2L2 with AUB , with hypothyroidism underwent Total Abdominal Hysterectomy with bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy.

On gross: Endometrium shows polypoidal growth of 0.5cm diameter, fibroid in lower uterine segment of 2cm diameter.

HPE : Cervix shows leiomyoma with chronic non-specific cervicitis, lower uterine segment leiomyoma shows features of lipoleiomyoma.

A 44 year female P3L3 with AUB. Total abdominal hysterectomy with bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy done.

On Gross: External surface shows nodular mass of 2cm diameter and shows whorled areas. Endometrium shows polypoid growth. Myometrium has intra-mural fibroid measuring 3cm diameter and 2cm fibroid in lower uterine segment.

HPE: lower uterine segment shows leiomyoma showing features of lipoleiomyoma.

Discussion

The exact pathogenesis remains unclear, may involve fatty metaplasia of smooth muscle cells, differentiation of multipotential mesenchymal cells into adipocytes and fatty infiltration within a conventional leiomyoma. The tumors detected incidentally during imaging or surgical procedures. Radiologically, lipoleiomyomas may mimic other fat-containing pelvic lesions such as ovarian teratoma or liposarcoma. Recognition prevents misdiagnosis as a malignant adipocytic tumor and ensure appropriate management.

Conclusion

Lipoleiomyoma is a rare benign uterine tumor with excellent prognosis. Histopathological examination remains the gold standard for diagnosis and it prevents overtreatment.

PP-32

Rare case of invasive squamous cell carcinoma arising in an intradiploic epidermoid cyst

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Introduction

Intradiploic epidermoid cysts are rare developmental lesions arising within the diploe of the skull due to congenital ectodermal inclusion during embryogenesis. They are slow-growing and typically benign. Squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) arising from intradiploic epidermoid cyst is exceedingly rare.

Objective

To report a rare case of invasive SCC arising in an intradiploic epidermoid cyst.

Case report

A 72-year-old male presented with headache for three years. MRI revealed an well defined peripherally enhancing extra axial cystic lesion causing calvarial bone defect in right occipital bone with mass effect. Radiological diagnosis of intradiploic epidermoid cyst in the right occipital region was given. Histopathological examination showed a cyst wall lined by stratified squamous epithelium with areas of SCC in situ and invasive SCC infiltrating the cyst wall and skull bone. Immunohistochemistry demonstrated p40 positivity, and Ki-67 proliferation index was high (80%), supporting the diagnosis.

Discussion

SCC arising in an epidermoid cyst was first described in 1912. Malignant transformation of primary intraosseous epidermoid cysts has been reported in only in 6 cases. These tumours either present as long-standing lesions with repeated recurrences or may be malignant at presentation. Metastasis from an unknown primary must be excluded.

Conclusion

Invasive SCC arising in an intradiploic epidermoid cyst is a rare but aggressive entity requiring thorough histopathological and IHC evaluation for accurate diagnosis and management.

PP-33

Schwannoma-like leiomyoma of vulva: a rare diagnostic mimicker

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Introduction

Schwannoma-like leiomyoma is a rare histological variant of leiomyoma that mimics schwannoma due to nuclear palisading and Verocay body-like structures. Vulvar occurrence of this lesion is extremely rare.

Objectives

To describe a rare vulvar schwannoma-like leiomyoma and its diagnostic mimickers.

Case report

A 45-year-old female presented with a freely mobile, non-tender cystic mass in the left labia majora. It was clinically diagnosed as lipoma and was excised.

Grossly, a single grey-white globular soft tissue specimen measuring 1.4 cm was received; the cut surface was solid and grey-white.

Microscopy showed a well-circumscribed tumor composed of interlacing fascicles of bland spindle cells with elongated blunt-ended nuclei and eosinophilic cytoplasm. Prominent nuclear palisading with the Verocay body-like structures and intervening anuclear zones was seen throughout the tumor. No hypocellular areas or mitotic figures were identified. On immunohistochemistry, tumor cells showed diffuse positivity for smooth muscle actin (SMA) and were negative for S100, confirming the diagnosis of schwannoma like leiomyoma of vulva.

Discussion

Vulvar leiomyomas constitute approximately 0.03% of gynecologic tumors and 0.07% of vulvar neoplasms. Nielsen et al. reported a 5% recurrence rate. Wide local excision with clear margins is the treatment of choice to reduce recurrence. Although reported between 15–70 years, most cases occur in postmenopausal women.

Conclusion

Schwannoma-like leiomyoma of the vulva is a rare benign tumor requiring careful histopathological and immunohistochemical evaluation for accurate diagnosis and management.

PP-34

A diagnostic surprise : Breast mass caused by extramedullary disease in multiple myeloma detected on cytology

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Introduction

Multiple Myeloma with extramedullary spread is a rare phenomenon with an incidence of 7% which can occur in the upper respiratory tract, liver, spleen, lymph nodes, skin etc. Multiple Myeloma with breast infiltration, is an extremely rare form of extra medullary disease occurring in less than 0.1% of all multiple myeloma cases.

Case Presentation

A 71-year old female, known case of multiple myeloma since 2 years, presented with a palpable right breast lump of size 3x4 cm since last 1 month. FNAC from the lump showed singly scattered and loose clusters of tumour cells having eccentric nuclei, coarse chromatin and inconspicuous nucleoli with occasional binucleate cells. CD 138 Immunocytochemistry was done on the cell block which showed diffuse membranous positivity. The case was reported as category V, malignant breast lump with infiltration with plasma cells in a known case of multiple myeloma.

Discussion and Conclusion

Multiple Myeloma involving the breast is a challenging diagnosis because the clinical and radiological features of breast multiple myeloma are not distinct to other forms of primary or metastatic breast disease. The case emphasizes the importance of cytology as a rapid and minimally invasive diagnostic tool for detecting plasma cell infiltration at rare sites, which can help avoid delay in diagnosis and more invasive procedures like Trucut biopsy.

PP-35

Cervical leiomyoma with schwannoma-like pattern. A rare case report.

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Introduction

Leiomyoma is uncommon benign smooth muscle tumour arising from the uterine, cervix. Cervical leiomyoma is a benign smooth muscle tumor arising from the smooth muscle of the cervix. It is much less common than uterine (corpus) leiomyomas and accounts for about 0.6-2% of all leiomyoma. The most common age group affecting is 30-40. Histologically, leiomyomas exhibit various morphological patterns, some of which may mimic other mesenchymal tumours. One such rare variant is leiomyoma with schwannoma-like pattern which shows palisading nuclei and fascicular arrangement resembling a schwannoma, but it is still composed of smooth muscle cells.

Aim and objectives

Interpretation of rare differential histopathological diagnosis of cervical leiomyoma with schwannoma-like pattern.

Case Report

A 36 year old female presented with abnormal vaginal bleeding with occasional pelvic discomfort from past 7 months. The clinical diagnosis of cervical polyp was made. The polyp was excised and grossly a globular grey-white to grey-brown soft tissue piece measuring 3.0×2.2×1.4 cm in size received. Microscopic examination done.

Results

Section examined shows feature suggestion of leiomyoma which is having Schwannoma like pattern, which on immunohistochemistry is SMA positive but S100 Negative.

Conclusions

Cervical leiomyoma is an exceedingly rare, benign histological variant of uterine leiomyoma that exhibits features mimicking a nerve sheath tumor (Schwannoma), featuring Antoni A (hypercellular) and Antoni B (hypocellular) areas. This unusual morphology may lead to diagnostic confusion with neural tumours. Careful histomorphological evaluation along with immunohistochemistry is essential to establish the smooth muscle origin and to differentiate it from schwannoma and other spindle cell neoplasms.

PP-36

Neuroendocrine tumor of the urinary bladder: a rare paraganglioma case

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Introduction

Paraganglioma (PGLs) is a rare extra-adrenal pheochromocytoma. About 10% of PGLs occur in extra-adrenal sites, of which 10% are located in bladder wall accounting for 0.05% of all bladder tumors. It arises from chromaffin cells of bladder wall.

Case presentation

A 40-year-old female presented with headache while micturition. On ultrasonography the urinary bladder was normal in shape. A well-defined hypoechoic mass of 2.5cms x 2cms size was observed along its posterior wall. On color doppler- much enhanced vascularity was observed in the mass. On CT (Abdomen and Pelvis)- UB was partially distended and shows enhancing lesion measuring 2x1.7cms. Biopsy was taken and was sent for histopathological examination which was reported as paraganglioma of urinary bladder and was further confirmed on IHC.

Conclusion

Paraganglioma of the urinary bladder, though rare, should be considered in patients presenting with micturition-induced symptoms as in this case. A combination of clinical suspicion, histopathology and immunohistochemistry is essential for accurate diagnosis and optimal management.

PP-37

Multiple ileal plasmacytomas with extensive amyloid deposition presenting as acute intestinal obstruction: report of a rare occurrence

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Introduction

Extramedullary plasmacytoma (EMP) arises outside the bone marrow and accounts for a small proportion of plasma cell dyscrasias. Ileal involvement with extensive amyloid deposition is exceedingly rare and we report this uncommon occurrence.

Objectives

To present a rare case of ileal EMP with amyloid deposition.

Case report

A 70 years old female presented with abdominal distention and recurrent vomiting for 5 days. A clinical diagnosis of acute intestinal obstruction was made. The patient underwent stapled right hemicolectomy.

Grossly, mesentery and wall of ileum showed 2 tan brown submucosal nodules measuring (4x3x2)cm and (2.5x2.5x2.5)cm respectively . Histopathological examination revealed extensive deposits of eosinophilic hyaline material surrounded by sheets of atypical plasma cells with eccentric round nuclei, coarse chromatin, variably conspicuous nucleoli and moderate amount of eosinophilic cytoplasm. Occasional binucleated forms were noted.

On Congo red staining, under polarized microscopy, the eosinophilic material exhibited apple green birefringence consistent with amyloid deposition. On IHC, atypical plasma cells were positive for CD38 and CD138. Hence, the diagnosis of Plasmacytoma with amyloid deposition was made.

Discussion

Ileal involvement by EMP with extensive amyloid deposition is exceedingly rare, with only isolated cases described in literature worldwide. Unlike the more common head and neck presentations, gastrointestinal lesions often present late with obstructive symptoms. Extensive amyloid accumulation contributes to mass effect and luminal compromise.

Conclusion

EMP with amyloid deposition in the gastrointestinal tract is an uncommon entity that may present as intestinal obstruction. Accurate histopathological evaluation, Congo red confirmation and exclusion of systemic disease are necessary.

PP-38

Metaplastic carcinoma of the breast: a diagnostic challenge

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Introduction

Metaplastic breast carcinoma (MBC) is a rare and aggressive histological subtype of invasive breast cancer characterized by the transformation of glandular epithelium into squamous or mesenchymal elements. Clinically, these tumors often present as rapidly growing, large masses that frequently lack estrogen, progesterone, and HER2 receptor expression. Due to its heterogeneous nature and "triple-negative" profile, MBC poses a significant diagnostic challenge and typically follows a more guarded prognosis compared to standard invasive ductal carcinomas.

Case Report

A 71-year-old female presented to the Department of pathology, GNDH, ASR with chief complaint of painless lump in the left breast of one month. Radiology revealed a BIRADS III hypermetabolic mass in the left breast with associated low-load axillary and mediastinal lymphadenopathy. An initial biopsy suggested a poorly differentiated malignancy. On histopathological examination, sections show malignant tumour composed of areas of sarcomatoid, squamoid and heterologous mesenchymal differentiation composed of chondroid tissue. Immunohistochemical analysis was further done for confirmation and recognising different histological components.

Conclusion

This case highlights the clinical urgency required when managing rapidly progressing breast masses in elderly patients. The diagnosis of metaplastic carcinoma necessitates meticulous histopathological and immunohistochemical correlation to differentiate it from other poorly differentiated or spindle-cell malignancies. Early and accurate identification is paramount for initiating appropriate aggressive multimodality treatment.

PP-39

Beyond acute appendicitis: the clinicopathological spectrum of appendiceal mucinous neoplasms

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Introduction

Appendiceal mucinous neoplasms (AMNs) are rare epithelial tumors, identified in approximately 2% of appendectomy specimens. Their clinical presentation is often nonspecific and may mimic acute appendicitis, resulting in incidental diagnosis on histopathological examination.

Objective

To highlight the clinicopathological spectrum and diagnostic significance of appendiceal mucinous neoplasms through three representative cases.

Case Series

Case 1: An 84-year-old female presented with right iliac fossa pain and vomiting; histopathology revealed low-grade appendiceal mucinous neoplasm (LAMN).

Case 2: A 68-year-old female presented with perforated appendicitis, and subsequent examination confirmed high-grade appendiceal mucinous neoplasm (HAMN).

Case 3: A 61-year-old male presented with persistent right iliac fossa pain, and histopathology demonstrated well differentiated mucinous adenocarcinoma involving the appendix.

Discussion

Appendiceal mucinous tumors represent a distinct subset of appendiceal epithelial neoplasms, ranging from LAMN and HAMN to invasive mucinous adenocarcinoma. They typically occur in adults in the fifth to seventh decades and may be associated with pseudomyxoma peritonei, a serious complication resulting from peritoneal dissemination of mucin.

Conclusion

Although rare, appendiceal mucinous neoplasms should be considered in patients presenting with right iliac fossa pain. Careful histopathological evaluation is essential for accurate diagnosis, guiding management, and preventing complications such as recurrence, peritoneal seeding, and pseudomyxoma peritonei.

PP-40

Role of cytology and adenosine deaminase estimation in diagnosis of pleural effusion lesions and their significance in clinical approach

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Introduction

Pleural effusion is a frequent clinical issue with diverse etiologies. Cytological examination and adenosine deaminase (ADA) estimation are crucial tools for accurate diagnosis, particularly for identifying tuberculous pleuritis.

Objective

To evaluate cytological features and ADA levels, and to determine the distribution of various lesions causing pleural effusion.

Material & Method

An observational study of 100 cases was conducted. Pleural fluid was analyzed using Giemsa or PAP staining for cytology and specific kits for ADA estimation.

Result

Tuberculosis (TB) was the most frequent diagnosis (47 cases), followed by pneumonia (24 cases), eosinophilic pleural effusion (18 cases), malignancy in 9 individuals, and congestive heart failure in 2 individuals. TB cases demonstrated the highest mean ADA levels (61.9 ± 12.2), lymphocytes (85.7 ± 7.3), and protein (5.0 ± 0.3). The ADA test achieved perfect discrimination with an Area Under the Curve (AUC) of 1.000.

Discussion

Elevated ADA and lymphocyte levels strongly correlate with TB effusions, whereas conditions like pneumonia and malignancy exhibit higher neutrophil counts. This supports the use of ADA as a highly effective diagnostic marker for TB.

Conclusion

Distinct pleural fluid characteristics, especially elevated ADA levels, provide robust diagnostic accuracy for identifying TB. Integrating multiple fluid parameters significantly enhances diagnostic and clinical management.

PP-41

Plasma cell gingivitis simulating a neoplastic lesion on NCCT: a diagnostic challenge and a rare case report

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Introduction

Plasma cell gingivitis (PCG) is a benign inflammatory condition presented histologically as a dense plasma cell infiltration in the subepithelial connective tissue. It is also known as allergic or idiopathic gingivostomatitis and gingival plasmacytosis. Based on etiology, PCG may be associated with allergens, neoplastic processes, or may be idiopathic. Most commonly, it results from a hypersensitivity reaction. Clinically, it presents as reddish, friable gingiva that bleeds easily on touch.

Case presentation

A 24 year old male presented to the ENT department with swelling over the right cheek for 2 years, insidious in onset and gradually progressive. Routine blood investigations were within normal limits. NCCT PNS revealed a well-defined expansile lytic lesion involving the right maxillary alveolus extending into the maxillary sinus with bony erosions. A provisional diagnosis of odontogenic myxoma was made. The patient underwent Caldwell-Luc surgery with complete enucleation, and sent for histopathological examination. Grossly showed a grey brown mass measuring 3x1.5x1cm and on microscopy showed dense subepithelial plasma cell infiltration along with characteristic eccentrically placed nucleus. On IHC plasma cells are positive for CD38, CD138, kappa, lambda and do not show any light chain restriction. Features are consistent with plasma cell gingivitis.

Conclusion

PCG is a diagnosis of exclusion, characterized histologically by dense submucosal plasma cell infiltration after ruling out infections, plasmacytoma, leukemia, and other systemic diseases. Careful history, hematological investigations, and histopathological examination are essential to exclude malignancy and systemic causes. Although recurrences may occur, no progression to malignancy has been reported. PCG is considered a nonspecific inflammatory reaction, possibly triggered by an unknown external agent.

PP-42

When inflammation masks malignancy: a case of recurrent myxoinflammatory fibroblastic sarcoma

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Introduction

Myxoinflammatory Fibroblastic Sarcoma (MIFS) is a rare low to intermediate grade soft tissue sarcoma commonly occurring in the distal extremities of adults. It is characterized by myxoid stroma, inflammatory infiltrate, and atypical spindle to epithelioid tumor cells, often mimicking benign inflammatory lesions and posing diagnostic challenges.

Objectives

To present a recurrent case of MIFS of the lower limb and highlight its histopathological and immunohistochemical features.

Material and Methods: A 55-year-old female presented with recurrent swelling in the right leg with prior excision biopsy six months earlier. Wide local excision was performed. Frozen section was done intraoperatively. The specimen was examined by routine histopathology and immunohistochemistry.

Results

Frozen section showed fibrous tissue with spindle to stellate cells; interpretation was limited. Histology revealed tumour centred in the subcutaneous plane. Tumor cells were spindle to epithelioid arranged in fascicles and sheets with moderate atypia and 18–20 mitoses/HPF. Scattered RS like cells and mixed inflammatory infiltrate were noted. Numerous thin-walled vessels were present in a collagenous to myxoid stroma with focal hemosiderin deposition. Tumor cells were positive for CD10, CD99, and S100 with retained INI1 and H3K27me3.

Discussion

MIFS demonstrates distinctive morphology including inflammation, myxoid stroma, and bizarre tumor cells, which may mimic reactive conditions. Recognition of these features and immunohistochemistry is essential for diagnosis.

Conclusion

MIFS is a rare sarcoma with a high risk of recurrence. Awareness of its characteristic morphology and immunoprofile is crucial for correct diagnosis and appropriate management.

PP-43

Radiology deceived, histology revealed: a case of mucormycosis masquerading as sebaceous cyst

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Introduction

Mucormycosis is an acute opportunistic fungal infection caused by non septate fungi belonging to the class Zygomycetes commonly affecting structures in head and neck, such as sinuses, orbit and brain. Common predisposition factors include diabetes mellitus and immunosuppression.

Case report

A 57-year-old male presented to ENT OPD with history of soft tissue swelling in left maxillary region since seven months. Lesion was confined to the soft tissue and did not involve maxillary sinus. No history of fever, cold & cough, diabetes or hypertension. USG findings were suggestive of sebaceous cyst since there was no bony involvement. FNAC was done and diagnosis of giant cell lesion was made. On histopathological examination multiple perineural & perivascular epithelioid granulomas were seen. PAS stain and GMS showed broad nonseptate hyphae with wide angle branching establishing a diagnosis of granulomatous inflammation secondary to mucormycosis infection.

Discussion and conclusion

Mucormycosis is an uncommon fatal fungal infection, which rarely arises in otherwise healthy people. An underlying disease is always present as in our case patient had hepatitis B infection creating a state of immunosuppression, detected incidentally before patient underwent surgical excision. Tissue invasion by hyphae of mucormycosis must be seen to establish the diagnosis followed by culture. The case is being presented to draw attention that mucormycosis infection can present as solitary lesion in soft tissue around maxilla without any bony involvement or involvement of any orbital sinus and should be considered a differential diagnosis of such maxillary lesion.

Key words

Mucormycosis, opportunistic infection

PP-44

Histomorphologic Spectrum of Low-Grade Appendiceal Mucinous Neoplasms: A Case Series

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Introduction

Low-grade appendiceal mucinous neoplasm (LAMN) is a rare malignant epithelial tumor of the appendix, accounting for approximately 1% of gastrointestinal neoplasms and occurring in fewer than 0.3% of appendectomy specimens. Clinically, it often mimics acute appendicitis due to appendiceal distension, and a definitive diagnosis is established only after histopathological evaluation.

Objective

To study the histomorphologic spectrum of LAMN and highlight their distinction from important mimics, including high-grade appendiceal mucinous neoplasm and mucinous adenocarcinoma, benign epithelial lesions such as serrated polyp and villous adenoma, and non-neoplastic conditions like ruptured appendiceal diverticulum or endometriosis. Accurate recognition is essential because, despite their low-grade cytology, LAMNs may perforate and lead to peritoneal mucin dissemination resulting in pseudomyxoma peritonei.

Case series

Four cases of LAMN were identified in patients aged 50–63 years. Gross examination revealed dilated appendices with mucocele formation and luminal accumulation of gelatinous mucin, with focal areas of wall thinning and perforation in some cases. HPE demonstrated mucinous epithelium with low-grade cytologic atypia and villous to flat architectural patterns. These features were variably associated with attenuation of the lamina propria, atrophy of underlying lymphoid tissue, loss of crypt architecture, and effacement of the muscularis mucosae, along with focal mucin pools.

Discussion and conclusion

LAMN is an uncommon appendiceal neoplasm that may mimic acute appendicitis, making preoperative diagnosis difficult. HPE of resected appendix is essential for confirming the diagnosis and distinguishing LAMN from its differentials. Early recognition and timely surgical management are important, as perforation can lead to mucin dissemination and pseudomyxoma peritonei.

PP-45

A clear cell diagnostic dilemma in the mandible: a rare case report

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Introduction

Clear cell odontogenic carcinoma (CCOC) is a rare and aggressive malignant odontogenic tumor first described by Hansen et al. in 1985. More than 100 cases have been reported, with a mean age of presentation of 53 years and a female predominance. The mandible is the most common site of occurrence. Histopathologically, CCOC may resemble clear cell salivary gland tumors and other epithelial tumors, making diagnosis challenging.

Objective

To present a rare case of clear cell odontogenic carcinoma of the mandible and emphasize the importance of histopathological and immunohistochemical analysis in differentiating it from other clear cell lesions of the jaw.

Case report

A 39-year-old male presented with progressively enlarging mandibular swelling involving both sides of the jaw. The lesion was ulceroproliferative associated with tooth mobility and necrosis. Radiographs revealed erosion and resorption of the inferior border of the mandible. Contrast-enhanced CT showed a large mixed-density lesion measuring $11 \times 9.5 \times 8$ cm with heterogeneous enhancement. Histopathological examination and immunohistochemistry showed strong positivity for p63 and p40, confirming epithelial origin, while CK7 was negative, supporting the diagnosis of CCOC.

Discussion

Clear cell tumors of the jaw are rare and difficult to diagnose due to overlapping features with other tumors. Differential diagnosis includes clear cell SCC, hyalinizing clear cell carcinoma and clear cell MEC which can be distinguished using histopathological and immunohistochemical findings.

Conclusion

Accurate diagnosis using histopathology and immunohistochemistry is essential for appropriate surgical management and to reduce the risk of recurrence.

PP-46

The Pancreas That Took a Detour: A Rare Entity

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INTRODUCTION

Heterotopic pancreas is defined as pancreatic tissue found outside the normal anatomical location of the pancreas without direct vascular or ductal continuity with the main pancreas. It is usually an incidental finding. It can occur at various sites in the gastrointestinal tract like stomach, duodenum, and proximal jejunum. Heterotopic pancreatic tissue has been reported in up to 15% of individuals in autopsy studies. Majority of cases remain asymptomatic with the incidence in of approximately 0.2%. The reported male-to-female ratio is about 3:1.

CASE REPORT

A 45-year-old male presented with complaints of epigastric pain for four years. The pain was moderate in intensity, aggravated after meals, and relieved on sitting. Routine haematological investigations were within normal limits. USG and CECT scan of the whole abdomen did not reveal any significant abnormality. Upper GI endoscopy showed a duodenal sessile polyp suspected of malignancy. Elective distal gastrectomy revealed a growth measuring 2 × 1 cm approx. was identified at the level of the pylorus and first part of the duodenum, and the pancreas appeared bulky. Exploratory laparotomy with distal gastrectomy followed by Roux-en-Y gastrojejunostomy and side-to-side jejunojejunostomy was performed. HPE of the gastrectomy specimen revealed heterotopic pancreas. On IHC: CK7 + for pancreatic tissue and Synaptophysin and Chromogranin + for islets cells. The postoperative period was uneventful and the patient was discharged in stable condition.

DISCUSSION

Heterotopic pancreas is a rare entity and its preoperative diagnosis is challenging. The lesion is usually located in the submucosa, making it difficult to differentiate from gastrointestinal stromal tumors. Management of asymptomatic, histologically confirmed gastric heterotopic pancreas remains controversial.

CONCLUSION

For unidentified gastrointestinal masses, heterotopic pancreas should be included in the differential diagnosis. This is because the condition often presents with vague and nonspecific clinical symptoms, potentially leading to misdiagnosis.

PP-47

Evaluating the role of platelet parameters in predicting complicated appendicitis. A prospective cross-sectional study

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Introduction

Acute appendicitis can lead to serious complications like abscess formation, perforation and gangrene. Platelet parameters are a promising tool to predict complications.

Objectives

The primary objective of this study was to measure the platelet parameters including Platelet count (PC), Mean Platelet Volume (MPV), Plateletcrit (PCT) and Platelet Distribution Width (PDW) in emergency appendectomy patients. Secondary objective was to correlate the platelet parameters with histopathological features of appendectomy specimens.

Material and Methods

The study was conducted from April 2024 to July 2025 where the above mentioned platelet parameters were observed in the blood samples taken prior to surgery and correlated with histologic features of the removed appendix. Cases with histologic features like gangrene and thrombosed vessels were taken as complicated appendicitis. The mean of the platelet parameters in these cases were compared with the rest of the cases (uncomplicated) using unpaired t test. Multivariate regression analysis to predict gangrene was also done.

Results

Out of the total 72 cases, there were 25 cases showing complicated histology i.e gangrene and thrombosed vessels. Statistically significant reduced mean platelet volume (7.7 ± 0.8 fl) and elevated platelet count ($338.4 \pm 79.6 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$), plateletcrit ($0.26 \pm 0.07\%$) and platelet distribution width ($17.7 \pm 3.0\%$) were observed in complicated cases (n=25) versus uncomplicated (n= 47) ones. Additionally, multivariate regression analysis identified platelet count $>300 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$, MPV <8.0 fL, PDW $>16\%$, and PCT $>0.25\%$ as significant predictors for gangrene development.

Discussion

Platelet parameters like platelet count, MPV, PDW and PCT were significantly associated not only with the presence of neutrophils in the muscularis propria, but also with complications.

Conclusions

These findings highlight the potential role of platelet indices in predicting the complications in clinical settings.

PP-48

Coexistence of brenner's tumor and mucinous cystadenoma.

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Introduction

Ovarian collision tumors are very rare. The most common reported is mature teratoma and mucinous cystadenoma. Brenner tumor is a rare benign epithelial ovarian tumor accounting for 1–2% of ovarian tumors, whereas mucinous cystadenoma is a more common benign cystic tumor comprising about 14%. Their coexistence in the same ovary is uncommon.

Objective

To report a rare case of coexistence of Brenner's tumor with mucinous cystadenoma.

Case Report

A 74-year-old female presented with a mass per abdomen and pelvic discomfort for 1 month. MRI pelvis showed a 10 × 9 cm complex ovarian cyst with an eccentric solid mural nodule in the left ovary. With high clinical suspicion of malignancy, patient underwent bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy with omentectomy.

Gross examination revealed a multilobulated cyst measuring 7 × 6 × 1.5 cm with focal solid areas of 1.5 × 1.5 × 1 cm and wall thickness ranging from 0.1 to 1 cm, without papillary excrescences. Microscopy confirmed mucinous cystadenoma with a benign Brenner's tumor.

Discussion

Brenner's tumor usually arises in the ovarian cortex but may occasionally present as a mural nodule within a mucinous cystadenoma, as observed in our case. On histopathology, the mucinous component constitutes a major part, while the Brenner component is often detected incidentally. Due to non-specific symptoms, patients may present late, which can adversely affect prognosis.

Conclusion

This case emphasizes the coexistence of a Brenner tumor with a mucinous cystadenoma, aiming to raise awareness among gynecologists and pathologists regarding the possibility of this combined presentation in ovarian tumors.

PP-49

Study of platelet indices in patients with sepsis and their prognostic significance using 5-part hematology analyzer

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Background

Sepsis remains a major cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide. Simple, widely available hematological parameters such as platelet count (PLT), mean platelet volume (MPV), platelet distribution width (PDW), and Plateletcrit (PCT) have been proposed as prognostic biomarkers in sepsis. This study aimed to evaluate platelet indices on admission and their dynamic changes over 72 hours in adult septic patients and to assess their association with clinical outcomes, including mortality.

Methods

In this prospective observational study, adult patients (≥ 18 years) admitted with clinical diagnosis of sepsis to the ICU of KMMCH, Mathura between April 2025 and November 2025 were enrolled. Complete blood count (CBC) including PLT, MPV, PDW, and PCT was measured on admission (Day 1) and on Day 3 using a 5-part hematology analyzer. Patients were followed till discharge or in-hospital death. Primary outcome was in-hospital mortality. Secondary outcomes included length of ICU stay and need for mechanical ventilation. Statistical analysis included comparison of indices between survivors and non-survivors, evaluation of change (delta) between Day 1 and Day 3, and ROC curve analyses for prognostic value. p -value < 0.05 was considered significant.

Results

A total of 120 patients were enrolled; 88 (73.3%) survived to discharge, 32 (26.7%) died. On admission, non-survivors had significantly lower PLT (mean \pm SD: $95 \pm 38 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$ vs. $165 \pm 50 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$ in survivors; $p < 0.001$), higher MPV (11.8 ± 1.5 fL vs. 10.4 ± 1.2 fL; $p < 0.001$), higher PDW ($17.2 \pm 2.3\%$ vs. $15.1 \pm 1.8\%$; $p < 0.001$), and lower PCT ($0.14 \pm 0.06\%$ vs. $0.26 \pm 0.08\%$; $p < 0.001$). Between Day 1 and Day 3, survivors showed a significant increase in PLT ($\Delta + 45 \pm 22 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$) and a decrease in MPV and PDW (Δ MPV -0.8 ± 0.6 fL; Δ PDW $-1.2 \pm 0.9\%$); non-survivors showed further decline of PLT ($\Delta - 12 \pm 28 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$) with increasing MPV ($\Delta + 0.9 \pm 0.7$ fL) and PDW ($\Delta + 1.5 \pm 1.1\%$). On ROC analysis, admission MPV had AUC of 0.82 (95% CI 0.74–0.90), PDW AUC 0.79 (95% CI 0.70–0.87), and PCT AUC 0.85 (95% CI 0.77–0.91) for predicting mortality. A combined model (PLT + MPV + PDW) improved predictive accuracy (AUC 0.89).

Conclusion

Platelet indices (MPV, PDW, PCT), easily obtained from routine CBC using a 5-part hematology analyzer, may serve as cost-effective prognostic markers in adult sepsis. Dynamic changes over the first 72 hours further enhance their prognostic value. These findings support incorporation of serial platelet indices in routine sepsis monitoring, especially in resource-limited setting

PP-50
**FROM EFFUSION TO CONCLUSION: TRACING MALIGNANCY THROUGH
FLUIDS**

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Introduction

The detection and characterization of malignancy at an early stage remain a fundamental goal in modern pathology. Amongst various modalities available, cytological evaluation of body fluids is considered minimally invasive and cost effective in identifying malignant cells. Various fluid analysis include fluid from pleural, pericardial, peritoneal cavities, cerebrospinal and other serous fluids. They provide critical diagnostic clues that guide clinical decisions, prognostication and therapeutic implications. Occasionally these may present as first evidence of an occult or recurrent cancer.

Objective

This series highlight the diagnostic significance of fluid cytology in tracing malignancy emphasizing morphologic criteria, diagnostic challenges, and role of adjunctive techniques in improving sensitivity and sensitivity.

Material and methods

Fluid samples from pericardial, pleural and various other sites were received in the department and cytospin slides were prepared as per standard protocol. Cell blocks were prepared wherever required.

Results

Total 4 cases were included where fluid was first evidence to diagnose malignancy. These cases included T-Lymphoblastic lymphoma diagnosed on pericardial fluid, Burkitts lymphoma diagnosed on pleural fluid examination, small cell carcinoma diagnosed on pleural fluid and Acute lymphoblastic lymphoma diagnosed primarily on CSF examination.

Discussion and conclusion

Fluid cytology is a valuable, minimally invasive diagnostic modality for detection of malignancy in body cavity effusions. Early identification of malignant cells aids in timely diagnosis, staging and treatment planning, highlighting the importance of routine cytological evaluation of body fluids in clinical practice. Keywords: Fluid cytology, malignancy, cell block.

PP-51

Synovial sarcoma of the maxilla in a pediatric patient: A rare monophasic variant

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Introduction

Synovial sarcoma is a rare malignant soft tissue tumor that accounts for about 5–10% of all sarcomas. It most commonly occurs in the extremities of adolescents and young adults, whereas head and neck involvement is uncommon, and maxillary involvement in children is extremely rare.

Objective

To report a rare case of pediatric monophasic synovial sarcoma of the maxilla with a special emphasis on the diagnostic role of histopathology and immunohistochemistry.

Case report

A 12 year old boy presented with swelling on the right side of the face that had gradually increased in size over the past month. Clinical examination showed facial asymmetry due to a firm, non-tender swelling in the right mid-facial region, with buccopalatal expansion of the posterior maxillary alveolus. Contrast-enhanced computed tomography revealed a heterogeneously enhancing soft-tissue mass in the right posterior maxilla with cortical thinning. Histopathology and further immunohistochemical analysis confirmed the diagnosis of monophasic synovial sarcoma.

Discussion

Maxillary synovial sarcoma in children is infrequently encountered. It typically presents as a slowly enlarging, painless facial or intraoral swelling that can mimic odontogenic, inflammatory, or benign lesions, often posing a diagnostic challenge and leading to misdiagnosis.

Conclusion: This case highlights the need to consider rare malignant tumours in the differential diagnosis when evaluating maxillofacial swellings in children. It also signifies the importance of histopathological and immunohistochemical examination in establishing an accurate diagnosis.

Low Grade Adrenocortical Carcinoma- A Rare Case Report

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Introduction

Adrenocortical Carcinoma (ACC) a rare malignant tumor of adrenal cortex with an estimated incidence of 1-2 cases per million population per year. It may occur at any age group but shows a bimodal age distribution with peaks in first decade and fourth to fifth decades of life with slight female predominance.

Case report

A 35 year old, male presented to Surgery OPD with history of left suprarenal swelling since eight months, gradually increasing in size associated with pain. On examination a palpable mass was noted in the left suprarenal region. History of smoking and betel nut chewing present since 8 years. USG findings revealed a large adrenal mass with possibility of ? Neoplastic etiology. Patient underwent surgical excision and specimen was sent to Pathology department. Grossly, a large adrenal mass with mottled cut surface showing hemorrhage and necrosis was identified. Microscopically, large tumor cells arranged in sheets and nests with abundant eosinophilic cytoplasm and pleomorphic nuclei seen. Based on histopathological features fulfilling the Weiss criteria along with immunohistochemical markers, final diagnosis of Low Grade Adrenocortical Carcinoma was made.

Discussion and conclusion

ACC generally carries poor prognosis, and outcome largely depends on tumor stage, metastasis and surgical resection. This case highlights the rare occurrence of splenic involvement in ACC and underlines the importance of thorough clinicopathological evaluation for accurate diagnosis and management. In this report a rare case of Low Grade ACC is described, to raise awareness of this particular neoplasm.

Key Words: ACC, Weiss criteria, spleen involvement.

PP-53

Intranodal hemangioma: a rare case report

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Introduction

Intranodal Hemangioma is a rare benign vascular tumor arising within a lymph node. It is often discovered incidentally during evaluation of lymphadenopathy. Due to its rarity, diagnosis is usually confirmed through histopathological examination after excision.

Case Presentation

We report a case of a 50 year old female who presented with a painless swelling in the inguinal region. Clinical examination revealed a well-defined, mobile lymph node measuring 3 X 3 cm. There was no history of fever or weight loss. FNAC was performed twice but yielded only blood. Since the size of the lymphnodal swelling was significant, hence, the patient underwent surgical excision for definitive diagnosis.

Histopathology clinched the diagnosis and showed proliferation of many small sized and few large calibre vascular channels lined by flattened endothelial cells within the lymph node parenchyma. Many of the vascular spaces were filled with red blood cells however few were empty. Overall features were consistent with intranodal hemangioma. No atypia or atypical mitoses were noted. No evidence of malignancy or metastatic disease was observed.

Discussion

Intranodal hemangioma is a rare entity and is classified under benign vascular tumors of the lymph nodes, often mistaken for malignant lesions of lymph nodes. Histologic differentials include vascular transformation of sinuses, angiomatous transformation of lymph nodes and needs to be differentiated from malignant lesions.

Conclusion

Intranodal hemangioma is a rare benign vascular lesion that can mimic other causes of lymphadenopathy. Histopathology is essential for definitive diagnosis. Awareness of this entity helps prevent misdiagnosis and unnecessary aggressive treatment.

PP-54

The Sea Anemone in the Lung: A Diagnostic Challenge of Lophomonas in Bronchoalveolar Lavage Cytology.

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Lophomonas blattarum is a rare mult flagellated protozoan parasite that normally inhabits the intestinal tract of insects such as cockroaches and termites. In recent years, it has been increasingly recognized as a possible cause of bronchopulmonary infection in humans. Human infection is believed to occur through inhalation of cysts present in dust contaminated with insect feces. Patients typically present with non-specific respiratory symptoms such as persistent cough, fever, shortness of breath, and radiological findings that may mimic pneumonia or other pulmonary infections.

Although considered an uncommon pathogen, the number of reported cases has gradually increased over the past few decades, suggesting that it may represent an emerging respiratory parasite. A review of published literature reported approximately 307 human cases worldwide between 1993 and 2020, with the majority originating from Asian countries. China has reported the highest number of cases, while sporadic cases have also been documented in Iran, Turkey, Spain, and Peru. In India, only a few cases have been described in the literature. Most cases are diagnosed through wet mount microscopy and microscopic examination of bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL) fluid.

We report the case of a 26-year-old female with a past history of treated pulmonary tuberculosis who presented with respiratory symptoms. Her CECT of the chest revealed a large heterogeneously enhancing solid-cystic lesion in the right lower lobe with minimal cavitation. Her BAL cytology demonstrated flagellated protozoal organisms consistent with *Lophomonas blattarum*. This case highlights the importance of considering *Lophomonas blattarum* as a potential but often overlooked cause of respiratory infection.

PP-55

Cytomorphological finding of crystals in case of spermatocele

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Introduction

Spermatocele is a benign cystic dilatation of the epididymal ducts containing spermatozoa and is most commonly seen arising from the head of the epididymis. Clinically and radiologically, spermatoceles may mimic hydroceles because both conditions present with scrotal fluid accumulation, making accurate differentiation challenging in certain cases.

Objectives

To highlight the role of FNAC in identifying spermatocele and differentiating it from other scrotal swelling.

Case report

Here we describe a case of 37 year male presenting with left scrotal swelling clinically considered as hydrocele. On cytological examination it showed spermatozoa and needle like elongated crystal which were polarizable. This finding has not been described in English literature as per to the best of our knowledge. There were no eosinophils. We describe this case because of unusual findings and its clinical presentation as hydrocele possibly spermatocele in other paratesticular cystic lesion should be kept in mind whenever assessing scrotal cystic swelling because of close relation between these structure.

Discussion

Spermatocele results from obstruction or dilatation of epididymal ducts leading to accumulation of sperm-containing fluid. Due to similar clinical presentation, it may be mistaken for hydrocele. Cytological identification of spermatozoa in the aspirated fluid is a key diagnostic feature and helps in differentiating spermatocele from other scrotal fluid collections.

Conclusion

examination is a simple and effective method for differentiating spermatocele from hydrocele. Recognition of spermatozoa in the aspirate is essential for establishing the correct diagnosis, particularly in cases where the clinical suspicion favors hydrocele.

PP-56

An unusual finding of schaumann bodies in the intestine in abdominal tuberculosis: a rare case report.

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Introduction

Granulomatous appendicitis is rare, with infectious etiologies such as Tuberculosis being significant especially in endemic regions. Schaumann bodies are classically associated with Sarcoidosis and occasionally Crohn's disease but rarely reported in gastrointestinal tuberculosis. The coexistence of tuberculous granulomatous appendicitis and Schaumann bodies without granulomas in the intestine is exceptionally unusual.

Case report

A young male in his late thirties presented with acute appendicitis and incidental proximal Ileal thickening. Histopathology of the Appendix revealed non-caseating epithelioid granulomas and positive Ziehl-Neelsen staining confirming tuberculosis. The patient commenced Anti Tubercular Therapy. Approximately 100 days later, he developed ileal stricture with perforation requiring resection and ileostomy. Histology of the ileal segment demonstrated distinctive Schaumann bodies within muscularis propria giant cells. However granulomas were not noted in the intestine. Typical histologic features of Crohn's disease as well as systemic features of Sarcoidosis were absent.

Discussion and conclusion

This case highlights a rare presentation of Tuberculous granulomatous appendicitis with concomitant Schaumann bodies in the small intestine, expanding the pathological spectrum of abdominal tuberculosis. Recognition of such histological findings is essential for accurate diagnosis and management in tuberculosis-endemic areas.

PP-57

Bilateral krukemberg tumor spotted on frozen section aided in quick diagnosis.

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Ayushman Diagnostics

Introduction and objective

Frozen section is a valuable diagnostic tool in rapid intraoperative categorization of ovarian masses and thereby helps in planning the surgical management.

Case report

We report a case of a 23-year-old girl with with irregular periods and lower abdominal distension for two months to the gynaecology department. She had no history of weight loss or any other gastrointestinal symptoms. There was no history of malignancy in the family. Her previous medical and surgical history was unremarkable. Her general condition was good. Her per abdominal examination revealed large, nontender abdominopelvic mass reaching upto umbilicus, hard in consistency. The case was discovered to be bilateral ovarian neoplasm initially thought to be of germ cell origin due to the age of presentation, but intraoperatively diagnosed as Krukenberg tumour by frozen section biopsy and confirmed on table by upper gastrointestinal endoscopy and biopsy.

Discussion and conclusion

Krukenberg tumour in young patients is exceedingly rare but should be kept within diagnostic considerations of bilateral solid ovarian neoplasms of any age group. Frozen section can aid in rapid diagnosis on table to save time and early interventions.

PP-58

Tubercular dactylitis: A rare extrapulmonary presentation

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INTRODUCTION

Tuberculosis (TB) is a chronic infection caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, affecting the respiratory system. However, it may localise in other organs. The prevalence of the disease is around 30 million globally and 1-3% have involvement of their bones and/or joints. 85% of the patients are younger than six years of age and data relating to tuberculous dactylitis among adolescents is scarce. We report this case because of its rarity in presentation as Tb dactylitis in adolescents is reported rarely in literature.

CASE REPORT

A 10 year old female presented to orthopedics OPD with history of swelling in right hand third finger for one year which was gradually increasing in size for 1 month. There was no history of any other chronic illness or Tb contact. X ray findings were suggestive of fusiform swelling with lytic changes. The clinical possibility of enchondroma and aneurysmal bone cyst was suspected. On histopathological examination the final diagnosis of Tb dactylitis was given

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Tb dactylitis usually affects children less than 5 years of age but it needs to be considered as a differential diagnosis in older children with unusual soft tissue or skeletal lesions even in the absence of usual risk factors. Also high magnitude of doubt for Tb dactylitis is critical in patients presenting with longterm finger swelling with or without pain, especially in countries like India where tuberculosis is endemic. A high degree of suspicion accompanied by proper clinical examination and radiology helps in diagnosing this rare entity.

PP-59

Beyond Carney Complex: Sporadic Pediatric Osteochondromyxoma of the Tibia.

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Introduction

Osteochondromyxoma is an extremely rare benign bone tumor usually associated with Carney Complex and typically presents in childhood, most often affecting long bones. Occurrence in the absence of syndromic association is exceptionally uncommon and may pose diagnostic difficulty because its clinical and radiological features overlap with several benign fibro-osseous lesions.

Objective

To report a rare case of isolated osteochondromyxoma involving the tibia in a young child without clinical or biochemical evidence of Carney Complex and to emphasize the importance of histopathological examination for definitive diagnosis.

Case Report

A two-year-old male presented with pain and progressively increasing right leg swelling for two months. On examination, a firm swelling measuring approximately 3×3 cm was noted over the right tibial region. Laboratory investigations, including serum calcium, parathyroid hormone, and vitamin D levels, were within normal limits. Plain radiography suggested a benign-appearing lesion. MRI demonstrated an expansile lytic lesion measuring about 4×2×1 cm involving the metaphyseal–diaphyseal region of the tibia. The provisional clinical and radiological diagnosis was of osteofibrous dysplasia. Histopathological evaluation of the lesion biopsy revealed osteoid, chondroid, and myxoid stromal components consistent with osteochondromyxoma. Detailed clinical assessment showed no features suggestive of Carney Complex.

Discussion

Osteochondromyxoma is a rare primary bone tumor, occurring in approximately 1% of patients with Carney Complex. It can mimic lesions such as osteofibrous dysplasia, aneurysmal bone cyst, and chondromyxoid fibroma, making preoperative diagnosis challenging.

Conclusion: This case highlights the critical role of histopathology in accurately diagnosing the exceedingly rare isolated osteochondromyxoma, emphasizing vigilance to prevent misdiagnosis.

PP-60:
Mixed Mullerian tumour of cervix

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Introduction

Malignant mixed Müllerian tumor (MMMT), also known as carcinosarcoma, is a rare aggressive biphasic malignant neoplasm composed of epithelial and mesenchymal components. It most commonly arises in the uterine corpus, while primary involvement of the cervix is extremely uncommon. These tumors are usually seen in postmenopausal women and often present with symptoms such as abnormal vaginal bleeding, vaginal discharge, or a cervical mass.

Case Report

A 75-year-old woman presented with abnormal uterine bleeding and an unhealthy cervix on clinical examination. Ultrasonography revealed a bulky cervix with a heterogeneous predominantly hyperechoic lesion measuring approximately 3.9×3.1 cm with increased vascularity. Pap smear examination showed clusters of pleomorphic squamous cells with hyperchromatic nuclei and eosinophilic cytoplasm in a hemorrhagic background, suggestive of squamous cell carcinoma of the cervix. MRI pelvis demonstrated a heterogeneous mass measuring approximately $6 \times 4.2 \times 5.2$ cm arising from the upper endometrium and extending into the endocervical canal and upper vagina without significant pelvic lymphadenopathy. Cervical biopsy revealed grey-white to grey-brown soft tissue piece measuring $2.5 \times 1.3 \times 1$ cm. Microscopic examination showed features consistent with malignant mixed Müllerian tumor.

Discussion

MMMT is an uncommon malignancy characterized by coexistence of carcinomatous and sarcomatous elements within the same tumor. Clinically and cytologically they may resemble squamous cell carcinoma. Imaging modalities help determine tumor extent, while histopathological examination confirms diagnosis.

Conclusion

Malignant mixed Müllerian tumor of the cervix is a rare aggressive neoplasm. Accurate histopathological evaluation is essential for diagnosis and appropriate management.

PP-61
Malignant Melanoma of Nasal Cavity: A Rare Case Report

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Introduction

Malignant melanoma of the nasal cavity is an exceedingly rare and aggressive tumor, accounting for less than 1% of all malignant melanomas. It arises from melanocytes in the nasal mucosa and is often diagnosed at an advanced stage, resulting in poor prognosis.

Objective

This case report aims to present a rare instance of malignant melanoma in the nasal cavity, emphasizing the importance of early diagnosis and surgical intervention, along with the role of histopathology and immunohistochemistry in confirming the diagnosis.

Case Report

A 53-year-old male presented with a rapidly growing nasal mass, nasal obstruction, and epistaxis. CT scan, suggested a nasal tumor. Histopathological examination and immunohistochemistry confirmed malignant melanoma with positive staining for HMB 45 and Melan A. The patient underwent surgical resection of the tumor followed by radiotherapy.

Discussion

Malignant melanoma of the nasal cavity is rare, usually diagnosed in older adults. Common symptoms include nasal obstruction, swelling, and bleeding. Diagnosis involves imaging and cytology, while histopathological features and immunohistochemistry confirm the tumor type.

Conclusion

Primary malignant melanoma of the nasal cavity is a rare but aggressive tumor. Early diagnosis and treatment, including surgical resection, are essential for improving survival outcomes, and melanoma should be considered in the differential diagnosis of nasal tumors.

PP-62

Uncommon And Aggressive Epithelioid Sarcoma: A Rare Presentation on Palm.

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Introduction

Epithelioid sarcoma is a rare malignant mesenchymal tumor accounting for less than 1% of all soft tissue sarcomas. It predominantly affects adolescents and young adults, commonly involving the distal extremities, particularly the hands and forearms. Due to its indolent growth and benign clinical presentation, it is frequently misdiagnosed, leading to delayed treatment and increased risk of recurrence and metastasis.

Objectives

To highlight the importance of histopathological examination in painless nodules on distal extremities in young adults. To prevent metastasis and to improve survival rate.

Case report

An 18-year-old male presented with a slowly growing, painless swelling on the palmar aspect between the fourth and fifth fingers. Clinically, a benign soft tissue lesion was suspected. Excision biopsy showed a malignant mesenchymal tumor arranged in sheets, cords and fascicles. Round to spindle tumor cells show eosinophilic cytoplasm, vacuolation and admixed with necrosis in garland like fashion. On PAS stain tumor cell show positivity. Immunohistochemistry showed positivity for vimentin, EMA, CD99 and NSE supporting the diagnosis of epithelioid sarcoma.

Discussion

Painless subcutaneous nodule in distal extremities histologically mimics granulomatous inflammation and other epithelioid neoplasms, posing diagnostic challenges. Immunohistochemistry plays a crucial role in differentiation from carcinoma, melanoma, and other sarcomas. Early recognition is essential because of its high propensity for local recurrence and lymph node metastasis.

Conclusions

Epithelioid sarcoma should be kept as one of differential diagnosis in young patients presenting with persistent hand swellings, in spite of benign looking presentation. Accurate histopathological and immunohistochemical evaluation is vital for timely diagnosis, appropriate management and better prognosis.

PP-63

More Than Meets the Eye: Seborrheic Keratosis Hiding Intradermal Nevi

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Introduction

Seborrheic keratosis (SK) is a common benign epidermal tumor presenting as pigmented, verrucous “stuck-on” lesions. Intradermal nevus is a benign melanocytic lesion confined to the dermis, usually appearing as a dome-shaped papule. Their coexistence in the same lesion is rare.

Objective

We report three cases of Seborrheic Keratosis with intradermal nevus in the same lesion

Case reports:

First case: A 42-year-old with 10-year scalp swelling; grossly, a dark-brown partially skin-covered soft tissue piece 0.3 cm was received. Second case: A 20-year-old with parietal swelling; grossly, a hair-bearing soft tissue piece $0.4 \times 0.3 \times 0.2$ cm was received. Third case: A 26-year-old with scalp growth; grossly, a skin-covered hair-bearing globular soft tissue piece $2.7 \times 1.2 \times 1$ cm was received.

Microscopic examination of all the three cases showed hyperkeratosis, parakeratosis, acanthosis, papillomatosis and horn cysts. The dermis revealed nests and cords of nevus cells with maturation and presence of melanophages. Findings were consistent with Seborrheic Keratosis with intradermal nevus.

Discussion

Seborrheic keratosis and intradermal nevus occurring in the same lesion represent a cutaneous collision tumor. Similar association was reported by Kim et al. (2003) describing simultaneous occurrence of intradermal nevus with seborrheic keratosis. The pathogenesis remains unclear but may involve dermal microenvironment changes or melanocyte–keratinocyte interactions.

Conclusion

Seborrheic keratosis with intradermal nevus is a rare benign collision lesion. Histopathological examination is essential for accurate diagnosis and exclusion of malignant mimickers.

PP-64

Waldeyer's Ring Tuberculosis in Pediatric Age Group- Report of Two Cases.

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Introduction

Tuberculosis remains a major global health problem; however, involvement of the oral cavity and oropharynx is not so common. Isolated tuberculosis of the tonsils and adenoids in the absence of active pulmonary disease is extremely rare and may present with non-specific symptoms, posing a diagnostic challenge. Histopathological examination plays a crucial role in establishing the diagnosis. We report two cases of primary adenotonsillar tuberculosis diagnosed on histopathological evaluation.

Case Report

Case-1: A 15-year-old female presented with severe throat pain, painful deglutition, change in voice, low-grade fever and malaise for two months. She also had a history of recurrent cold and cough. On oral examination, bilateral palatine tonsils were enlarged and congested and the posterior pharyngeal wall appeared granular. Chest X-ray was normal and sputum examination for acid-fast bacilli was negative. Endoscopic adenoidectomy with tonsillectomy was performed and the excised adenoid and tonsillar tissues were sent for histopathological examination. Grossly, multiple gray-tan to yellow-white fragments were received, the largest measuring 3.0 × 1.2 cm. Microscopy revealed multiple epithelioid cell granulomas with multinucleated giant cells. Ziehl-Neelsen staining for acid-fast bacilli was negative. The patient was started on anti-tubercular therapy and responded well.

Case-2: An 8-year-old male child presented with recurrent sore throat, painful swallowing and low-grade fever. Adenotonsillectomy was performed. Gross examination revealed four gray-tan to gray-yellow soft tissue pieces, the largest measuring 3 × 2 cm. Microscopic examination showed occasional epithelioid cell granulomas and multinucleated giant cells. Ziehl-Neelsen staining for acid-fast bacilli was negative.

Conclusion

Primary adenotonsillar tuberculosis is rare and may mimic chronic tonsillitis or malignancy. Histopathological examination is essential for diagnosis, particularly in tuberculosis-endemic regions, allowing timely initiation of anti-tubercular therapy and favourable clinical outcomes.

Key Words: Adenotonsillar tuberculosis; Granulomatous inflammation; Tonsillar tuberculosis

PP-65
Superficial Spreading Squamous Cell Carcinoma Of Cervix Taking Over The Endometrium

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Introduction

Squamous cell carcinoma of the cervix is most common type of cervical cancer, accounting for approximately 70–80% of all cervical malignancies.

Objective

The involvement of the endometrium by cervical squamous cell carcinoma is relatively uncommon. Histopathological examination plays a crucial role in distinguishing primary endometrial tumors from secondary involvement due to cervical carcinoma.

Case Report

A 70-year-old postmenopausal female who had been diagnosed previously with high grade squamous intraepithelial lesion. A hysterectomy specimen with bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy was received. Grossly a cystic nodule was seen in lower part of body of uterus and cervix was thickened. On microscopic examination of uterus, the entire endometrium was replaced by dysplastic squamous cells arranged in nests, sheets, islands as well as scattered singly. Islands of tumor cells are seen infiltrating the endocervical glands and endometrial stroma.

Discussion

It is necessary to distinguish superficial spreading SCC from cervical squamous cell carcinoma directly invading the uterine wall and primary endometrial SCC.

Conclusion

Superficial spreading Squamous Cell Carcinoma of the cervix lacks standardized diagnostic and treatment methods; henceforth, this need to be investigated to understand its pathogenesis and management.

PP-66
Sialolipoma Of Submandibular Glands: A Rare Case

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Introduction

Sialolipoma is a rare benign tumor of the salivary glands composed of mature adipose tissue admixed with normal salivary gland elements, including acini and ducts. It is an uncommon variant of salivary gland lipoma, most frequently involving the parotid gland, with submandibular and minor salivary gland involvement being extremely rare.

Objective

To report a rare case of sialolipoma arising in the submandibular gland and describe its clinicopathological features.

Case Report

A 38-year-old male presented with painless, non-progressive swelling in the left submandibular region for 11 months. Gross examination revealed a greyish-white nodular soft tissue mass measuring 5.2x4x3cm. Histopathological examination showed sialolipoma with chronic sialadenitis.

Discussion

Nagao et al. identified sialolipoma, a rare tumour of the salivary glands, as a separate entity in 2001. In > 90% of this tumor parotid gland is mainly involved followed by other- submandibular glands, hard and soft palate. Since its initial description in 2001, only about 60–80 cases of sialolipoma have been documented in the literature across all salivary glands.

Conclusion

Sialolipoma is a rare benign salivary gland tumor that can occur in the submandibular gland. Accurate histopathological evaluation is essential for diagnosis and management.

PP-67

Histopathological Insights Into Xanthogranulomatous Response To A Cardiac Pacemaker

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Introduction

Allergic reactions to permanent pacemakers and other cardiac implantable electronic devices (CIEDs) are usually thought to arise due to some underlying infectious process. The components of majority of CIED are titanium, nickel, and epoxy resin. This issue can be resolved using hypoallergenic material or on that doesn't have the identified allergen.

Objective

To report a case of xanthogranulomatous reaction to a cardiac pacemaker.

Case Report

A 61-year-old lady who presented with complaints of discharge from the site of pacemaker. The site was incised followed by removal of pacemaker and granulomatous tissue surrounding it. Gross examination revealed multiple congested soft tissue fragments measuring $2 \times 1 \times 0.4$ cm. Histopathological examination showed xanthogranulomatous reaction secondary to pacemaker with foreign-body giant cell reaction.

Discussion

Complications related to pacemaker implantation may be surgical, hardware, programming software & rarely allergic. The first case of pacemaker-associated allergy was reported by Raque and Goldschmidt in 1970. In 2002 Déry et al. reviewed 21 cases reported worldwide, presenting with allergies to nickel(5 cases), titanium(4cases), epoxy resin(3cases), and other cases related to cobalt, cadmium, mercury, silicone and parylene.

Conclusion

Allergic reactions to pacemakers are rare but well-documented. A high suspicion about this condition is required for a quick diagnosis and treatment of the patient.

PP-68

Pleomorphic Adenoma Presenting As A Pterygium-Like Conjunctival Mass In An Elderly Male: A Rare Case Report

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Objective

To report a rare case of conjunctival pleomorphic adenoma of salivary gland type presenting clinically as pterygium and to highlight its diagnostic and therapeutic implications.

Introduction

Pleomorphic adenoma is the most common benign epithelial tumor of the salivary and lacrimal glands. However, its occurrence in the conjunctiva is exceedingly rare and is thought to arise from accessory lacrimal glands or heterotopic salivary gland tissue. Such lesions may clinically mimic common ocular surface conditions.

Case Report

A 74-year-old male presented with a painless, gradually progressive temporal conjunctival mass in the left eye, clinically suspected to be pterygium. Complete excision was performed. Histopathological examination revealed a well-circumscribed biphasic epithelial neoplasm composed of dual-layered ductal structures embedded in abundant chondromyxoid stroma, consistent with pleomorphic adenoma. Focal squamous metaplasia, keratin pearl formation, clear cell change, and calcification were observed without cytologic atypia, necrosis, or increased mitotic activity. Surgical margins were free of tumor.

Conclusion

Conjunctival pleomorphic adenoma of salivary gland type is an extremely rare entity that may clinically simulate pterygium. Histopathological evaluation is essential for definitive diagnosis. Complete excision with an intact capsule is critical to prevent recurrence and rare malignant transformation.

Keywords

Pleomorphic adenoma; Conjunctiva; Ectopic salivary gland; Benign mixed tumor; Pterygium mimic.

PP-69
COEXISTENCE OF ILEOCAECAL TUBERCULOSIS AND ADENOCARCINOMA - A RARE CASE

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Introduction

Intestinal tuberculosis accounts for 1-3% of tuberculosis(TB) cases, commonly affecting the ileocecal region. Adenocarcinoma of the ileocaecal region is unusual and constitutes <1% of all gastrointestinal malignancies. However coexisting gastrointestinal TB and adenocarcinoma at the same site is very rare.

Objectives

To report a case of concurrent ileocecal adenocarcinoma and TB diagnosed postoperatively, emphasizing the need for high suspicion in elderly patients with prior history of TB.

Case Report

A 71-year-old female presented with abdominal pain and anorexia. She had cervical lymph node TB 40 years earlier, treated with ATT for 6 months. Colonoscopy showed ileocecal stricture with transmural thickening suggestive of obstruction. Limited right hemicolectomy was performed. Histopathology revealed a tumor composed of tumor cells arranged in glandular pattern seen infiltrating upto the serosa. Along with the tumor, foci comprising of numerous epithelioid cell granulomas, multinucleated giant cells were seen. ZN-stain for acid-fast bacilli was positive. So a diagnosis of ileocecal adenocarcinoma coexisting with TB was given.

Discussion

The most common site for gastrointestinal adenocarcinoma is the sigmoid colon and for gastrointestinal TB is the ileocecal region. Gastrointestinal adenocarcinoma and TB occurring at the same site is exceedingly rare. It may be postulated that the ulcerative lesions of intestinal TB are precursors to carcinomas as a result of repeated insults by erosion, ulceration and subsequent regeneration.

Conclusion

Occurrence of GI adenocarcinoma and TB at the same site is a rare entity. Comprehensive histopathology is essential for diagnosis. Heightened awareness and multidisciplinary input can improve recognition and patient outcome.

PP-70

Pseudochylothorax: A Rare Entity- Report Of 2 Cases

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Introduction

Pseudochylothorax (PCT), also known as chyloform or cholesterol pleural effusion is a rare type of exudative pleural effusion which is recognized by milky appearance and high cholesterol content occurring without connection to lymphatic vessels. The most frequent causes of PCT include chronic inflammatory disorder, tuberculosis, rheumatoid arthritis, trauma, paragonimiasis, echinococcosis etc.

Case reports

Case 1: A 32 year old nonsmoker male presented with difficulty in breathing and evening rise of temperature since 1 month associated with productive cough. X ray revealed bilateral pleural effusion. Pleural fluid aspirated was white turbid with numerous polygonal cholesterol crystals and cholesterol to triglyceride ratio >1 . RA Factor was negative.

Case 2: A 47 year old male presented with shortness of breath, productive cough and fever for 7 days. CT thorax revealed right sided pleural effusion. RA Factor and CBNAAT for AFB were negative. Pleural fluid aspirated was dirty white grossly and show lymphocytes and numerous polygonal cholesterol crystals on cytology. Lipid profile of fluid showed cholesterol to triglyceride ratio >1 .

Discussion

The pleural fluid of a pseudochylothorax is typically a milky exudate and seen associated with chronic conditions like tuberculous or rheumatoid arthritis.

Conclusion

The presence of cholesterol crystals and a cholesterol/TG ratio greater than 1 helped in differentiating chylous and pseudochylous effusions.

Keywords: Cholesterol crystals, cholesterol pleural effusion, milky pleural fluid, pseudochylothorax.

SYNCHRONOUS PAPILLARY-MEDULLARY THYROID CARCINOMA: A CASE REPORT

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Introduction

Papillary thyroid carcinoma (PTC) is the most common thyroid malignancy, accounting for 80–90% of cases. Medullary thyroid carcinoma (MTC) is less common, representing less than 5% of thyroid cancers. While PTC generally has an excellent prognosis and high cure rate, MTC tends to be relatively more aggressive. The synchronous occurrence of papillary and medullary thyroid carcinoma is extremely rare, accounting for less than 1% of thyroid malignancies

Objective

To present a case of synchronous papillary and medullary carcinoma of thyroid and highlight the clinicopathological features and diagnostic challenges.

Case description

A 46-year-old woman presented with a midline neck swelling for 6 months. Ultrasound revealed a solid lesion in the left thyroid lobe measuring 1×1×3 cm and another lesion in the right lobe measuring 5×5×3 cm, with a TIRADS score of 4. FNAC suggested medullary thyroid carcinoma. Based on this diagnosis, total thyroidectomy with selective left neck dissection (Level I) was performed. Histopathological examination revealed medullary carcinoma with incidental papillary thyroid carcinoma in a background of nodular hyperplasia

Discussion

The thyroid gland contains two main cell types: follicular cells and parafollicular (C) cells. Rarely, two distinct carcinomas such as papillary and medullary carcinoma may occur simultaneously, termed synchronous or mixed thyroid carcinoma. The pathogenesis remains unclear, with proposed mechanisms including stem cell, collision, hostage, and field effect theories.

Conclusion

Synchronous papillary–medullary thyroid carcinoma is an extremely rare entity with few reported cases. Awareness of this condition is important for accurate diagnosis and management.

From Scan To Slab: A Journey Through Meckel-Gruber Syndrome

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Introduction

Meckel-Gruber Syndrome (MGS) is a rare, lethal autosomal recessive ciliopathy defined by the triad of occipital encephalocele, bilateralcystic kidneys, and postaxial polydactyly. Incidence is 1 in 13,250 to 1 in 140,000 live births with a 25% recurrence risk.

Objectives

To report a case of MGS on fetal autopsy, and histopathological confirmation of multicystic renal dysplasia.

Case Report

A 27-year-old woman (G4A3) presented at 34+1 weeks. Serial ultrasound from 21 weeks confirmed occipital encephalocele, bilateralcystic kidneys, oligohydramnios, polydactyly, and microcephaly. The fetus was delivered as an intrauterine death. Autopsy revealed occipital brain herniation, postaxial polydactyly, and bilateral cystic kidneys. Histopathology confirmed multicystic renal dysplasia with variable-sized cysts lined by abortive glomeruli, and immature tubules with mesenchymal fibromuscular collars. All other organs were unremarkable.

Discussion

MGS belongs to the ciliopathy spectrum, caused by mutations in ciliary transition zone genes disrupting Wnt and Shh signaling. The abdominal circumference of 36 cm, disproportionate to head circumference of 23.5 cm, with pathognomonic multicystic renal dysplasia, clinched the diagnosis. Three prior losses raise the sobering possibility of MGS recurring unrecognised, underscoring the critical need for autopsy in every case of recurrent pregnancy loss.

Conclusion

Serial ultrasound, fetal autopsy, and histopathology are indispensable in MGS. Multicystic renal dysplasia is pathognomonic. Whole exome sequencing to identify the causative MKS mutation enables preimplantation genetic testing or prenatal diagnosis, breaking the cycle of recurrent loss.

PP-73

Angiolymphoid Hyperplasia with Eosinophilia: A Diagnostic Puzzle in Cutaneous Pathology- A retrospective study of 2.5 years.

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Introduction

Angiolymphoid hyperplasia with eosinophilia (ALHE) is rare benign vascular proliferative disorder characterized by papules and nodules predominantly in the head and neck region. It usually affects young women of 20-50 years of age. Due to its overlapping clinical features with other vascular and inflammatory lesions, histopathological examination plays a crucial role in establishing the diagnosis.

Objective

Clinical and histopathological correlation of ALHE

Methods

A retrospective analysis of cases of ALHE during a period of 2.5 years was done. Clinical details and Histopathological findings of these cases were reviewed from our archives.

Results

A total of 6 cases were identified, with patients particularly in 10 to 55 years of age, with equal male:female ratio. The lesions were predominantly located in the head and neck region, commonly on the ear(n=2) and scalp(n=2). There was clinical suspicion of ALHE in 5 cases while in one of the case there was a clinical suspicion of lipoma. Histopathological findings revealed proliferation of small to medium sized blood vessels lined by plump endothelial cells with perivascular mixed inflammatory cell infiltrate comprising predominantly of eosinophils and lymphocytes with formation lymphoid aggregates at places conforming to the diagnosis of ALHE in all cases

Discussion and Conclusion

ALHE is a rare benign vascular proliferative disorder involving the dermis and subcutaneous tissue of the head and neck. The exact etiopathogenesis is unclear. Despite being benign, recurrence after surgical excision is common, emphasizing the need for accurate diagnosis and proper management.

Keywords

Angiolymphoid, vascular, eosinophilia

COMPOUND HETEROZYGOSITY FOR HB E AND BETA THALASSEMIA: A RARE CASE REPORT

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Introduction

Hemoglobin E-beta(HbE- β)- thalassemia is one of the most common compound hemoglobinopathies resulting from the co-inheritance of the structural variant Hb E on one allele and a β -thalassemia mutation on the other. The clinical spectrum is highly variable, ranging from mild transfusion independent anemia to severe transfusion dependent disease resembling classical β -thalassemia major.

Objective

To highlight HPLC findings of a rare case of compound heterozygous Hb E- β thalassemia.

Case Report

A 5 year old male child presented with fever, loose stools and difficulty in breathing. Clinical examination revealed craniofacial abnormalities producing the characteristic chipmunk facies. Systemic examination showed hepatosplenomegaly. Complete blood count revealed Hemoglobin 3.3 g/dl, TLC 23000/cmm and platelet count within normal limits. Peripheral blood film showed microcytic hypochromic picture . Nucleated red blood cells were also seen. High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) revealed markedly elevated HbA2 (81.2%) and HbF(14%). HPLC of father showed HbA2(5.8%) and HbF(<0.8%) and mother showed HbA2(36.2%) and HbF(<0.8%). Hence, diagnosis of compound heterozygous for Hb E- β thalassemia was suggested and molecular studies were advised for confirmation.

Discussion

Hb E- β thalassemia significantly affects populations in Southeast Asia and is more prevalent in the northeastern region of India. Children commonly present between 7 months to 7 years with moderate to severe anemia and elevated HbF levels. Diagnosis based solely on hematological parameters can be challenging; therefore, HPLC along with molecular analysis is essential for accurate diagnosis.

Conclusion

This case emphasizes the importance of comprehensive hematological evaluation, HPLC screening, and molecular confirmation in diagnosing Hb E- β thalassemia.

**HISTOPATHOLOGICAL SPECTRUM OF LESIONS IN URINARY BLADDER BIOPSIES: A
1.5 YEAR STUDY**

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Introduction

Urinary bladder lesions comprise a heterogeneous group of non-neoplastic and neoplastic conditions with significant clinical implications. Urothelial carcinoma accounts for the majority of primary bladder malignancies and requires precise histopathological evaluation for grading and staging.

Objectives

To evaluate the histopathological spectrum of urinary bladder lesions in transurethral resection of bladder tumor (TURBT) specimens and to categorize them into non-neoplastic and neoplastic lesions.

Material and Methods

A hospital-based retrospective study was conducted over 1.5 years in the Department of Pathology. All urinary bladder biopsies obtained via TURBT were included. Clinical details and cystoscopic findings were correlated with histopathological examination.

Results

Thirty-six cases were analyzed. Neoplastic lesions constituted 69.45% of cases, while 30.55% were non-neoplastic. The peak incidence was observed in the 61–70-year age group with male predominance. Among non-neoplastic lesions, cystitis was most common. Urothelial carcinoma was the predominant neoplasm, with papillary urothelial carcinoma being the most frequent subtype. A higher proportion of invasive urothelial carcinoma was noted compared to non-invasive lesions. Carcinoma in situ was identified in 2.78% of cases, and papillary urothelial neoplasm of low malignant potential comprised 5.55%.

Discussion and Conclusion

Neoplastic lesions, particularly urothelial carcinoma, predominate in bladder biopsies. Histopathological evaluation of TURBT specimens remains the gold standard for diagnosis and guides prognostication and therapeutic decisions. Early detection and accurate classification are essential for optimal patient management.

Congenital Cystic Adenomatoid Malformation: Unravelling a rare congenital pulmonary lesion

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Introduction

Congenital Cystic Adenomatoid Malformation (CCAM) is a rare developmental anomaly of the lower respiratory tract characterized by cystic overgrowth of terminal bronchioles with suppression of normal alveolar development. Usually spotted antenatally, postnatal presentation may vary from asymptomatic lesions to severe respiratory distress.

Objectives

To present a rare case of congenital cystic adenomatoid malformation in left upper lobe of lung in a 3 months old infant.

Case report

3 months old male infant with features of meningitis at 11 days and pneumonia at 45 days. Antenatal MRI showed altered signal intensity lesion in left lung with mild mediastinal shift. On HRCT Thorax left lung volume was reduced with multiple variable sized cystic lesions in left upper lobe. The child underwent left upper lobe lobectomy at 3 months of age.

Grossly Cut section of left lower lobectomy section showed variable sized cystic spaces ranging in diameter from 0.5 to 1.5 cm.

Histopathological examination revealed cysts lined by ciliated cuboidal to stratified columnar epithelium with interspersed alveolar spaces with frequent transitions from thick cyst wall. Some cysts showed papillary projections with focal mucinous cell clusters.

Discussion

CCAM is a rare development anomaly and studies show >95% survival for patients after surgical management for all its subtypes. It can further undergo malignant transformation to Pleuropulmonary blastoma/Bronchoalveolar Carcinoma.

Conclusion

This case explains the importance of antenatal detection, grossing and histopathological evaluation in congenital cystic lesions to rule out any neoplastic transformation. Early surgical intervention offers better prognosis.

FINE NEEDLE ASPIRATION CYTOLOGY OF GANGLION CYST IN THE POPLITEAL FOSSA: A CASE REPORT

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Introduction:

Ganglion cysts are benign cystic lesions arising from the joint capsule or the tendon sheaths. They most commonly occur in the wrist and palm. Their occurrence in the popliteal fossa is rare. Clinically, cystic lesions in the popliteal region may mimic Baker's cyst, synovial cyst, lipoma or other soft tissue lesions. Fine needle aspiration cytology(FNAC) is a rapid, minimally invasive and cost effective diagnostic modality for evaluating such lesions.

Objectives:

To highlight the cytomorphological features of a ganglion cyst arising in the popliteal fossa and to emphasize the role of FNAC in establishing an accurate diagnosis.

Case report:

A 60 year old female presented with a painless swelling in the right popliteal fossa for two years, which had gradually increased in size. There was no history of trauma, pain or restriction of joint movements. On clinical examination, a soft, cystic, non tender swelling measuring approximately 4x3 cm was noted in the right popliteal fossa. FNAC was performed using a 22 gauge needle, yielding 2 ml of thick, clear gelatinous aspirate. Cytological smears stained with Giemsa stain revealed abundant myxoid background with histiocyte like cells with small, oval nuclei and abundant cytoplasm. No atypia or significant inflammatory infiltrate was seen.

Discussion:

Ganglion cysts show characteristic cytological findings of paucicellular smears with abundant myxoid material. Recognition of these features helps to diagnose it and distinguish from other cystic lesions.

Conclusion

FNAC is a simple and reliable diagnostic modality for ganglion cysts occurring at uncommon sites such as the popliteal fossa.

**UNRAVELLING THE DIAGNOSTIC DILEMMA OF SINO-NASAL SPINDLE CELL
TUMORS: A SERIES OF TWO CASES**

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Introduction

Spindle cell neoplasms of the sinonasal tract are rare and pose significant diagnostic challenges due to marked morphological overlap among benign and malignant entities. Accurate diagnosis is crucial for appropriate management.

Objectives

To highlight the diagnostic approach and emphasize the role of immunohistochemistry in differentiating rare spindle cell tumors of the nose and paranasal sinus.

Case Report

We describe two cases of sinonasal spindle cell neoplasms. The first case was a 32-year-old male presenting with nasal obstruction and facial pain. Histopathology revealed a high-grade spindle cell tumor arranged in storiform pattern with pleomorphism, necrosis, and mitotic activity. Tumor cells showed positivity for vimentin and negativity for S100, desmin, CD34, and PanCK, supporting a diagnosis of undifferentiated pleomorphic sarcoma.

The second case involved a 50-year-old male with nasal obstruction and episodic epistaxis. Initial biopsy suggested a malignant spindle cell lesion. Excision specimen revealed spindle cells with focal melanin pigment. Immunohistochemistry showed strong positivity for S100 and HMB45 and negativity for PanCK, P40, and P63, confirming malignant melanoma.

Discussion

Sinonasal spindle cell tumors encompass a broad differential diagnosis including sarcoma, melanoma, sarcomatoid carcinoma, and malignant peripheral nerve sheath tumor. Histomorphology alone may be insufficient due to overlapping features, particularly in small biopsies. A structured panel of immunohistochemical markers is indispensable for accurate classification.

Conclusion

Sinonasal spindle cell neoplasms represent a diagnostic challenge. Integration of clinical findings, detailed histopathological assessment, and targeted immunohistochemistry is essential for definitive diagnosis and optimal patient management.

ROLE OF FINE NEEDLE ASPIRATION CYTOLOGY IN HEAD AND NECK LESIONS AND ITS HISTOPATHOLOGICAL CORRELATION

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Introduction-

Head and neck lesions comprise a wide range of inflammatory, infectious, benign, and malignant conditions. Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) is a diagnostic technique widely used for the initial evaluation of these lesions, while histopathological examination (HPE) remains the gold standard for definitive diagnosis.

Objectives

To study the role of FNAC in head and neck lesions and its histopathological correlation. To establish the sensitivity, specificity and diagnostic efficacy of FNAC. To evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of FNAC by comparing it with HPE findings.

Material and methods

A prospective observational study done for one year from February 2025 to January 2026. A total of 80 cases underwent FNAC, followed by Histopathology Lab, SIMS, Hapur

Results

Among the 80 cases, females constituted 75% of the study population, and most affected age group was 21–30 years. Lymph nodes were the most commonly involved site (45%), followed by thyroid (23.8%), skin and soft tissues (16.3%) and salivary glands (15%). On FNAC, 42.5% cases were non-neoplastic, 25% benign, 27.5% malignant, and 5% non-diagnostic. FNAC showed a sensitivity of 100%, specificity of 69.2%, positive predictive value of 93.5%, negative predictive value of 100%, and overall diagnostic accuracy of 94.4%.

Discussion

The findings demonstrate a strong correlation between FNAC and histopathology in diagnosing head and neck lesions. FNAC proved highly sensitive in detecting malignancies. However, moderate specificity suggests that histopathological confirmation is necessary in suspicious cases.

Conclusion

The study revealed that although FNAC is a useful diagnostic tool, histopathology still remains the gold standard.

PP-80

A RARE VARIANT: IDENTIFYING AND MANAGING HER2- POSITIVE INVASIVE APOCRINE BREAST CANCER

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Introduction

Apocrine Carcinoma is an uncommon form of Breast cancer, representing 0.5-4% of all cases of Invasive Breast Carcinoma in women. Invasive Apocrine carcinoma is defined as Invasive carcinoma characterized by large cells with abundant eosinophilic granular cytoplasm and enlarged nuclei with prominent nucleoli

Case Report

A 40yrs female presented with hard lump in upper inner quadrant of breast for which modified radical mastectomy was done. We received MRM specimen measuring 22x14x6cm with overlying elliptical skin flap measuring 17x9.5cm bearing nipple areolar complex. On Microscopy , sections revealed neoplastic cells arranged in sheets exhibiting marked pleomorphism with abundant eosinophilic granular cytoplasm, vesicular nuclei and prominent nucleoli. Immunohistochemistry demonstrated negativity for estrogen and progesterone receptors , positive Her2neu expression and strong Androgen positivity

Discussion

As per World health Organization , breast cancer is categorized as invasive apocrine breast cancer when minimum of 90% of its cells display apocrine differentiation

Vranic et al. have proposed a molecular characterization of pure apocrine breast cancer defining it as a tumor expressing ARs while lacking ERs or PRs. pure apocrine cancer may exhibit either HER2 overexpression or either HER2 negativity. The primary treatment option involves surgery, which may entail breast- conserving surgery, mastectomy

Adjuvant treatment options such as hormonal therapy, radiotherapy, or chemotherapy are administered. HER2 and AR-positive patients have the option of receiving anti-HER2 and hormone therapy as a part of their adjuvant treatment.

Conclusion

Recognition of this rare subtype is important due to its unique receptor status and potential implications for targeted therapy.

EPITHELIOID MENINGIOMA: AN UNSUAL MORPHOLOGICAL VARIANT MIMICKING UNDIFFERENTIATED SARCOMA CREATING A DIAGNOSTIC DILEMMA

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Introduction

Epithelioid meningioma is a rare pediatric tumor with low incidence. Its epithelioid morphology and overlapping immunohistochemical profile may mimic undifferentiated sarcoma or metastatic tumors creating significant diagnostic challenges.

Objective

To present a rare case of epithelioid meningioma and highlight the diagnostic challenge caused by epithelioid morphology mimicking an undifferentiated sarcoma, emphasizing the role of histopathology and immunohistochemistry.

Case report

A 13-year-old male presented with headache, nausea, vomiting, left-sided hemiparesis for one month. MRI revealed a homogeneously enhancing extra-axial lesion in right temporo-parietal region. Patient underwent right fronto-temporo-parietal craniotomy with tumor excision.

Histopathology showed a cellular tumor with patternless architecture composed of monomorphic ovoid cells with scant eosinophilic cytoplasm and round nuclei. Branching capillaries, scattered mitoses, focal necrosis were noted. Initial immunohistochemistry showed CD34 positivity in vascular lining cells with Ki-67 index of ~5%.

Four years later, tumor recurred. Repeat excision revealed sheets of round to epithelioid cells with pseudoglandular architecture and intraluminal eosinophilic secretions. Tumor cells were positive for Pan-cytokeratin, vimentin, BCL-2, and CD99 with patchy EMA positivity, while S100, PR, CD34, TLE1, INI1, desmin, GFAP were negative. PET-CT showed no disease elsewhere.

Discussion

Sheets of epithelioid cells with pseudoglandular architecture and intraluminal eosinophilic secretions suggested epithelial differentiation. Diffuse pan-cytokeratin and patchy EMA positivity supported meningeal origin, while negativity for S100, CD34, TLE1, INI1, desmin, GFAP excluded other entities.

Conclusion

In the absence of systemic disease on PET-CT, morphological and immunohistochemical profile favored epithelioid meningioma over undifferentiated sarcoma, emphasizing the importance of detailed histopathology and broad immunohistochemical panel for accurate diagnosis.

BEYOND EXPECTED: METASTATIC BILATERAL ADULT GRANULOSA CELL TUMOUR OF THE OVARY IN A YOUNG FEMALE

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Introduction

Adult granulosa cell tumour is a malignant sex cord–stromal tumour of the ovary accounting for about 2% of all ovarian neoplasms. These tumours are usually unilateral, with bilateral involvement being rare. It commonly occurs in peri-menopausal women and may present with abdominal mass, or hormonal manifestations due to estrogen production. Rarely, it may be associated with ascites and pleural effusion, mimicking advanced ovarian malignancy.

Case presentation

A 33-year-old female presented with abdominal distension, anorexia, and breathlessness for three months. She had ascites and pleural effusion which was tapped and cytological examination resulted malignant cells in both, categorized as Category V (Malignant). CT scan demonstrated heterogeneously enhancing lobulated masses in the bilateral pelvic fossae with solid–cystic components, areas of necrosis, and omental caking. Subsequently, USG-guided FNAC from the left abdominopelvic mass suggested a malignant tumour with possibilities including granulosa cell tumour and adenocarcinoma. Immunocytochemistry performed on cell block of FNA were positive for inhibin, negative for CK7 and final diagnosis of granulosa cell tumor rendered.

The patient received six cycles of chemotherapy, followed by staging laparotomy. Bilateral ovarian masses sent for histopathological examination revealed granulosa cell tumour with omental metastasis.

Discussion and conclusion

This case highlights the rarity of metastatic bilateral granulosa cell tumour presenting in a young female with ascites and pleural effusion. It reinforces the pivotal role of minimally invasive procedures such as fluid cytology and USG-guided FNAC in early recognition, enabling timely diagnosis, accurate staging, and prompt patient management.

Keywords

Adult granulosa cell tumour; FNAC; Cytology; Bilateral; Inhibin.

PP-83

Esophageal manifestation of behcet's disease in a pediatric patient.

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Post graduate institute of child health

Introduction

Behçet's syndrome is a chronic relapsing systemic vasculitis involving arteries and veins of various calibers. While mucocutaneous and ocular manifestations are well recognized, gastrointestinal involvement is uncommon, and esophageal involvement is particularly rare, especially in pediatric patients.

Case Report

A 13 year old girl presented with recurrent oral ulcers, odynophagia, dysphagia, genital ulcer and conjunctival congestion. Upper gastrointestinal endoscopy revealed circumferential superficial ulcers in the esophagus. Histopathological examination from esophageal biopsy demonstrated multiple tissue bits lined by stratified squamous epithelium with reactive atypia and suprabasal clefting. Subepithelium shows mixed inflammatory infiltrate comprising of neutrophils and lymphocytes. No granulomas or fungal organisms identified. These findings, in conjunction with the clinical presentation and exclusion of infectious and other inflammatory etiologies, supported the diagnosis of esophageal involvement in Behçet's syndrome.

Discussion

Esophageal involvement in Behçet's syndrome is rare and may histologically mimic other causes of ulcerative esophagitis. Recognition of vasculitic changes, neutrophil-predominant inflammation, and exclusion of infectious or granulomatous pathology is essential for accurate diagnosis.

Conclusion

Recognition of this rare gastrointestinal manifestation is important for early diagnosis and appropriate management, particularly in pediatric patients.

FRONTAL LOBE EPENDYMOMA IN A 65-YEAR-OLD MALE: A CASE REPORT

Dr. Tamanna Goyal, Dr. Pooja, Dr. Permeet Kaur Bagga.

GMC Amritsar

Introduction

Ependymomas are neuroepithelial tumors that typically arise from the lining of the ventricular system or the central canal of the spinal cord. While more common in children and usually found in the posterior fossa, supratentorial (brain hemisphere) ependymomas can occur in adults. These lesions often present as "space-occupying lesions" (SOL) and require surgical intervention and histopathological confirmation for definitive diagnosis and grading.

Case Presentation

A 65-year-old male presented to the department of pathology, GNDH, ASR with neurological symptoms, including head shaking, shouting, and whole-body trembling/shivering lasting 3–4 minutes (first episode). This progressed to a generalized seizure, a fall, and loss of bowel control (incontinence). On radiology, a space-occupying lesion in the left frontal lobe. On histopathology examination, atypical cuboidal cells forming characteristic perivascular pseudorosettes and true ependymal rosettes. The tumor exhibited several high-grade features, most notably marked nuclear pleomorphism, increased nuclear-cytoplasmic ratio, moderate amount of eosinophilic cytoplasm, irregular nuclear contour, granular chromatin & inconspicuous nucleoli & brisk mitotic activity. Extensive areas of hemorrhage, necrosis, and hemosiderin deposition suggesting an aggressive (likely Anaplastic/Grade 3) tumor.

Conclusion

The histopathological impression is consistent with an Ependymoma. Given the brisk mitotic activity and presence of necrosis, this case represents a high-grade primary brain tumor requiring close oncological follow-up. Immunohistochemistry was done. Post-operative management will likely involve a combination of radiotherapy and monitoring for recurrence.

Keywords

Ependymoma, Perivascular rosettes, Pseudo-rosettes, Anaplastic High grade

**JOURNEY THROUGH THE DIVERSE FACES OF ORAL SQUAMOUS CELL CARCINOMA:
AN INSTITUTIONAL STUDY**

Dr. Tanvi Singla, Dr. Mala Kamboj, Dr Anjali Narwal, Dr Anju Devi.

PGIDS ROHTAK

Introduction

Oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC) is the most common malignant tumor of the head and neck region, accounting for the majority of oral malignancies. Although conventional OSCC is the predominant form, several histopathological variants are recognized such as verrucous carcinoma, adenoid (acantholytic) squamous cell carcinoma, spindle cell carcinoma, adenosquamous carcinoma, basaloid squamous cell carcinoma, and papillary squamous cell carcinoma. Identification of these variants is important because their histomorphological features may influence diagnosis, treatment planning, and clinical outcomes. This poster presents a series of cases highlighting different histopathological variants of OSCC observed in our institution.

Objectives

1) To analyze the clinico-epidemiological characteristics (age, gender, and smoking habits) of patients and compare them with different histomorphological types and histopathological grade. of OSCC

Case Report

We present histopathologically confirmed variants of OSCC retrieved from the archives of the Department of Oral Pathology at our institution. Clinical details including age, gender, lesion site, and habit history were recorded. Hematoxylin and eosin–stained sections were evaluated to identify the characteristic histomorphological features of each variant. Immunohistochemical staining with the proliferative marker Ki 67 was performed to assess tumor cell proliferation.

Discussion

Histopathological variants of oral squamous cell carcinoma can pose significant diagnostic challenges. As these variants differ in biological behavior, prognosis, metastatic potential, and treatment outcomes, early recognition and accurate diagnosis are essential for appropriate patient management and better prognosis.

Conclusion

This poster emphasizes the diverse histomorphological spectrum of OSCC and highlights the importance of recognizing its rare variants in routine histopathological practice. Early and accurate identification can significantly influence prognosis and treatment outcomes.

**WHEN ARCHITECTURE PREDICTS BEHAVIOUR: RECOGNISING THE HOBNAIL
VARIANT OF PAPILLARY THYROID CARCINOMA**

Dr. Vaishali Sharma, Dr. Kavita Mardi

IGMC SHIMLA HIMACHAL PRADESH

INTRODUCTION

Papillary thyroid carcinoma (PTC) comprises variants with differing biological behavior. The hobnail variant is an uncommon subtype characterized by loss of cellular polarity and apically placed nuclei producing a hobnail appearance, corresponding to structurally high-grade morphology in WHO classification.

OBJECTIVES

To describe clinicopathological features of hobnail variant PTC and its diagnostic significance.

CASE REPORT

A 43-year-old male presented with thyroid swelling. Imaging showed a heterogeneous left-lobe lesion with cystic areas. FNAC suggested an adenomatoid nodule, and a subtotal thyroidectomy was performed.

Microscopy revealed papillary and micropapillary architecture with >30% tumor cells showing hobnail morphology, nuclear grooves, and intranuclear inclusions. Psammoma bodies with capsular and lymphovascular invasion were present.

Immunohistochemistry showed positivity for MUC1, CK7, and p53 with a low Ki-67 index.

DISCUSSION

WHO defines hobnail variant PTC by $\geq 30\%$ hobnail cells and categorizes it among differentiated carcinomas with high-grade features. It carries increased recurrence risk and is frequently associated with BRAF V600E and TERT promoter alterations. Cytology may underestimate this entity, making histopathology essential for risk stratification.

CONCLUSION

Recognition of the hobnail variant of PTC is important due to its clinical implications and need for close postoperative follow-up.

PP-87

Angiomatoid Fibrous Histiocytoma of the Thigh in a Young Adult: A Diagnostic Challenge.

Dr. Vandana, Dr. Sonam Sharma, Dr. Geetika Khanna, Dr. Dharmendra Kumar Singh.

Vardhman Mahavir Medical College and Safdarjung Hospital, New Delhi

Introduction

Angiomatoid Fibrous Histiocytoma (AFH) is a rare soft tissue neoplasm of intermediate malignant potential that typically arises in the superficial soft tissues of the extremities in children and adolescents. Its variable morphology and overlapping histological features with several benign and malignant soft tissue tumors often make the diagnosis challenging.

Objectives

To highlight the diagnostic conundrum of AFH occurring at an atypical site and age group, and emphasize the importance of histopathological evaluation with clinicoradiological correlation in establishing the correct diagnosis.

Case Report

A 32-year-old male presented with a painful swelling in the mid-left thigh for the last 2 years. The lesion was initially a small painless mass excised at a local facility, but it recurred after 11 months. MRI revealed a well-defined subcutaneous lesion measuring approximately 1.5 cm with heterogeneous signal intensity. Biopsy demonstrated nodular proliferation of spindle to ovoid histiocytoid cells with characteristic blood-filled pseudovascular spaces and a prominent peripheral lymphoid cuff within a fibrous pseudocapsule. These features were diagnostic of AFH.

Discussion

AFH can mimic several entities due to its hemorrhagic spaces, myxoid areas, and inflammatory infiltrate. Important differentials include vascular lesions, myxoid soft tissue tumors, small round cell tumors, and spindle cell lesions. Recognition of the triad of histopathological features along with clinical and radiological findings is critical for diagnosis.

Conclusion

This case underscores the importance of considering AFH in the differential diagnosis of recurrent superficial soft tissue masses even in adults. Early recognition and accurate diagnosis are essential for guiding appropriate management and preventing recurrence.

TITLE: DESMOPLASTIC FIBROBLASTOMA OF MANDIBLE: REPORT OF A RARE CASE

Dr. Varun K K, Dr. Anju Devi, Dr. Anjali Narwal, Dr. Mala Kambo.

PGIDS, ROHTAK

Objectives

1. To present a rare case of intraoral desmoplastic fibroblastoma involving the mandible in a young patient.
2. To highlight the clinicopathological, radiographic, and immunohistochemical features important for accurate diagnosis of this rare lesion.

Case report

A 20-year-old male presented with a swelling on the left side of the face that had been gradually increasing in size over a period of three years. Clinical examination revealed a diffuse, bony hard, non-tender swelling over the left side of the mandible with no associated alleviating or aggravating factors. Intraoral examination showed obliteration of the buccal vestibule extending from the region of 33 to 37. Radiographic evaluation demonstrated a partially ill-defined lesion with mixed radiolucent–radiopaque areas. Contrast-enhanced computed tomography revealed a heterogeneous density involving the left mandible. Histopathological examination showed an encapsulated connective tissue lesion composed of stellate-shaped fibroblasts with eosinophilic cytoplasm scattered within a densely collagenized stroma, with areas of hyalinization. Special staining with Masson's trichrome showed strong positivity in the collagen bundles and hyalinized areas. Immunohistochemical analysis demonstrated diffuse positivity for vimentin and negativity for β -catenin, MUC4, SMA, CD34, and S-100, supporting the diagnosis of desmoplastic fibroblastoma.

Discussion

Desmoplastic fibroblastoma is a rare benign tumor of fibroblastic or myofibroblastic origin, with very few cases reported in the oral cavity. Clinically, it presents as a slow-growing, painless mass that can mimic other fibrous lesions of the oral and maxillofacial region. Histopathological findings of hypocellular dense collagenous stroma with spindle or stellate fibroblasts are characteristic of this lesion. Immunohistochemical positivity for vimentin and negativity for markers such as β -catenin, SMA, CD34, and S-100 help in confirming the diagnosis and differentiating it from other fibrous tumors.

Conclusion

Desmoplastic fibroblastoma is a rare benign tumor that may present as a well-circumscribed mass in the oral and maxillofacial region, often posing a diagnostic challenge due to its clinical and radiographic resemblance to other fibrous lesions and its histopathological similarity to low-grade fibromyxoid sarcoma. Histopathological examination along with special staining and immunohistochemistry plays a crucial role in establishing a definitive diagnosis. Awareness of this rare entity is important to avoid misdiagnosis and unnecessary aggressive treatment.

PP-89:

FNAC OF SKIN AND SUBCUTIS: SPECTRUM OF LESIONS REPORTED AT A DISTRICT HOSPITAL

Dr. Sneha Singh, Dr. Snigdha Goel, Dr. Liza Joshi

Background

Although surgical excision is more prevalent at peripheral health care facilities, FNAC of the skin and subcutis is standard protocol in multidisciplinary tertiary centers. Unless contraindicated, all such lesions are subjected to FNAC ensuring rapid, minimally invasive screening.

Objective

1. Evaluate malignancies diagnosed on FNAC of skin and subcutis; correlate with clinical diagnoses 2. Categorize cytological diagnosis of other benign lesions.

Material and methods

Retrospective analysis of skin FNACs was performed (Jan–Dec 2025). Slides and records for malignant, suspicious, and indeterminate lesions were retrieved and reviewed. Benign cases were categorized by pathology, including cystic, inflammatory, and infective lesions, alongside non-neoplastic tumors.

Results

Of 2,409 total procedures, 685 FNACs (28.4%) were performed on cutaneous and subcutaneous lesions. Lipomatosis (18.5%) and inflammatory cases (10%) were excluded from categorization. Malignancy was identified in 14 patients, comprising basal cell carcinoma (n=6), squamous cell carcinoma (n=3), malignant melanoma (n=2), and single cases of malignant mesenchymal and poorly differentiated carcinoma. Six cases were reported as indeterminate or highly suspicious for neoplasia. Benign pathologies were dominated by epidermal cysts (40.72%) and ganglion cysts (13.57%), while 23.5% of lesions were identified as tumors of adnexal, spindle cell, or fibro histiocytic origin.

Conclusions

- Diagnostic Utility: FNAC is an essential, minimally invasive protocol for the mandatory screening of nodules, papules, and patches.
- Malignancy Screening: It reliably differentiates primary and metastatic disease, enabling streamlined workup and management.
- Therapeutic Monitoring: Beyond oncology, it allows for the accurate reassessment of inflammatory and infectious lesions following treatment.
- FNAC of skin & subcutis is diagnostically relevant even at secondary health care facilities and should be included as a standard protocol.

PP-90

PLEOMORPHIC LEIOMYOSARCOMA

Dr.Karan Bhatia,Dr Manas Madan,Dr.K.S.Gill,Dr. Vikas Sharma

SGRDIMSR,Amritsar

Introduction

Pleomorphic leiomyosarcoma (PLMS) is a rare, high-grade morphological variant of leiomyosarcoma, representing a malignant mesenchymal tumour of smooth muscle differentiation. It accounts for approximately 8–10% of soft tissue sarcomas and predominantly affects elderly individuals, with peak incidence in the seventh to eighth decades. PLMS can arise in the retroperitoneum, abdominal cavity, large vessels, mediastinum, scalp, and extremities.

Objectives

To describe the clinicopathological and immunohistochemical features of a case of pleomorphic leiomyosarcoma involving the distal upper limb.

Material and Method

A 72-year-old male presented with a gradually progressive, painless swelling in the distal left arm for one year. Magnetic resonance imaging demonstrated a well-defined heterogeneous soft tissue mass suggestive of a mesenchymal tumour. Excision biopsy was performed, followed by detailed gross examination, histopathological evaluation using routine haematoxylin and eosin staining, and immunohistochemical analysis.

Results

Grossly, a single grey-yellow to grey-brown soft tissue mass measuring $9 \times 8 \times 5$ cm was received, with a firm grey-white cut surface and multiple haemorrhagic areas. Microscopy revealed a malignant mesenchymal neoplasm composed of oval to spindle-shaped tumour cells arranged in interlacing bundles and intersecting fascicles. Marked pleomorphism, vesicular chromatin, prominent nucleoli, moderate cytoplasm, brisk mitotic activity, haemorrhage, and necrosis were noted. Immunohistochemistry showed diffuse positivity for smooth muscle actin and focal positivity for h-caldesmon and desmin, while S100, CD34, myogenin, MyoD1, MDM2, and TFE3 were negative.

Discussion and Conclusion

PLMS poses diagnostic challenges due to morphological overlap with other high-grade sarcomas. Immunohistochemistry is essential for confirming smooth muscle differentiation and establishing a definitive diagnosis

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The Annual Conference of the North-West Chapter of the Indian Association of Pathologists and Microbiologists (NWIAPM-2026) is a prestigious academic event centred on the theme "Current Insights in Pathology." Guided by the motto "Inquisitive Minds, Nurturing Science," the conference aims to promote scientific exchange and critical discourse among Pathologists, clinicians, researchers and postgraduate students, while highlighting recent advances in the field through expert-led sessions. The conference is being organised in collaboration with the Regional Society of Pathologists-IAPM (Haryana Chapter) by the Department of Pathology, Pt. B.D. Sharma Post Graduate Institute of Medical Sciences (PGIMS), Rohtak, a premier tertiary care teaching institute of North India, renowned for excellence in medical education, patient care and research. Rohtak is a prominent medical, academic and educational hub of the region, offering an ideal setting for a scientific meeting of this stature

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